

SPARROW

SOLID PREPAREDNESS AND RESILIENCE
FOR ROBUST OPERATIONS DURING
DISASTER WILDERNESS

Deliverable: D2.1

Gap Analysis and Best Practices for Emergency Communications and Critical Infrastructure preparedness under digital breakdowns.

Work Package: 2

Participatory Co-designed SPARROW Architecture

31 August 2025

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ABSTRACT	<p>This report presents key findings from the SPARROW project on the resilience of emergency communication and critical infrastructure during digital disruptions. Based on research, surveys, interviews and case studies from Nicosia, Pilsen, and Trikala, it identifies major vulnerabilities, such as fragmented coordination and outdated systems, and highlights effective practices, including integrated platforms and cross-sector exercises. The insights support strategic recommendations to enhance preparedness, cybersecurity, and digital resilience across Europe.</p>		

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
3GPP MCX	Third Generation Partnership Project - Mission critical
ADRASEC	Association Départementale des Radioamateurs au Service de la Sécurité Civile
AI	Artificial intelligence
AMS	Aerial Mission System
ARECOM	Communications Regulatory Authority
BTS	Base Transceiver Station
CAP	Common Alerting Protocol
CAQDAS	Computer Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software
CESER	Cascading Effects Scenario BuildER
CI	Critical infrastructure
CIIP	Critical information infrastructure protection
CIP	Critical infrastructure protection
CITWIN	City Digital Twin
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 19
D2D	Device-to-device
DDoS	Distributed denial of service
DORA	Digital Operational Resilience Act
DTN	Delay tolerant network
ECOMAPP	Emergency communication mobile App

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EECC	European Electronic Communications Code
EENA	European Emergency Number Association
eICS	Extended Intensive Care Service
EMC	Emergency communication
EMER5G	Self-powered Ruggedised Mobile 5G Network for Emergency Internet Provision
EMPEER	Emergency Communication Messaging Protocol through Emergency Peer-to-peer network
EMPS	Enhanced mobile phone system
ETC	Emergency Telecommunications Cluster
ETSI EMTEL	Emergency Communications
EU	European Union
FR	First Responders
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSMA	Global System for Mobile Communications Association
GSO	Geostationary orbit
ICS	Industrial control systems
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IDS	Intrusion detection system
IoPST	Internet of Things for Public Safety
IoT	Internet of things

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IRS	Integrated rescue system
ISCRAM	Information Systems for Crisis Response and Management
ISP	Internet service provider
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
KOPIS	Krajské operační a informační středisko (Regional Operational and Informational Centre)
LEA	Law enforcement agencies
LoRa	Long range
LoRaWAN	Long Range Wide Area Network
LPWAN	Low Power Wide Area Network
LTE	Long-term evolution
M	Mean
MANET	Mobile ad hoc Network
MCOP	Mission critical open platform
NDN	Next Generation Network
NGO	Non-governmental organizations
NIS2 Directive	Network and Information Systems Directive 2
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
PSC	Private security company
PUC	Pilot use case
SARCALL	Multi-Agency Search and Rescue (SAR) Incident Management Platform
SCADA	Supervisory control and data acquisition
SD	Standard deviation

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SED	Signal-area Expansion Drone
SMS	Short message service
SSH	Social science and humanities
TETRA	Terrestrial Trunked Radio
TSF	Télécoms Sans Frontières
UAV	Unmanned aerial vehicle
UMUX	Usability Metric for User Experience
UPS	Universal Power Supply
VASE	Assessment Synoptic Engine
VHF	Very High Frequency
VSAT	Very Small Aperture Terminal
WebEOC	Web-based Emergency Operations Center
WiMAX	Worldwide Interoperability for Microwave Access
WIS	Warning Information System
WLAN	Wireless Local Area Network
WMO	World Meteorological Organization
WP	Work package
WP2	Work Package 2
WSN	Wireless sensor Networks

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Executive summary

This deliverable “Gap analysis and best practices for emergency communications and critical infrastructure” presents the main findings of Tasks 2.1 and 2.2 of the SPARROW projects, which focus on identifying vulnerabilities and documenting good practices related to emergency communication systems and the resilience of critical infrastructures during digital disruptions. The analysis combines desk research with field interviews, in addition to analysis of pilot use cases in three pilot sites: Nicosia, Pilsen, and Trikala.

The work carried out under Task 2.1 maps existing emergency communication systems, tools, and channels, and identifies common gaps such as fragmented coordination, outdated technologies, and weak inclusion of vulnerable groups. Task 2.2 examines how critical infrastructures react to digital breakdowns, with attention to cascading effects, lack of redundancy, and limited scenario planning.

The report highlights several good practices, including the use of integrated digital platforms, multi-language alerts, resilience dashboards, and cross-sector simulations. It also identifies recurring needs such as stronger coordination mechanisms, shared standards, and better integration of cybersecurity into crisis planning.

The conclusions feed into a set of strategic recommendations aimed at improving preparedness, communication, and cooperation across agencies and sectors. The findings will serve as a foundation for the design of the SPARROW platform and support the project's broader goal of strengthening digital resilience in Europe.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background and Context of the SPARROW project

Critical infrastructures such as energy, communication, transport, finance, and public services are essential to the daily functioning of modern societies. These systems have become increasingly interconnected, combining physical networks with digital technologies to deliver services more efficiently. However, this interdependence also brings new risks. Failure in one area can quickly trigger cascading effects across sectors, causing widespread disruption and compromising public safety.

In recent years, several large-scale events have demonstrated the scale of these risks. For example, the North American blackout in 2003 and the Western European power outage in 2006 showed how vulnerable electricity grids can be. The cyberattacks on Estonia in 2007 highlighted the potential impact of digital threats on national infrastructure. More recently, Storm Daniel in 2023 severely disrupted digital and physical infrastructure across Southern Europe and North Africa. On 28 April 2025, a major blackout in the Iberian Peninsula left parts of Spain and Portugal without electricity, telecommunications, and emergency services for hours. In June 2025, Chile experienced a nationwide blackout affecting more than 90 percent of the population, and in July, a similar disruption occurred in the Czech Republic. These examples as shown in the Figure 1 underline the urgent need for more coordinated and resilient systems capable of responding to both technical failures and external threats.

Figure 1 Timeline of selected blackouts

Although national and European institutions have introduced various frameworks to protect critical infrastructure, efforts often remain fragmented. Differences in risk assessment, emergency planning, and coordination mechanisms continue to limit the effectiveness of cross-sector and cross-border responses. The SPARROW project was launched to address these gaps. It aims to strengthen the resilience of critical infrastructures and emergency communication systems during digital

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disruptions by bringing together a wide range of actors. These include First Responders, infrastructure operators, civil protection services, local authorities, and other security practitioners.

This deliverable supports SPARROW's objectives by identifying operational gaps, mapping best practices, and providing a foundation for the technical and strategic development of the SPARROW architecture.

1.2. Purpose, scope and structure of the deliverable

This deliverable provides a baseline assessment of current practices, challenges, and good practices in the fields of emergency communication and critical infrastructure resilience under digital disruption scenarios. It contributes to the objectives of Work Package 2 (WP2) by supporting the design of the SPARROW platform with evidence-based insights and practical recommendations drawn from both literature and field-level experience. The aim is to ensure that the future architecture developed through SPARROW is grounded in real operational needs and can be adapted to different crisis settings across Europe.

The work brings together the findings from two complementary tasks. Task 2.1 focuses on emergency communication systems, analysing how First Responders and other key actors coordinate during digital breakdowns. This task reviews academic and institutional literature, identifies emerging technologies, and gathers lessons from past crises. It also integrates feedback from SPARROW partners and external stakeholders to highlight common obstacles and current limitations in crisis communication. Task 2.2 shifts the focus to the robustness of critical infrastructures, exploring how different types of infrastructures manage service continuity and mitigate cascading failures when digital systems are compromised. This part of the analysis is based on both desk research and interviews with crisis managers, infrastructure operators, local authorities, and civil protection professionals.

Together, these two tasks provide a comprehensive overview of systemic vulnerabilities and promising practices across two closely linked domains. The findings are used to identify operational gaps, support knowledge transfer, and guide the development of scalable, user-informed solutions for the SPARROW platform.

The structure of the report, as explained in the Figure 2, follows the sequence of the research and analytical work carried out. Chapter 2 focuses on emergency communication systems, presenting a review of emerging technologies, a gap analysis, and an overview of good practices, including findings from literature, stakeholder surveys, and pilot sites. Chapter 3 shifts to critical infrastructure resilience, outlining key threat typologies, vulnerabilities identified through literature and field interviews, and examples of preparedness strategies in use. Chapter 4 explores cross-cutting themes such as ethical considerations, regulatory constraints, and community engagement. Chapter 5 presents strategic recommendations addressed to policymakers, civil protection authorities, infrastructure operators, and researchers. Chapter 6 concludes the report by summarising key insights and highlighting SPARROW's contribution to improving crisis resilience through a participatory, evidence-based approach.

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Figure 2 Methodology and scope of the analyses

This deliverable employs a mixed-method, inclusive, and participatory approach, with adequate triangulation to ensure credible, reliable, and unbiased findings. The methodology encompasses a comprehensive and systematic review of existing literature, case studies, in addition to engaging some stakeholders in interviews to have their input and recommendations. These methodologies, as applied in the task 2.1 and task 2.2 are explained in the Figure 3.

Figure 3 Methodology flowchart for D2.1 / Task 2.1 and Task 2.2

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1.2.1. The methodology used within Task 2.1

The methodology used to achieve the objectives of Task 2.1. (Figure 3) can be characterised as a standard mixed-method approach to obtain a comprehensive view and analytically complementary outputs concerning the latest trends in EMC and their tools, systems and channels. Hence, approaches focusing on the role of FRs and key stakeholders, reflecting on their experience and practice, and shifting the intention from the actor to the structural level were thus chosen. This level of analysis is captured primarily through the critical literature review and its interpretation.

The sub-methodological approaches and their utilisation are characterised in more detail in the subsections devoted to them. In this section devoted to the general characteristics of the methods used and how the analysis itself is processed and interpreted, we consider it crucial to note that the approach to the data is based on the logic of text analysis and is thus based on a combination of human, machine and AI-assisted computer-driven reading.

AI tools were also used to correct stylistics and grammar (specifically DeepL¹ and Grammarly²). All data fed into the AI tools (whether for stylistics and grammar correction or cases of analytical assistance) did not come from internal or non-public documents and was always of public character. The output provided by the AI was always checked by human proofreading.

The literature review:

The literature analysis for Task 2.1 was carried out in several successive steps. The analysis was conducted twice to achieve maximum transparency, complementarity, and comparability, and different approaches and procedures were used each time. The findings, conclusions and main lines of argument of the two approaches were then juxtaposed.

The first step was to search for data relevant to the topic of interest manually, with broadly defined selection criteria (e.g. not older than 15 years, available, related to topic, English language). This data corpus typically includes academic journals, conference proceedings, books, reports, government and industry websites, news articles and blogs. Thus, this data corpus follows the logic that its data relate to case studies and best practices, human-centred approaches to EMC, their network design and optimization, or the characteristics of technological innovations and solutions. This data corpus contains 53 documents.

Subsequently, a combination of human and machine reading was used. AI tools were utilized where the character of the document allowed it. Specifically, the NotebookLM³ tool was used to perform an initial thematic analysis of the documents. To achieve this, the following prompts served as inputs:

- "Identify the latest emergency communication systems, tools and channels."
- "Spotlight best practices."
- "Identify emergency communication systems, tools and channels related to digital breakdowns."

¹<https://www.deepl.com/en/translator> DeepL. (n.d.). DeepL Translate: The world's most accurate translator. <https://www.deepl.com/en/translator>.

²<https://app.grammarly.com/> Grammarly. (n.d.). Grammarly: Free AI writing assistance.

³<https://notebooklm.google.com/> Google. (n.d.). NotebookLM. <https://notebooklm.google.com/>

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- "Spotlight best practices."

The results were then checked by human reading. A classical manual approach to text analysis was used: deductive coding structured according to the above-mentioned and used prompts. The outputs were assigned to thematic clusters and quantified in a subsequent step.

In addition to analysing the content and the basic line of argument in the data corpus, the standard procedure for creating a literature review and its thematic interconnections - quantitative analysis of keywords contained in the data corpus - was used. Specifically, keywords were manually extracted and then subsequently unified for analytical simplification. Subsequently, they were processed in the same way as the previous data, i.e. by cluster analysis and subsequent quantification. These two procedures thus made it possible to capture the underlying structure and thematic interconnectivity of the EMC-related texts.

A second literature review was subsequently carried out differently to ensure the transparency of the results. In the initiation phase of the analysis, AI tools were used, and the following prompts were given:

- "Prepare texts that deal with the latest emergency communication systems, tools, and channels."
- "Highlight current best practices"
- "Limit search results to the last 3 years."
- "List the 50 most relevant texts"
- "For each text, if possible, provide the main arguments, brief content, and summarize the abstract"

The results of the AI-assisted literature review were then manually checked by human reading. For some texts, it was impossible to fulfil prompt 5 using AI. It was subsequently completed using human reading and inductive coding, where this was not realized. Keywords were also extracted from all 50 texts as part of the manual processing. In the last step, the data corpus thus created was worked with in the same way as the first - i.e. primarily at the level of cluster, network and thematic analysis of its content. The results of the two separately conducted literature reviews were then juxtaposed

The survey:

The primary objective of this survey was to evaluate various aspects of emergency communication systems, channels and tools, focusing on their usability, performance and relevance in emergency communications, with a particular focus on digital breakdowns. The questionnaire was therefore structured around two key scenarios.

- The most recent crisis in which the participating organization was involved.
- A hypothetical digital breakdown scenario.

These scenarios provided a framework within which to assess the practical application and perceived effectiveness of emergency communication mechanisms.

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Concerning its design, the survey took approximately 15 minutes to complete. Before participating, respondents were presented with an informed consent form which outlined the purpose of the study, the data processing procedures and the assurances regarding confidentiality, anonymity and data protection in accordance with GDPR regulations. Participation was entirely voluntary, and consent was required to proceed with the survey.

Concerning materials and measures, the questionnaire was developed based on insights from a comprehensive literature review conducted during an earlier stage of the project. It underwent several iterative validation steps with task group members to ensure it aligned with the research objectives. The final version was implemented using LimeSurvey⁴, an online survey platform.

The survey included both open-ended and closed-ended questions and was structured into the following sections:

- Demographic information
- Details of a recent emergency event experienced by the participant
- Evaluation of communication systems, channels, and tools
 - Frequency of use during the incident
 - Perceived relevance
 - Usability and performance

Measurement scales were applied as follows:

- *Frequency of use*: Rated on a five-point Likert scale (1 = Never, 5 = Daily), with a “Not applicable” option.
- *Relevance*: Participants ranked each system, channel, or tool according to its importance during the incident.
- *Usability and performance*: Assessed using the Usability Metric for User Experience (UMUX) on a seven-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 7 = Strongly Agree), with a “Not applicable” option.

A total of 67 professionals completed the survey either fully or partially. All participants worked in emergency management or related fields and represented a wide variety of institutions and countries. Participants ranged in age from 20 to 70 years, with an average age of 43.61 years (SD = 10.79), reflecting diverse levels of professional experience. Most respondents identified as male (82.1%, n = 55), while 17.9% (n = 12) identified as female.

Participants reported a high level of academic qualification, with an average education level of 6.37 on an 8-point scale. The majority held a master’s degree (61.2%), followed by bachelor’s degrees (13.4%), doctoral degrees (6.0%), and upper secondary or post-secondary non-tertiary education

⁴<https://survey.johanniter.at/index.php/753828> Johanniter. (n.d.). SPARROW Emergency Communication Evaluation Questionnaire. <https://survey.johanniter.at/index.php/753828>.

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(19.4%). No participants reported having only primary or lower-secondary education. Thus, Table 1 summarizes the distribution of participants by their highest level of education.

Table 1 Distribution of the sample regarding the highest level of education

Level of Education	Frequency	Percentage
No formal education	-	-
Primary education / Elementary school	-	-
Lower secondary education / Middle school	-	-
Upper secondary school / High school	11	16.4
Post-secondary non-tertiary education	2	3.0
Bachelor's degree of equivalent	9	13.4
Masters's degree or equivalent	41	61.2
Doctoral degree (PhD) or equivalent	4	6.0

Respondents came from a wide range of countries, with the highest representation from the Czech Republic, followed by Austria. Others were based in France, Germany, Greece, Israel, Italy, Sweden, and the United Kingdom. Institutional affiliations included national and regional civil protection authorities, fire and rescue services, Red Cross organizations, municipal governments, police departments, emergency medical services, and NGOs.

Participants reported roles across multiple operational levels: 52.2% at the operational level, 55.2% at the strategic level, and 61.2% at the tactical level. Some also indicated involvement in research and technical infrastructure activities.

Professional experience in emergency management ranged from less than one year to 39 years, with an average of 13.07 years. The most reported value was 20 years, noted by nine respondents. Most participants fell within the 10–20-year experience range.

Thus, the survey assessed emergency communication systems' usability, performance, and relevance—especially during digital breakdowns—by gathering insights from 67 diverse emergency management professionals across multiple countries, using scenario-based questions that captured their experiences, roles, and perceptions within real and hypothetical crisis contexts.

Pilot use case analyses

To provide an analysis of individual pilot use cases, the following methodology was employed. Firstly, the relevant findings from the literature review were accompanied by an AI-made in-depth analysis, complemented by information from the relevant pilot scenarios, as set in project proposal.

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Afterwards, this analysis of individual sections, compiled and overseen by human professionals in the individual pilot sites, was drafted.

In accordance with the findings of the literature review conducted for Task 2.1, the use of artificial intelligence tools, specifically NotebookLM and ChatGPT, were employed for the analysis of the uploaded responses from the reviewed documents. The results of the AI analysis were subsequently compared with the findings of the literature review and the pilot use case scenario. As source document 1, description of individual pilot case was used; source document 2 represented the full text of aggregated results of the literature review in the individual category.

Information regarding the alignment of each use case was obtained through the following prompts:

- How does the SPARROW use case (source document 1) align with the latest EMC trends (source document 2; i.e. emerging trends)?
- Are there any specific tools or methodologies mentioned in the literature (source document 2; i.e. best practices) that could be adapted or applied to the SPARROW project (source document 1)?
- Are there any potential risks or challenges associated with the SPARROW use case (source document 1) that could be mitigated by drawing on existing search? (source document 2; i.e. shortcomings)?

For each AI tool, the same prompts and the same source documents were uploaded. The results were manually checked and compiled under human supervision. Then, an internal expert discussion took place to get the most objective view of the situation.

1.2.2. The methodology used within Task 2.2

The methodology applied in Task 2.2 was based on a combination of desk research and field-based qualitative data collection. The first phase involved a comprehensive literature review aimed at establishing a solid theoretical and analytical foundation. This review drew on reputable scientific databases such as ISCRAM⁵, Web of Science⁶, Scopus⁷, and HAL⁸, to access peer-reviewed publications focused on critical infrastructure resilience, crisis management, digital disruptions, and business continuity. Among 100 documents, a total of 32 scientific papers were selected for in depth review of their relevance to the project's scope. This step allowed us to identify key challenges, methodological approaches, and conceptual frameworks used by the research community.

In the second phase, a series of qualitative interviews were conducted with European stakeholders to gather real-world insights on how digital disruptions have affected critical infrastructures. Interviewees included professionals involved in local government crisis management, critical infrastructure operations or supervision, and civil protection networks. They represented a variety

⁵<https://idl.iscram.org/> International Association for Information Systems for Crisis Response and Management (ISCRAM). (n.d.). ISCRAM Digital Library. <https://idl.iscram.org/>.

⁶<https://www.webofscience.com/> Clarivate. (n.d.). Web of Science. <https://www.webofscience.com/>.

⁷<https://www.scopus.com/> Elsevier. (n.d.). Scopus. <https://www.scopus.com/>.

⁸<https://hal.science/> HAL/CCSD. (n.d.). HAL: Multidisciplinary open archive. <https://hal.science/>.

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of roles, from first responders and emergency services to local authorities responsible for continuity planning and inter-agency coordination.

The report aims to bridge academic knowledge with operational experience. By combining findings from the literature with insights gathered through interviews, the analysis will highlight both conceptual frameworks and practical realities. This methodological approach ensured that the project outcomes are anchored in actual practices, challenges, and needs observed on the ground across diverse infrastructure sectors and governance contexts.

The literature review:

For the literature review for task 2.2, it builds on the literature review conducted in T2.1 by deepening the analysis of how digitalisation is transforming both the risk landscape and the resilience capacities of critical infrastructure systems. Drawing from the conceptual frameworks identified—such as system adaptiveness, cascading failures, and socio-technical interdependencies—T2.2 examines how digital disruptions challenge traditional resilience paradigms and necessitate new approaches to crisis anticipation and management. Special attention is given to emerging risks linked to algorithmic decision-making, cyber-physical coupling, and data-driven dependencies, as highlighted in the reviewed literature. This theoretical grounding provides the basis for the development of a structured analytical lens that will guide subsequent empirical work across case studies.

An in-depth literature review was conducted on the digital components of critical infrastructures, drawing on all available scientific formats (peer-reviewed articles, institutional reports, theses, conference proceedings, etc.). This allowed to identify numerous sources and better understand the technical and organisational challenges involved.

However, this field remains underexplored. Unlike critical communications widely studied due to their central role in crisis situations, digital continuity has not yet received the same systematic attention. This gap is largely due to the novelty of the issue: digital resilience has only recently emerged as a key concern, driven by the increasing digitalisation of essential services.

The focus group:

The initial methodology outlined for Task 2.2 included the organisation of an online focus group aimed at gathering diverse stakeholder perspectives in a collective setting. The intention was to facilitate interactive discussions among local actors involved in crisis management and infrastructure resilience, encouraging dialogue around shared challenges and cross-sectoral interdependencies. However, during the operational phase, it became apparent that coordinating a single session involving all relevant stakeholders posed significant logistical challenges. In response, the research team adapted the methodological approach by prioritizing individual semi-structured interviews. This shift allowed for greater flexibility in engaging participants and ensured a higher participation rate without compromising the depth or relevance of the insights collected. While the interactive dynamic of a focus group was not fully replicated, the one-on-one format offered the opportunity for more in-depth and candid discussions, tailored to each interviewee's expertise and institutional context. This adaptation preserved the original intent of capturing grounded, practice-based knowledge while aligning with the realities of field engagement.

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The stakeholders' interviews:

As part of Task 2.2 of the SPARROW project, a series of stakeholder interviews were carried out to collect in-depth qualitative data from professionals directly involved in the management, oversight, or coordination of critical infrastructures. The primary objective was to better understand how local actors perceive, prepare for, and respond to digital disruptions—particularly in contexts where such disruptions intersect with physical infrastructure vulnerabilities and crisis management processes.

The interviews employed a semi-structured format, allowing for consistency in key themes while providing flexibility to adapt to the specific experiences and institutional roles of each participant. Stakeholders were carefully selected to ensure a representative cross-section of critical infrastructure domains and governance levels. Participant selection was conducted collaboratively, with consortium partners recommending relevant stakeholders based on their expertise and relevance to the project. Participants included municipal authorities, crisis management, emergency service coordinators, and other relevant actors as showed in the Table 2.

The interviews were conducted online, for 1 hour each, following a consistent and pre-defined structure divided into six thematic sections, allowing for both comparability across participants and flexibility to explore individual experiences. The interviewer begins with an introduction, explaining the SPARROW project's objectives, ensuring confidentiality and consent, and clarifying the structure and purpose of the interview. The core of the interview consists of open-ended questions grouped into four key topics: (1) continuity of critical services during digital disruptions, (2) use of emerging technologies to enhance resilience, (3) cascading effects of infrastructure failures, and (4) lessons learned and preparedness. Each section encourages participants to reflect on real-world experiences, challenges, and best practices. The interview ends with a recap, a chance for final comments, and an explanation of follow-up steps, such as reviewing anonymised summaries. This approach supports the collection of qualitative data rich in contextual detail, ideal for identifying patterns and insights in infrastructure resilience strategies. Thus, covered topics included early warning and detection mechanisms, decision-making under uncertainty, inter-organisational coordination, continuity planning, and post-event learning. Special attention was paid to how digital dependencies influenced operational vulnerabilities and the capacity to adapt during crises.

Table 2 Summary of interviews conducted

City/Org	Date	Department	Main Topics Covered
Cannes (France)	8 July 2025	Crisis Management – Director of Major Risks	Crisis preparedness, power outage response, critical service continuity, emerging tech (Starlink, cloud), cascading effects, best practices
EENA (Brussels)	14 May 2025	European Emergency Number Association	European perspective, threats (natural/cyber), PSAP resilience,

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			emerging tech, cascading failures, interoperability
Leuven (Belgium)	27 June 2025	Crisis Manager	Crisis framework, BCP development, energy resilience, simulation tool needs, cascading risks
Pilsen (CZ) - Police	2 June 2025	Municipal Police Officer	Traffic control, power outage response, critical services (signals, surveillance), limited digital tools
Pilsen (CZ) - Traffic	2 June 2025	Traffic Management Lead	Traffic light systems, backup power, response plans, emerging tech (smart sensors), cybersecurity

This activity provided critical empirical grounding for the SPARROW project. The insights gathered not only deepened the project's understanding of critical infrastructure vulnerabilities and systemic interdependencies but also revealed practical constraints, innovations, and resilience strategies that often remain undocumented in academic or policy literature. Furthermore, these interviews helped identify gaps between formal preparedness frameworks and the realities encountered in field operations, informing future recommendations for adaptive governance and cross-sector resilience planning.

Building upon the foundational understanding of methodologies and analytical approaches detailed in the previous section, the subsequent chapter, "Emergency communication systems: Emerging technologies, gap analyses and best practices," will delve into the practical applications and findings. This next section will explore the latest advancements in emergency communication technologies, identify existing gaps, and highlight best practices derived from our comprehensive literature reviews, stakeholder insights, and pilot use case analyses.

2. Emergency communication systems: Emerging technologies, gap analyses and best practices

This chapter aims to identify the latest emergency communication systems, tools and channels as well as potential shortcomings and best practices by first, conducting a comprehensive literature review. Second, individual pilot use case analyses then reflect upon the principles outlined in the latter and showcase the potential enhancement of these use cases. Additionally, the survey conducted among SPARROW stakeholders and a wide international network of professionals' sheds light on the current status quo and the practical use of various technologies.

2.1. Emerging technologies review

The initial set of 53 reviewed documents consists of a diverse set of sources focused on emergency and crisis communication. It predominantly includes peer-reviewed scientific articles from prestigious journals, such as IEEE⁹ (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers) and MDPI¹⁰ (Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute), which focus on technologies such as unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), the Internet of Things (IoT), satellite and mobile networks, and algorithms for effective communication management in disasters. An example is the article by Deepak G.C. et al. "An Overview of Post-Disaster Emergency Communication Systems in the Future Networks"¹¹ (IEEE Wireless Communications, 2019) or the work of Carreras-Coch, A. et al. "Communication Technologies in Emergency Situations"¹² (Electronics, 2022). These are supplemented by chapters in specialist books that develop the strategic and communication aspects of crisis management, as well as technical standards (e.g., recommendations from the ITU-T (International Telecommunication Union Telecommunication Standardization Sector of ITU)¹³ and government or agency documents, in particular from FEMA (Federal Emergency Management Agency)¹⁴, CISA (Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency)¹⁵ as well as the projects funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020/Horizon Europe programmes, which set out frameworks and recommendations for practice. It also includes case studies of the use of modern technologies in specific events and several sources from private sector practice that reflect current trends, such as the role of social networks and artificial intelligence. Overall, this is a comprehensive overview of the literature

⁹<https://www.ieee.org/> IEEE. (n.d.). IEEE. <https://www.ieee.org/>.

¹⁰<https://www.mdpi.com/> MDPI. (n.d.). Publisher of Open Access Journals. <https://www.mdpi.com/>

¹¹D. G.C., A. Ladas, Y. A. Sambo, H. Pervaiz, C. Politis & M. A. Imran (2019). An Overview of Post-Disaster Emergency Communication Systems in the Future Networks. IEEE Wireless Communications, 26(6), 132–139. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MWC.2019.1800467>

¹²Carreras-Coch, A., Navarro, J., Sans, C., & Zaballos, A. (2022). Communication Technologies in Emergency Situations. Electronics, 11(7), 1155. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics11071155>

¹³<https://www.itu.int/en/Pages/default.aspx> International Telecommunication Union (ITU). (n.d.). ITU: Connecting the world and beyond. <https://www.itu.int/en/Pages/default.aspx>.

¹⁴<https://www.fema.gov/> Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA). (n.d.). Home. <https://www.fema.gov/>.

¹⁵<https://www.cisa.gov/> Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA). (n.d.). Home. <https://www.cisa.gov/>.

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combining theoretical, technical, and practical perspectives on the functioning of crisis communication.

Among the sources listed, several key articles can be identified that represent the basic literature in the field of crisis communication. An Overview of Post-Disaster Emergency Communication Systems in the Future Networks (IEEE Wireless Communications, 2019), which maps current and future technologies that can be used after disasters, in particular 5G networks and other platforms. A similarly systematic view is offered by Carreras-Coch, A. et al. in the article Communication Technologies in Emergency Situations (Electronics, 2022), where the authors compare the advantages and limitations of LTE, satellites, IoT, and UAVs. A comprehensive overview of wireless technologies is complemented by the study by Pervez, F. et al. Wireless Technologies for Emergency Response: A Comprehensive Review and Some Guidelines (IEEE Access, 2018)¹⁶, which also provides practical recommendations for their deployment. The specific role of unmanned vehicles is analysed by Hossein Motlagh, N. et al. in the article Low-Altitude UAV-Based Internet of Things Services (IEEE Internet of Things Journal, 2016)¹⁷, which discusses in detail the use of drones for emergency communications and Internet of Things services. An empirical perspective is provided by Yli-Kauhahuoma, S. et al. in Safe City (Multimodal Technologies and Interaction, 2023)¹⁸, which compares the effectiveness of various public warning channels in European cities. A broad overview of current trends is also provided by Wang, Q. et al. An Overview of Emergency Communication Networks (Remote Sensing, 2023)¹⁹, which summarizes the integration of satellites, UAVs, IoT, and 5G networks. Together, these publications show that the literature combines both technological innovations and empirical findings and overviews, providing a solid foundation for further exploration of emergency communication issues.

The second literature review works with a corpus (50 items) spanning peer-reviewed journals (e.g., Int. J. Disaster Risk Reduction²⁰, Frontiers in Public Health²¹, BMC Emergency Medicine²², Sustainability, Government Information Quarterly²³, Social Science Computer Review), flagship conference proceedings (IEEE, ACM, ASCE, EGU, SPE), scholarly books/chapters (Springer), or policy reports (World Bank; Mineta Transportation Institute). Technological themes include

¹⁶Pervez, F., Qadir, J., Khalil, M., Yaqoob, T., Ashraf, U., & Younis, S. (2018). Wireless Technologies for Emergency Response: A Comprehensive Review and Some Guidelines. *IEEE Access*, 6, 71814–71838.

<https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2878898>

¹⁷Motlagh, N. H., Taleb, T., & Arouk, O. (2016). Low-Altitude Unmanned Aerial Vehicles-Based Internet of Things Services: Comprehensive Survey and Future Perspectives. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 3(6), 899–922.

<https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2016.2612119>

¹⁸Yli-Kauhahuoma, S., Statheropoulos, M., Zygmanski, A., Anttalainen, O., Hakulinen, H., Kontogianni, M. T., Kuula, M., Perna, J., & Vanninen, P. (2023). Safe City: A Study of Channels for Public Warnings for Emergency Communication in Finland, Germany, and Greece. *Multimodal Technologies and Interaction*, 7(10), 94. <https://doi.org/10.3390/mti710094>

¹⁹Wang, Q., Li, W., Yu, Z., Abbasi, Q., Imran, M., Ansari, S., Sambo, Y., Wu, L., Li, Q., & Zhu, T. (2023). An Overview of Emergency Communication Networks. *Remote Sensing*, 15(6), 1595. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15061595>

²⁰Elsevier Ltd.. (n.d.). International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction. Retrieved September 4, 2025, from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/international-journal-of-disaster-risk-reduction>.

²¹Frontiers in Public Health. 2025, from <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/public-health>

²²BioMed Central Ltd.. (n.d.). BMC Emergency Medicine. Retrieved September 4, 2025, from <https://bmcmemergmed.biomedcentral.com/>

²³Elsevier Ltd.. (n.d.). Government Information Quarterly: Special Issues. Retrieved September 4, 2025, from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/government-information-quarterly/special-issues>

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chatbot-mediated communication (ERMES: Urbanelli et al., 2024)²⁴, human-AI/cloud decision support (Konakanchi, 2025)²⁵, IoT/LPWAN/SD-WAN and low-cost hybrids for off-grid crises (Cheimaras et al., 2023;²⁶ 2024²⁷), video livestreaming from callers to dispatch (Magnusson et al., 2024)²⁸, the alerts–social media “synergy” (Vafaeva et al., 2024)²⁹, and city-scale digital twins/ML (Mintoo et al., 2024)³⁰. Operational/governance strands cover volunteer dispatch and digital co-production (Pilemalm et al., 2025)³¹, common operational pictures with wearables and drones (FASTER toolkit: Konstantoudakis et al., 2022)³², EMD in LMICs (Friesen et al., 2024)³³, as well as inclusive risk communication and pandemic lessons (Hannes et al., 2024³⁴; Wang & Zhang, 2024³⁵;

²⁴Urbanelli, A., Frisiello, A., Bruno, L., & Rossi, C. (2024). The ERMES chatbot: A conversational communication tool for improved emergency management and disaster risk reduction. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 112, 104792. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2024.104792>

²⁵Konakanchi, S. (2025). Real-time human-AI collaboration through scalable cloud platforms for emergency response. *International Journal of Science and Research Archive*, 14(1), 282. GSC Online Press. <https://doi.org/10.30574/ijdra.2025.14.1.0064>

²⁶Cheimaras, V., Peladarinos, N., Monios, N., Daousis, S., Papagiakoumos, S., Papageorgas, P., & Piromalis, D. (2023). Emergency communication system based on wireless LPWAN and SD-WAN technologies: A hybrid approach. *Signals*, 4(2), 315–336. <https://doi.org/10.3390/signals4020017>

²⁷Cheimaras, V., Papagiakoumos, S., Peladarinos, N., Trigkas, A., Papageorgas, P., Piromalis, D. D., & Munteanu, R. A. (2024). Low-cost, open-source, experimental setup communication platform for emergencies, based on SD-WAN technology. *Telecom*, 5(2), 347–368. <https://doi.org/10.3390/telecom5020018>

²⁸Magnusson, C., Ollis, L., Munro, S., & Maben, J. (2024). Video livestreaming from medical emergency callers' smartphones to emergency medical dispatch centres: A scoping review of current uses, opportunities, and challenges. *BMC Emergency Medicine*, 24(1), 1015. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12873-024-01015-9>

²⁹Vafaeva, K. M., Singh, D., Banoth, R., & Arora, R. (2024). The synergy of emergency alerts and social media: An evaluation with the Emergency Alert and Social Media Engagement Test. *BIO Web of Conferences*, 86(3), 01074. <https://doi.org/10.1051/bioconf/20248601074>

³⁰Mintoo, A. A., Saimon, A. S. M., & Begum, A. (2024). Transforming global crisis communication through digital twins enhancing media response strategies with machine learning. *Innovatech Engineering Journal*, 1(1), 35–52. <https://doi.org/10.70937/jnes.v1i01.28>

³¹Pilemalm, S., Follin, A., & Prytz, E. (2025). Digitalized co-production of emergency response: ICT-enabled dispatch and coordination of volunteers at the emergency site. *Journal of Humanitarian Logistics and Supply Chain Management*, 15(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHLSCM-03-2024-0031>

³²Konstantoudakis, K., Christaki, K., Sainidis, D., Babic, I., Kogias, D. G., Inglese, G., Bruno, L., Giunta, G., Patrikakis, C. Z., Balet, O., Rossi, C., Dimou, A., & Daras, P. (2022). Common operational picture and interconnected tools for disaster response: The FASTER toolkit. In *Disaster management and information technology* (pp. 83–110). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-21488-2_5

³³Friesen, J., Kharel, R., & Delaney, P. G. (2024). Emergency medical dispatch technologies: Addressing communication challenges and coordinating emergency response in low and middle-income countries. *Surgery*, 175(5), 1042–1049. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surg.2024.02.031>

³⁴Hannes, K., Thyssen, P., Bengough, T., Dawson, S., Paque, K., Talboom, S., Tuand, K., Vandendriessche, T., van de Veerdonk, W., Wopereis, D., & Vandamme, A.-M. (2024). Inclusive crisis communication in a pandemic context: A rapid review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 21(9), 1216. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph21091216>

³⁵Wang, X., & Zhang, C. (2024). Constructing the digital ark: How China utilizes shared media to foster online information collaboration and crisis management in public emergency response. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 109, 104239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2024.104239>

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Edwards et al., 2022³⁶; Lum, 2024³⁷; You, 2023³⁸). inclusive risk communication and pandemic lessons (Hannes et al., 2024³⁹; Wang & Zhang, 2024⁴⁰; Several anchors stand out in this literature. On the tech side: ERMES demonstrates a validated, user-centred, bidirectional channel; FASTER integrates wearables/UAVs into a unified COP; Dalela et al. (2022)⁴¹ advance AI-enhanced multi-channel alerting; and LPWAN/SD-WAN prototypes (Cheimaras et al., 2023;⁴² 2024⁴³) show practical, low-cost resilience—complemented by a live-streaming dispatch patent (HigherGround, 2023)⁴⁴ In practice, Pilemalm et al.⁴⁵ formalise volunteer coordination; Singh & Singh (2021)⁴⁶ and Vafaeva et al. (2024) evidence social-media-enabled response; Chen et al. (2024)⁴⁷ map affordances/constraints in public messaging; and Magnusson et al. (2024) scope caller video for dispatch. On public health and equity, Hannes et al. (2024), Geurts et al. (2023)⁴⁸, Wieland et al.

³⁶Edwards, F., Liu, K., Hughes, A. L., & Gao, Z. (2022). Best practices in disaster public communications: State of the practice in communicating information, building trust and compelling action (Report No. 2254). Mineta Transportation Institute. <https://doi.org/10.31979/mti.2022.2254>

³⁷Lum, M. (2024). SS07-02 A global perspective: Digital insights into crisis communication during the COVID-19 pandemic—Lessons learned for workers, workplaces and our community of practice. *Occupational Medicine*, 74(Suppl_1), kqae023.0078. <https://doi.org/10.1093/occmmed/kqae023.0078>

³⁸You, M. (2023). Making government-led risk and crisis communication more effective: Lessons learned from six countries during the COVID-19 pandemic. Republic of Korea – World Bank Group Partnership on COVID-19 Preparedness and Response. World Bank. <http://hdl.handle.net/10986/40705>

³⁹Hannes, K., Thyssen, P., Bengough, T., Dawson, S., Paque, K., Talboom, S., Tuand, K., Vandendriessche, T., van de Veerdonk, W., Wopereis, D., & Vandamme, A.-M. (2024). Inclusive crisis communication in a pandemic context: A rapid review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 21(9), 1216. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph21091216>

⁴⁰Wang, X., & Zhang, C. (2024). Constructing the digital ark: How China utilizes shared media to foster online information collaboration and crisis management in public emergency response. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 109, 104239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2024.104239>

⁴¹Dalela, P. K., Basu, S., Sharma, S., Kumar, A. N., Behera, S. S., & Upadhyay, R. (2022, May 23–27). AI-enhanced integrated alert system for effective disaster management. EGU General Assembly 2022, Vienna, Austria (EGU22-6758). Copernicus Meetings. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu22-6758>

⁴²Cheimaras, V., Peladarinos, N., Monios, N., Daousis, S., Papagiakoumos, S., Papageorgas, P., & Piromalis, D. (2023). Emergency communication system based on wireless LPWAN and SD-WAN technologies: A hybrid approach. *Signals*, 4(2), 315–336. <https://doi.org/10.3390/signals4020017>

⁴³Cheimaras, V., Papagiakoumos, S., Peladarinos, N., Trigkas, A., Papageorgas, P., Piromalis, D. D., & Munteanu, R. A. (2024). Low-cost, open-source, experimental setup communication platform for emergencies, based on SD-WAN technology. *Telecom*, 5(2), 347–368. <https://doi.org/10.3390/telecom5020018>

⁴⁴HigherGround, Inc. (2023). Systems and methods of live streaming emergency dispatch data to first responders (Patent No. MX 2022004987 A). Mexican Institute of Industrial Property (IMPI). <https://patentscope.wipo.int>

⁴⁵Pilemalm, S., Follin, A., & Prytz, E. (2025). Digitalized co-production of emergency response: ICT-enabled dispatch and coordination of volunteers at the emergency site. *Journal of Humanitarian Logistics and Supply Chain Management*, 15(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHLSCM-03-2024-0031>

⁴⁶Singh, A., & Singh, J. (2021). Twitter emergency response system during flood-related disaster. *International Journal of Emergency Management*, 1(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJEM.2021.10045788>

⁴⁷Chen, T., Gil-Garcia, J. R., Burke, G. B., Dey, A., & Werthmuller, D. (2024). Characterizing technology affordances, constraints, and coping strategies for information dissemination to the public: Insights from emergency messaging in US local governments. *Government Information Quarterly*, 41(4), 101910. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2024.101910>

⁴⁸Geurts, B., Weishaar, H., Saez, A. M., Cristea, F., Rocha, C., Aminu, K., Tan, M. M. J., Camara, B. S., Barry, L., Thea, P., Boucsein, J., Bahr, T., Al-Awlaqi, S., Pozo-Martin, F., Boklage, E., Delamou, A., Jegede, A. S., Legido-Quigley, H., & El Bcheraoui, C. (2023). Communicating risk during early phases of COVID-19: Comparing governing structures for emergency risk communication across four contexts. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 11, 1038989. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1038989>

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(2021)⁴⁹ and Brewer et al. (2020)⁵⁰ foreground inclusive RCCE. Collectively, these works knit infrastructure, analytics and human factors into an evidence-based playbook for crisis communication and emergency response. A comprehensive compilation of articles that underwent literature review is presented in Appendices 7.1, meticulously categorized based on their thematic themes.

2.1.1. Analysis based on literature review

For an initial insight into the findings based on literature review, Figure 4 can be used to quantify and summarize the results of the thematic analysis. It captures the most frequent occurrences of EMC Tools, systems and channels in the content sections of the literature reviewed. The preview of the preliminary findings can be further elaborated. Instead of focusing on the content dimension of the analysed articles, it is possible to focus on the visualization of the most frequent keywords in the studied literature. This is captured in Figure 5.

Figure 4 Frequency of Communication and Technology Tools

⁴⁹Wieland, M. L., Asiedu, G. B., Lantz, K., et al. (2021). Leveraging community engaged research partnerships for crisis and emergency risk communication to vulnerable populations in the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Clinical and Translational Science*, 5(1), e6. <https://doi.org/10.1017/cts.2020.47>

⁵⁰Brewer, L. C., Asiedu, G. B., Jones, C., Richard, M., Erickson, J., Weis, J., Abbenyi, A., Brockman, T. A., Sia, I. G., Wieland, M. L., White, R. O., & Doubeni, C. A. (2020). Emergency preparedness and risk communication among African American churches: Leveraging a community-based participatory research partnership COVID-19 initiative. *Preventing Chronic Disease*, 17, E158. <https://doi.org/10.5888/pcd17.200408>

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Figure 5 Top 20 Most Frequent Keywords

Overall, preliminary findings based on the overlap between thematic analysis and quantitative overview of keywords can be interpreted as follows. Regarding thematic connections in the analysed data, the categories of emergency communication, emergency response, and disaster preparedness dominate. This is reinforced by the emphasis on technologies that support these areas, such as UAVs, IoT, and communication platforms, with an emphasis on social media. A series of technical and conceptual connections can be identified in the content, with the most significant emphasis evident in the quantitative emphasis on UAVs. In terms of communication, there is a clear emphasis on D2D communication and the use of social media. We can highlight the following key points if we summarize the preliminary findings based on the juxtaposition of thematic analysis and a quantitative overview of keywords in the analysed corpus. The first is the dominant role of drones. This is the most frequently mentioned tool. From the perspective of crisis management and communication, UAV technology is therefore assigned a key role in monitoring and data collection, delivery, etc. Furthermore, emphasis is placed on the importance of interoperability and situational awareness. Thematic analysis of the data corpus points to the importance of different systems and components within the EMC, demonstrating their ability to cooperate and orient themselves in critical situations. The communication issue is linked to an emphasis on technologies such as MANET, IoT, and D2D, which lead to dynamic, distributed, and adaptive network infrastructure.

From a quantitative point of view, on the other hand, there is a noticeable lack of emphasis on technologies such as 5G or LTE. This can be interpreted in terms of a low level of implementation in actual applications or simply a low occurrence in the analysed discourse (in this case, the result may be biased in the sense that other technologies are significantly overvalued in the analysed corpus from a quantitative point of view, e.g., due to their repetitiveness or interconnection). The emphasis on the position of UAVs and their usability within the analysed topic can be illustrated in Figure 6 by

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pointing out the connection between the concepts associated with them and other key themes falling within the field of emergency communication.

This initial insight into the analysed data can be concluded by generalising the thematic analysis results.

- *Crisis communication and management*: A topic devoted to emergency management, communication, and preparedness. Topics related to emergency communication, emergency response, disaster response, crisis communication, preparedness, and emergency management dominated here.
- *Interoperability and cooperation network*: This topic reflects the importance of coordination, information sharing, and the ability of subsystems and components to cooperate. Topics related to interoperability, situational awareness, inclusive communication, real-time updates, and resource allocation are dominant here.
- *The role of social networks in communication*: This section covers topics related to information reach and various communication platforms, emphasizing the role of social media.
- *Autonomous technology*: This section is dominated by technologies such as UAVs and direct machine communication, which are important in crisis and field conditions. The most frequent topics, therefore, relate to drones, UAVs, and related communication tools.

Figure 6 Position of UAVs within Cluster Interconnections

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The thematic classification thus shows that the analysed literature emphasizes crisis scenarios, technological support for information sharing, and the use of autonomous means. Crisis communication is based on four interconnected pillars. This structure shows that crisis preparedness requires technological infrastructure. The capability of quick response and information sharing between the key pillars is also critical. It is also possible to provide an exhaustive list of technologies mentioned in the analysed corpus in relevant proportions to ensure transparency. The central node is Emergency Communication, which branches into three clusters: Communication Tools, Communication Systems, and Communication Channels. Each cluster further contains its specific technologies and functions. Thus, the emergency communication systems encompass the technical backbone, including network infrastructures, UAVs, IoT devices, and increasingly, AI-driven analytics for real-time data processing and threat detection. Communication Channels represent the transmission pathways, ranging from terrestrial and satellite technologies to public safety networks, ad hoc architectures, and emerging device-to-device solutions. Finally, Communication Tools reflect the operational interface—covering real-time dissemination platforms, decision support systems, and notably, public engagement mechanisms such as mobile apps, social media, and crowdsourcing tools. These tools are crucial in involving the public in the emergency communication process. Together, these clusters illustrate how emergency communication operates through a synergy of physical infrastructure, digital technologies, and participatory mechanisms, each playing a distinct role in enabling coordinated, timely, and resilient crisis response.

Emergency communication systems

Emergency communication systems category consists of four thematic areas: Network Technologies, Devices and Infrastructure, Artificial Intelligence and Data Analytics, Software and Platforms. The Figure 7 summarises the components of the Network Technologies thematic area. MANETs, DTNs, and WSNs dominate. The quantitative representation of other topics can then be interpreted in the overall context as a broad diversification of network technologies in the analysed literature. Devices and infrastructure are the second thematic area falling under Emergency Communication Systems. The quantitative emphasis on drones (and unmanned vehicles in general) is therefore also evident in Figure 8. Artificial Intelligence and data analytics are the fourth component of the central cluster Emergency Communication Systems and are visualized in Figure 9 in the following way. There is a clear emphasis on the use of AI systems and technologies for real-time data analysis, threat identification, and predictive analysis. The last category in the first thematic cluster is Software and Platforms quantified in Figure 10. According to the analysed literature, the dominant technological core of EMC systems are UAVs and Mobile Ad Hoc Networks. This shows that literature related to EMC emphasizes decentralized networks in crisis scenarios, and drones are understood (not exclusively, but predominantly) as data collection tools, mobile sensors, and mobile communication nodes (especially in the context of Small Cell Drones and Flying Base Stations). The trend in data evaluation is the expansion of the use of AI tools, mainly due to their ability to evaluate robust data sets in real time. The broad thematic spread also indicates that the EMC ecosystem is highly diversified, indicating a high degree of innovative and experimental potential.

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Figure 7 Overview of Network Technologies

Figure 8 Overview of Devices and Infrastructure

Figure 9 Overview of Artificial Intelligence and Data Analytics

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Figure 10 Overview of Software and Platforms

Emergency communication channels

This section consists of six thematic areas, with the most developed and ramified area being the Terrestrial Wireless Technologies category, which is divided into six subcategories.

Communication technologies are the overarching domain encompassing five functional clusters: Terrestrial Wireless Technologies, Satellite Communication Technologies, Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN) Technologies, Low Power Wide Area Networks (LPWAN), and Device-to-Device Communication Technologies. Each of these clusters' further branches into specific technology categories. Terrestrial Wireless Technologies exhibit the most significant internal complexity, incorporating Cellular, Ad Hoc, Specialized, and Public Safety Networks and supporting elements like Network Architectures and Protocols. This layered configuration illustrates how Communication Technologies in emergency contexts span from core transmission frameworks to highly specialized and adaptive tools, enabling flexible responses tailored to diverse infrastructural and situational demands.

We can arrive at the following findings if we focus our analysis on lower units and more specific communication technologies. From the perspective of the analysed literature, emphasis is placed on satellite communication technologies. This is mainly because they provide reliable coverage even in remote areas and situations where terrestrial systems fail, representing an important part of global communication networks. Using satellite phones in combination with ad hoc networks enables communication even in places with destroyed infrastructure. This approach is critical in disasters or crises when it is necessary to restore connections quickly. A limited number of satellite devices supplemented by a flexible network structure offers a practical and fast solution in demanding conditions. The quantification of individual technologies falling within this area is captured in the Figure 11.

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Figure 11 Overview of Satellite Communication Technologies

However, as mentioned above, the most diverse category was communication technologies, which can be classified under Terrestrial Wireless Technologies. Figure 12 illustrates their structure and quantification. Subsequently, individual technologies are briefly characterized in terms of their general characteristics in the analysed data corpus.

Figure 12 Overview of Terrestrial Wireless Technologies

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Cellular technologies are characterized in the analysed corpus as communication tools with low latency and high energy efficiency, offering broadband access to services such as voice, text, video, and other multimedia. Another key advantage is priority access to emergency services, which ensures reliable communication even in crises when every second counts. The literature analysed indicates that WLAN technologies are suitable for creating local wireless networks, enabling the rapid deployment of temporary access points and networks that can be used to share information during a disaster. Broadband technology can provide extended coverage and efficient voice and video transmission, key to coordinating rescue operations and providing up-to-date information to affected areas. Another thematic cluster related to Emergency Communication Channels in the analysed data are Ad-Hoc Networks, which represent a solution for communication without the need for traditional infrastructure. These networks can be created without fixed infrastructure, use decentralized architecture, and offer high resistance to multiple signal propagation, diffraction capability, and support for high-speed movement. Thanks to these features, they are ideal for deployment in dynamic environments where reliable connections need to be established quickly. LPWAN is viewed positively due to its long range and low energy consumption. This makes it ideal for wireless data transmission over long distances. It enables effective communication even where traditional infrastructure is unavailable and is suitable for applications requiring a permanent connection with minimal energy consumption.

Specialized Communication Technologies cluster shares the characteristics of being platforms designed for mobile telephony that use mesh networks and Wi-Fi tethering-based architecture to collect data from smartphone sensors. Although based on a traditional system, it provides only limited data services. It is designed for specific use cases where simplicity, low power consumption, and the ability to operate in conditions with limited connectivity are priorities. Following the thematic cluster Terrestrial Wireless Technologies, the next cluster in Emergency Communication Channels is Public Safety and Emergency Response Technologies, whose visualization, quantification is shown in Figure 13.

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Figure 13 Overview of Public Safety and Emergency Response Technologies

The Public Safety and Emergency Response Technologies category is relatively fragmented in terms of content in the analysed literature. It can therefore only be summarized in a superficial and general way. Overall, it represents a tool for critically essential applications in protection and rescue operations. It enables reliable voice communication between rescue services, direct connection between users nearby, and group communication. It is used for location sharing, warning residents, and sending short emergency messages. This strengthens the resilience of public safety networks and ensures an effective response in disaster-stricken areas.

The most important and most developed area in the data corpus is terrestrial wireless technologies, thanks to their diversity and wide use in emergency communications. When there is no working infrastructure, satellite technologies are essential. Flexible and decentralized methods like LPWAN and ad-hoc networks are recommended for quick deployment and low cost. Although they are not as well covered, topics like protocols and device-to-device communication have room to grow. Public safety technologies support robust crisis infrastructure, although they are generally described in the literature. The last two categories from the Emergency Communication Channels cluster are represented sporadically in the analysed data. The Device-to-Device Communication Technologies category focuses on direct communication between devices without needing a base station. Network Architecture and Protocols then highlight the differences and possibilities for using centralized and distributed routing algorithms.

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Emergency communication tools

The last thematic cluster is the Emergency Communication Tools category. Its structure is shown in the Figure 14. As with the previous categories, it is followed by a brief interpretation of how the content of this category is constructed in the analysed literature.

Figure 14 Overview of Latest Emergency Communication Tools

Digital platforms and technological innovations are fundamentally transforming the operational dynamics of crisis communication. They facilitate the efficient dissemination of information, foster public engagement, and enable real-time coordination of emergency services. Social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter (X), YouTube, and Instagram are pivotal in promptly disseminating news, alerts, and directives to the populace. Owing to the capability for direct interaction with citizens, they also assist in garnering invaluable feedback and thus represent some of the most expedient communication channels during crises.

Mobile applications deliver tailored information and alerts directly to mobile devices. These technological instruments furnish information and facilitate incident reporting and communication with emergency responders, thereby augmenting the overall efficacy of the emergency response framework. In addition to applications, websites and web-based applications are integral to the crisis communication landscape. Official institutional websites offer comprehensive information regarding current events, recommendations, and measures. Web applications, such as crisis maps, provide real-time data concerning infrastructure status, availability of assistance, or needs in specific geographic locales. Visualizing this data enhances the coordination of interventions and informs decision-making by the pertinent authorities. Chatbots represent another critical component of contemporary

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crisis communication, delivering automated responses to frequently posed inquiries and supporting the round-the-clock availability of information. Consequently, they alleviate the burden on call centre personnel and expedite public access to essential information. These systems facilitate content scheduling, response monitoring, and effective team collaboration management across various channels. In summary, these digital instruments bolster the resilience of public infrastructure, enhance the availability of information, and enable a swift, coordinated response in emergencies. It is imperative to incorporate them into crisis planning systematically and routinely assess their functionality and level of public engagement.

Similarly, the second thematic domain Data Analysis and Decision Support warrants summarization. Advanced digital instruments and analytical frameworks are utilized to orchestrate crisis management efficiently. While artificial intelligence-enhanced predictive analytics support anticipatory planning and risk mitigation, sentiment analysis contributes to comprehending public reactions and contemporary demands. The Crisis Track system enables expedited damage evaluation, eICS provides comprehensive crisis management solutions, and the WebEOC platform is a collaborative space for inter-agency interaction and information dissemination. Collectively, these technological advancements significantly enhance emergency response and management capabilities. Public Engagement and Crowdsourcing represent the final domains within this thematic cluster. The examined discourse elucidates the significant function of digital media in disseminating information and monitoring public sentiment amid crises. The secondary instrument—crowdsourcing platforms—elicits feedback and recommendations directly from impacted groups. From the micro-level, which is concerned with specific technologies, strategies, and their interconnections, the scope of analysis can be shifted to a macro level. The above interpretation of the three main thematic areas will be expanded upon by illustrating the extended number of clusters, as highlighted in the Figure 15. It confirms the thematic breadth by showing that the micro clusters are thematically compatible with the thematic areas analysed above. At the same time, it reveals and visualizes the interconnectedness of specific themes. The literature review devoted to emergency communication can be concluded with a final summary visualization. This is based on a combination of data corpus and the aggregation of the ten most frequent thematic areas in the keywords listed in the analysed texts to capture their interconnections, as explained in the Figure 16.

The Emergency Communication Systems cluster can be related to thematic areas such as ‘communication’, ‘coordination’, and ‘data’, and at the level of specific systems, for example, networks such as MANETs, DTNs or UAVs as potential mobile nodes. Furthermore, the thematically related area of ‘resilience’ can be appropriately assigned to this cluster. At the level of specific systems, the analysed literature shows a clear link between drones and the use of AI as systems contributing to resilience and adaptability. From the perspective of communication systems, there is also a clear link to the thematic areas of ‘trust’ and ‘information’. Platforms such as WebEOC and transparent information distribution positively impact strengthening social capital and trust in emergency communication for citizens.

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Figure 15 Dominant Terms in Thematic Clusters

Figure 16 Simplified Thematic Keyword Network (Top 10 Terms)

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The Emergency Communication Channels thematic cluster can be thematically and contextually linked to areas such as ‘communication’, “data”, and ‘coordination’, particularly thanks to its emphasis on Terrestrial Wireless Technologies, LTE, Wi-Fi and ad-hoc networks. In the overall analysed discourse, there is a clear link between the topics of ‘emergency’ and ‘crisis’ and channels for communication coverage in isolated areas, specifically with an emphasis on satellite communication. Overall, the Emergency Communication Channels thematic cluster in the analysed corpus is consistently linked to categories such as ‘emergency’, “coordination”, and ‘data’, corresponding to the key role of communication channels in crises.

The last thematic cluster – Emergency Communication Tools – emphasizes, among other things, tools such as social media, which act as links between emergency communication and public engagement. Categories such as ‘trust’ or ‘resilience’ are linked in the analysed corpus to tools such as sentiment analysis, Crisis Track, etc. The interpretation of keywords and their interconnectivity and subsequent interrelation with the main thematic clusters can be concluded by pointing out that one of the primary central thematic nodes is ‘resilience’, which runs through all the main thematic clusters. A similar role is played by ‘communication’, where all parts of emergency communication de facto form components aimed at effective communication. Social capital and trust are crucial for a resilient society and effective emergency communication. The interconnection with social media and the emphasis on practical and rapid evaluation of information reflect the focus on transparency and civic participation.

2.1.2. Survey findings on emergency communication systems

The survey revealed a wide range of incidents where emergency communication systems were deployed, with floods and pandemics being the most frequently cited. Nearly half of the institutions responded locally, while a significant share operated at regional, national, or international levels, reflecting the varying scales of emergency response. Across all incidents, traditional systems—such as analog/digital radio and mobile phones—were used most frequently and rated highest in usability and relevance. Drones emerged as the most common advanced system, followed by mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs) and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies, indicating a growing interest in sensor-driven and decentralized communication. However, newer systems like delay-tolerant networks (DTNs), wireless sensor networks (WSNs), and next-generation networks showed limited usage and lower usability, suggesting operational or integration barriers.

In terms of frequency, daily use was highest for traditional systems and mobile-based solutions, while emerging technologies were often used in more specialized or backup roles. Participants emphasized that ease of use, system reliability, and independence from digital infrastructure were key drivers of adoption. Systems with high usability, such as mobile phones and Motorola platforms, consistently outperformed more complex or emerging ones. Regarding communication channels, cellular technologies such as LTE and TETRA were overwhelmingly the most used and considered most relevant. WLAN, satellite communication, and device-to-device (D2D) links also played important roles. WLAN and cellular networks were used most consistently, while satellite and ad hoc channels were perceived as more situational. Usability ratings followed a similar pattern, with terrestrial

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wireless and D2D channels scoring highest, underscoring their reliability and accessibility during emergencies. Emergency communication tools followed a similar trend: mobile apps, SMS/text messaging, and social media were the most widely adopted and frequently used. Apps and SMS stood out for their daily use and high usability, while social media was valued for public outreach despite being more variable in performance. Less common tools—like chatbots, crowdsourcing platforms, and town hall meetings—were used in niche contexts and had limited perceived impact.

When asked about communication during digital breakdowns, respondents emphasized the importance of resilient, low-tech, and decentralized systems. Analog radio networks, SMS, sirens, and predefined routines were viewed as essential fallbacks. Tools such as drones, MANETs, and community-based networks were also valued for their flexibility and independence from centralized infrastructure. Respondents highlighted the importance of human-centred solutions—simple, accessible, and redundant—over complex, digital-first systems. Overall, the findings confirm that while digital innovation is increasingly integrated into emergency response, reliability, usability, and redundancy remain paramount. The most effective communication approaches blend trusted analog systems with emerging technologies in a layered, hybrid model that can adapt to both normal operations and infrastructure-compromised environments. Detailed quantitative and qualitative results supporting these conclusions are provided in Appendix 7.2.1.

2.1.3. Emerging approaches identified within individual pilot use cases

The literature review and thematic operational survey helped to identify key emerging trends in crisis communication. These approaches were then subsequently analysed in the individual pilot use cases presented from 3 pilot cities, Nicosia (Cyprus), Pilsen (Czech Republic), and Trikala (Greece).

Nicosia:

The PUC (pilot use case) in the SPARROW project, aimed at preparing for the risks leading to digital collapse, coincides in several respects with the latest trends in emergency communication (EMC) systems.

Within the literature review, latest systems, tools and channels for emergency communications were identified. They focus on various technologies that enable effective and reliable communication during disasters and emergencies. These technologies include wireless networks, satellites, drones, mobile applications, and social media. Resources focus on various aspects of emergency communications, including IoT network integration, optimizing drone deployment, developing robust, fault-tolerant systems, and using AI to collect and analyse real-time data.

As most frequently occurred in the searched texts, the drones were identified as the most frequent emerging tools for emergency communication.

The pilot use case in Nicosia scenario has been searched to reflect the latest EMC trends as follows:

- Alternative Means of Communication
- Drone-Assisted and IoT-based Communication
- Public Awareness and Citizen Engagement

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- Testing and improvement
- Focus on digital collapse

The Nicosia Use Case (PUC1) aligns closely with emerging EMC trends by adopting 5G, D2D, IoT, drones, satellite, and AI-driven decision-making for resilience against digital breakdowns. This synergy ensures better emergency preparedness, response, and coordination in flash flood scenarios.

Alternative Means of Communication

The objectives of the pilot are to augment the existing preparedness and response mechanisms during digital breakdown, focusing on alternative communications amongst teams of FRs and amongst citizens and crisis managers, and dynamic management of assets and responding teams as the situation unfolds.

The pilot use case in Nicosia places emphasis on alternative communication systems for the purposes of facilitating communication between first responders (FRs) and between citizens and emergency managers. This coincides with trends in EMC that emphasize the importance of ad hoc networks (MANETs, WMNs) and device-to-device (D2D) communications, which enable communication even in circumstances where conventional infrastructure has failed. Furthermore, technologies such as Self-powered Ruggedized Mobile 5G Network EMER5G, Signal-area Expansion Drones SEDs and EMPEER (Emergency peer-to-peer communication network), which serve as alternative communication tools, are utilized in the pilot use case in Nicosia.

Drone-Assisted Communication

The implementation of the pilot use case in Nicosia in Cyprus involves the use of several SPARROW technologies, including Signal-area Expansion Drones (SEDs), which facilitate the rapid deployment of communication infrastructure.

The EMC trends emphasize the use of drone-assisted communication and IoT-based emergency systems for real-time situation assessment, with drones (UAVs) frequently cited as mobile base stations to restore communication in affected areas. Additionally, drones can collect data and monitor the situation.

Public Awareness and Citizen Engagement

EMC places significant emphasis on the engagement of citizens in communication processes. This is facilitated by means of a variety of digital applications, including social media, web applications and mobile applications. The deployment of these applications is increasing in terms of their utilization for the purpose of crisis communication, given that they enable real-time feedback and suggestions from affected populations. The use of ECOMAPP (mobile application that will be developed within SPARROW and will be given to the citizens in order for them to self-report their current status) facilitates communication between citizens and FRs and considers feedback from citizens. This process can result in an alteration of the priorities of the intervening teams.

The pilot use case in Nicosia also uses SSH questionnaires to gather information from citizens that influences intervention priorities.

Testing and Improvement

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As the pilot use case in Nicosia's primary objective is to undertake systematic testing of diverse scenarios, with the aim of enhancing the response team's preparedness and decision-making skills, this approach is aligned with the overarching EMC objective of enhancing emergency preparedness.

Focus on digital collapse

The pilot use case in Nicosia has been developed for deployment in situations where digital systems fail due to flooding. Furthermore, the need to ensure communication in the event of failure or damage to traditional infrastructure is addressed by modern EMC standards.

Real-time data and AI-driven decision support

In the pilot use case in Nicosia, emphasis is placed on dynamic management of resources and response teams with respect to the evolving situation, with the use of ECOMAPP enabling communication between citizens and FRs and considering feedback from citizens, which in turn changes the priorities of the intervening teams. In addition, the implementation of CITWIN (City Digital Twin) for dynamic vulnerability assessment of critical infrastructure allows for the visualization of the affected area.

The pilot use case in Nicosia also leverages CESER (Cascading Effects Scenario Builder), a tool that enables the creation and assessment of operational preparedness training scenarios during digital breakdowns to capture threats, timing of critical events, and cascade effects on infrastructure. This is in line with EMC trends that emphasize AI-driven predictive analytics and IoT sensor networks for situational awareness in which AI algorithms can analyse data from IoT devices and other sources (e.g., social media) to identify patterns that could indicate an impending disaster. This predictive analysis can improve early warning systems and enable early warning of the population.

Pilsen

The literature review and the use case analysis revealed a consistency in following key areas, confirming that the city already possesses a significant infrastructure in these domains, that could be further build upon: Drones, IoT, 5G mobile network, Warning information system, Mobile application, and Real-Time Data Visualisation.

Drones

Based on the literature review, drones, have been identified as one of the most prevalent emerging technologies among emergency communication tools, systems, and channels.

SPARROW suggests use of drones to transmit live imagery from the scene of an incident, enabling comprehensive monitoring and assessment. The SPARROW use case integrates drones to monitor and relay real-time traffic information. This aligns with EMC's adoption of drone-assisted communication, where drones function as mobile base stations or data collection devices to maintain communication in areas with compromised infrastructure.

Drones SIT: This approach builds on more than a decade of work by the Drones SIT department, which has been developing UAV technology in the city of Pilsen for more than 10 years. In Pilsen, Drones SIT, a department of SITMP, builds on a long history of successful cooperation with firefighters and police officers. It became the first official part of the Integrated Rescue System (IRS) in the Czech Republic in 2019. For instance, it aids at major fires, mass casualty incidents, searches

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for missing persons, building collapses, or events that pose a security risk. Drones routinely transmit video from drones, ground cameras to wherever it is needed in real time. They provide IRS Stream – a comprehensive solution for streaming data from the scene of a crisis event.

Figure 17 Drones SIT's DJI Matrice 300 RTK with GL60 LED spotlight and DJI H20T hybrid camera payload

IRS stream: The IRS Stream project by Drones SIT provides advanced tools for integrated rescue systems (IRS), enabling low-latency video streaming and data sharing from crisis scenes. It employs Teradek technology to stream encrypted data via multiple LTE modems, ensuring reliable performance even in areas with poor connectivity. The system facilitates real-time positioning and object marking using drones, aiding in search-and-rescue and firefighting operations. It integrates with maps for efficient resource coordination and supports secure, multi-user access during simultaneous incidents. The technology is widely utilized by Czech police and fire services.

Figure 18 IRS stream 's map Dashboard in Pilsen

LoRa network, IoT integration

The results of the literature review identified the integration of IoT/LoRa as among the more prevalent emerging technologies for emergency communication.

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SPARROW use case describes the LoRa data network for efficient data transmission and communication. LoRa technology enables long-distance wireless data transmission with low power consumption and is suitable for IoT networks deployed in emergency situations. Therefore, SPARROW's use of LoRa networks for consistent data flow in low-power situations matches EMC's trend of leveraging IoT and low-power networks for reliable data transmission in emergency situations. LoRa's efficiency in remote data exchange without high energy demands is ideal for scenarios where traditional communication is limited.

LoRa IoT Network in Pilsen: In January 2017, SITMP and its partners initiated the establishment of an Internet of Things (IoT) communication network on the open LoRaWAN platform within the unlicensed 868 MHz frequency band. This is a wireless network based on LPWAN (Low Power Wide Area Network) technology, which enables simple and energy-efficient long-range communication. The network is utilised to establish communication between sensor units in locations where alternative access technologies or power sources are unavailable, thereby facilitating the processing of data transmitted by the sensors.

Figure 19 LoRa coverage in Pilsen

5G mobile network

Despite the lower occurrence of mentions on 5G mobile networks in the reviewed documents, some sources identified the advantages of integration of 5G mobile networks into emergency communication tools, systems and channels. SPARROW uses its own robust 5G mobile network to prioritize and streamline communications for emergency responders. Sources emphasize the potential of 5G networks to handle post-disaster communications with ultra-low latency, network densification, and increased efficiency.

SPARROW's implementation of a ruggedized, self-powered mobile 5G network to support real-time data transmission during a traffic control failure mirrors the current EMC trend of using 5G for its low latency and high network efficiency.

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5G for 5 cities: implementation of 5G network in Pilsen: Pilsen was one of the first cities in the Czech Republic to implement 5G network. The 5G network implementation in Pilsen enhanced its capabilities as a smart city, focusing on real-time data monitoring and secure communication systems. The project utilized advanced 5G infrastructure for optimizing urban mobility, including smart transportation zones. It facilitated near-instantaneous robotic responses and remote interactions with hospitals, improving healthcare efficiency. This initiative involved collaboration among government bodies, businesses, and residents, demonstrating a successful model for advancing urban digitalization and connectivity.

Figure 20 Test Polygon for Autonomous Vehicles

Warning Information System (WIS)

Dissemination of information towards public was also identified amongst latest emergency communication tools, systems and channels. SPARROW integrates WIS for issuing warnings and disseminating information to the public in real time. Sources cite early warning systems as essential for the rapid and efficient delivery of emergency notifications to the public. The Warning Information System (WIS), together with GIS data, will play a crucial role in disseminating real-time alerts and mapping, thus allowing efficient localisation of warnings.

WIS in Pilsen: In 2018, the city of Pilsen implemented a modern digital warning and information system (WIS) to enhance public safety during emergencies. The system covers specific city districts with 218 acoustic devices capable of broadcasting alerts and verbal instructions. It integrates with flood management plans and leverages the city's LoRa network for data collection, such as environmental and noise monitoring. Its implementation significantly improved crisis response and urban safety.

Mobile applications

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Mobile applications deliver tailored information and alerts directly to mobile devices. Examples include 112 Suomi in Finland, the Warn App NINA in Germany, and the forest fire warning application in Greece. These technological instruments furnish information and facilitate incident reporting and communication with emergency responders, thereby augmenting the overall efficacy of the emergency response framework.

Figure 21 Warning Information System location in Pilsen

Záchranka app: Záchranka is the mobile app aimed to enhance public safety and preparedness in crisis situations, and the city of Pilsen has enhanced steadily its crisis communication system by integrating it into the Záchranka mobile app. This enhancement allows citizens to receive real-time notifications about public health emergencies and critical updates, such as water supply contamination, large-scale fires, chemical leaks, unexploded ordnance and other dangerous situations. The system ensures rapid dissemination of information regarding hazards such as fires, floods, and industrial accidents. It also includes features like emergency contact accessibility and location sharing to aid rescue services.

Bezpečná Plzeň app + webpages: Bezpečná Plzeň is a mobile app launched by the city of Pilsen to enhance public safety and communication. The app provides real-time alerts about emergencies, such as floods or hazardous material leaks, along with instructions on how to respond. Developed by students supported by the city's IT department, the app also includes preventive advice and updates

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on local safety-related news. It is free to download for Android and iOS users. This initiative showcases Pilsen's commitment to leveraging technology for community well-being and fostering young talent.

Figure 22 Emergency alerts in Záchranka app

Figure 23 Public emergency warnings in Bezpečná Pilsen app

Real-Time Data Visualization

While the sources used for the literature review do not directly mention the digital twin platform, advanced data visualisation and situational visualisation is one of the contemporary trends. SPARROW's Digital Twin platform, which models the city's infrastructure in real time, is in line with the EMC trend of utilizing IoT and advanced data visualization tools. This allows emergency teams to maintain situational awareness and coordinate responses more effectively during digital outages.

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SPARROW's CITwin platform, which models the city's infrastructure in real time, is in line with the EMC trend of utilizing IoT and advanced data visualization tools. This allows emergency teams to maintain situational awareness and coordinate responses more effectively during digital outages.

Polivisu, Duet and EDIC: Pilsen has long been very active in the field of digital twins. It is one of the pioneering cities dedicated to the practical development and deployment of digital twin technologies in urban environments. The city is behind the development and growth of the POLIVISU platform, which was created as part of the European Horizon 2020 project and enables data-driven decision-making in urban planning and mobility. It built on this experience by participating in the *DUET project*, where Pilsen was one of three pilot cities testing the use of digital twins for modelling traffic scenarios and planning land use changes. Pilsen is also an active member of the LDT EDIC CitiVerse and participates in sharing best practices and shaping European strategies in the use of digital technologies for city management.

Trikala

The use case analysis along with the literature review has shed light to the following main areas, confirming that the Municipality of Trikala already uses a significant infrastructure in multiple domains. These are: drones, IoT, 5G mobile network, mobile application, citizens engagement communication applications, data visualisation through GIS.

The PUC scenario has been brought into line with the latest EMC trends as follows:

- Integration of Advanced Communication Networks
- Alternative and Resilient Communication Systems
- Use of IoT and Sensor Networks
- Citizen Engagement and Mobile Applications
- UAV and Satellite Communication Readiness

Integration of Advanced Communication Networks: The EMC overview emphasizes the use of 5G networks, LTE-Advanced (LTE-A), and wireless mesh networks for efficient post-disaster communication.

Trikala's crisis preparedness and response system leverages 5G, fiber optics, and Wi-Fi networks to ensure seamless emergency communication. The PUC in Trikala plans to use the 5G network for seamless data connectivity. This coincides with a trend that highlights the importance of 5G networks as emerging technology due to their potential to handle post-disaster communication with ultra-low latency, network densification, and improved efficiency.

The pilot use case in Trikala also emphasizes the use of fibre optics, Wi-Fi hotspots, 5G networking, and exploring LoRa networking for data connectivity. This reflects the trend of using diverse network technologies to ensure reliable communication during emergencies – e.g. Wi-Fi can be used to create temporary access points for communication in emergency situations.

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The city's connectivity is reinforced through a fiber optics network and 60 public Wi-Fi nodes, which are soon to be expanded with 160 additional access points. This ensures free and secure internet access for residents and visitors.

Alternative and Resilient Communication Systems: The EMC literature review highlights Device-to-Device (D2D) communication, Mobile Ad-hoc Networks (MANETs), and IoT-based emergency systems, which align with Trikala's deployment of IoT sensors and GIS mapping.

Figure 24 Map of WiFi nodes

The pilot use case in Trikala focuses on LoRa networks and GIS-based communication for first responders (FRs), along with AI-driven municipal digital data processing.

The pilot use case in Trikala aims to prepare and deploy alternative communication systems. This goal resonates with the broad trend of exploring different technologies for emergency communications that go beyond traditional infrastructure. The outcomes of the literature review mention in this context, for example, device-to-device (D2D) communications, mobile ad-hoc networks (MANETs) and satellite communications.

Additionally, the pilot use case in Trikala plans to use Artificial Intelligence (AI) for real-time decision-making during crisis events and to address cybersecurity challenges. This is in line with the trend of integrating AI for data analysis, threat detection, and improving response capabilities in emergency scenarios. AI-enabled systems can analyse data in real time, identifying patterns and potential threats, enabling proactive response. The integration of AI and IoT has the potential to improve communication during disasters. AI algorithms can analyse data from IoT devices and other sources (e.g., social media) to identify patterns that could indicate an impending disaster. This predictive analysis can improve early warning systems and enable early warning of the population. Integrating AI and IoT can facilitate information sharing and coordination of activities between emergency services, government authorities and other actors.

The Municipality of Trikala, a pioneer in smart city implementation, has already integrated such technologies on a pilot basis. When mobile networks fail due to floods or power outages, alternative communications systems—used by police, fire services, and emergency medical responders—is providing independent communication. Additionally, satellite phones and radio communications are deployed in isolated areas.

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Use of IoT and Sensor Networks: The EMC document discusses IoT-driven crisis management, including sensor networks, real-time data collection, and AI-enhanced predictive analytics.

Trikala’s pilot use case integrates real-time data from environmental monitoring sensors, behaviour tracking, and smart infrastructure for better situational awareness. The implementation of the pilot use case in Trikala involves integrating data from existing smart city infrastructure, such as autonomous buses, smart signs, smart parking and environmental monitoring. This approach reflects the broader trend of using Internet of Things (IoT)-based systems and sensors for better situational awareness in emergency response.

IoT devices such as sensors and wearable electronics can play a key role in monitoring and relaying information in emergency situations. Sensors and devices form ad-hoc communication networks to collect real-time data and support emergency operations. Internet of Things for Public Safety (IoPST) includes wearable devices for emergency responders, such as cameras, sensors and drones, connected via the internet. These devices enable real-time information sharing with command posts and relevant parties, improving coordination and decision-making.

Figure 25 The Smart City Control Center of the Municipality of Trikala

It is important to underline that the Smart City Control Center currently includes various functionalities that need to be expanded. For example, there are the GIS system and Infrastructure Monitoring Sensors. This system of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) assists in mapping and assessing high-risk zones and land-uses. These are often combined with IoT sensors installed on bridges and rivers (e.g., for monitoring water levels) and other locations of critical infrastructure, helping to predict failures or overflows. Specific devices relate to the traffic light operation monitoring system aiming to offer online monitoring of malfunctions and blown light bulbs in the city’s intersections that are regulated by traffic lights. Solenoid valves monitoring and regulating the system of Municipal Water and Sanitation Utility Recording. Last, by using special equipment for environmental factors (such as measuring the concentrations of air pollutants and particulate matter,

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noise levels, water levels, temperature, and other meteorological conditions), the quality of the atmosphere can be evaluated and any potential impact on public health can be assessed.

Citizen Engagement and Mobile Applications: The EMC overview points out the rising use of mobile emergency applications, crowdsourcing platforms, and AI chatbots for crisis communication.

The pilot use case in Trikala focuses on improving the citizen engagement platform 'Trikala check app', so that residents can report incidents and receive updates. Trikala's 'Trikala Check App' is integrated with SPARROW for real-time alerts, reporting, and communication. This is in line with the growing trend of using mobile apps for crisis communication and public engagement. Countries like Finland (112 Suomi), Germany (Warn-App NINA), and Greece (Forest Fire Risk Application) have developed mobile emergency apps to warn citizens about emergencies.

Platforms like the national 112 emergency system, along with apps provided by the municipality of Trikala, offer timely alerts and evacuation instructions to residents. The platform 20000 is designed for the citizens by the city and is playing a key role in this direction. Citizens, either by phone or email—and later through a mobile application, are able to inform the municipality about potential problems and then expect them to be resolved. These systems operate in coordination with the Ministry for Climate Crisis and Civil Protection.

UAV and Satellite Communication Readiness: The EMC document highlights the importance of UAVs, satellite communication, and airborne wireless networks for emergency response in scenarios where terrestrial infrastructure is compromised.

Although the pilot use case in Trikala does not explicitly mention the use of UAVs for communication, the existing smart city infrastructure in Trikala could potentially be integrated with UAV-based solutions for monitoring or as communication relay. This would coincide with the significant trend of using unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) in emergency response as mobile base stations or for data collection.

In Trikala, where smart city technologies are being adopted, drone infrastructure is already in place by the Municipality and operates in collaboration with civil protection and the fire department. Drones are used for monitoring areas in crises, assessing damage to infrastructure (roads, bridges, water and power networks), and locating missing or trapped individuals.

2.1.4. Summary on emerging technologies and communication systems

The literature review identified emerging technologies, the operational survey provided answers to the questions about how security stakeholders communicate in the event of a digital breakdown. The pilot use cases provided observation support for practical applications.

- *Q1: How do FRs and other security stakeholders communicate during digital breakdowns*

In accordance with the analysed literature, decentralized and independent technologies are used for crisis communication in the scenarios described above. The analysis has shown the importance of satellite communication in ensuring connectivity in remote areas and in the event of terrestrial network failure. UAVs are also a key component, especially drones conceived as mobile communication nodes that help establish and restore connectivity. Ad-hoc networks such as

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MANETs/DTNs also serve this purpose, allowing for the creation of a highly resilient network without fixed infrastructure. Based on a literature review, the discourse on emergency communication about the abovementioned issue emphasizes and prioritizes a combination of connectivity, decentralized networks, and mobile nodes that enable communication without a functional central infrastructure.

The survey results show that crisis communication combines traditional and modern technologies. Radio, SMS and mobile phones still form the basis, but drones, mobile applications, MANETs and IoT are also being used more frequently. New technologies are valued for their flexibility and ability to function in real time, especially in environments where infrastructure is compromised. The key factors for the adoption of communication tools are usability and reliability. Systems such as TETRA, SMS and mobile apps were rated the highest. In contrast, newer technologies such as DTN, NDN and crowdsourcing have low adoption rates, often due to poor integration or lack of training. As LTE, TETRA and WLAN dominate the channels, they are important for real-time coordination and wide availability. Satellite and ad-hoc networks are less common but have strategic value in backup scenarios.

The most used tools are SMS, social networks and mobile apps. SMS excels in terms of reach, even in areas with weak signals. Social networks are effective for informing the public. Mobile apps have high potential if they are well integrated. In the event of digital system failures, low-tech tools such as amateur radio, sirens and pre-agreed procedures are essential. The survey confirms that crisis communication cannot be relied upon without redundant and decentralized solutions.

- *Q2: Which emerging technologies can further enhance the resilience and efficiency of communication systems*

Based on the literature review and the above information, the resilience and effectiveness of communication systems lies in using emerging technologies in all analysed thematic clusters (Emergency Communication Systems, Emergency Communication Channels, Emergency Communication Tools). The data corpus emphasizes using AI tools for data analysis, mainly due to the possibilities of real-time data analysis and predictive modelling. An emphasis on using mobile applications and specific digital platforms follows this. These enable immediate response and precise targeting of the desired message. The dissemination of information and the overall form of communication is also relevant to citizens (in the sense of their use as a data source through, for example, sentiment analysis).

The analysed literature, therefore, emphasizes that using smart networks, AI tools, mobile tools for interaction, and real-time data-driven decision-making strengthens the resilience and efficiency of communication.

- *Q3: What are the emerging crisis communications trends observed in the three pilot use cases?*

The emerging trends in crisis communication observed across the pilot use cases in Nicosia, Pilsen, and Trikala reflect a convergence of innovative technologies and strategies aimed at improving emergency preparedness, communication resilience, and public engagement. In Nicosia, the focus lies on alternative communication networks in the event of digital collapse, highlighting the use of drones, IoT, AI-driven tools, and mobile 5G infrastructure to maintain connectivity and decision-

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making during flash floods. Public participation is emphasized through tools like ECOMAPP and SSH questionnaires, while the use of digital twins and cascading scenario modelling further aligns with the trend of real-time situational awareness. In Pilsen, a mature technological ecosystem supports robust EMC infrastructure, exemplified by the long-standing Drones SIT initiative, the IRS Stream system, and a comprehensive LoRa-based IoT network. The city also integrates 5G networks and advanced warning systems to deliver real-time alerts, while mobile applications like Záchranka and Bezpečná Plzeň empower citizens to report emergencies and receive guidance. Additionally, Pilsen's experience with digital twin platforms enhances crisis visualization and coordination. Meanwhile, Trikala's pilot underscores multi-network integration using 5G, fiber optics, and Wi-Fi, complemented by resilient communication alternatives like LoRa, D2D, and MANETs. AI is leveraged for decision-making and cybersecurity, while smart infrastructure and IoT sensors feed real-time data into emergency systems. The enhanced 'Trikala Check App' engages citizens in reporting and receiving crisis updates. Although UAV use is not yet explicit in Trikala, the city's digital infrastructure positions it well for future integration. Overall, the pilot use cases illustrate a shift toward diversified communication tools, AI-enhanced decision support, citizen-centric apps, and advanced visualisation platforms, all aimed at fortifying urban resilience during crises.

2.2. Identified gaps in emergency communication systems

The topic of gaps and shortcomings within emergency communication systems is addressed in the chapters below. These points are based on information gathered from various sources, such as literature review, practical limitations regarding satellite-based communication review, and individual pilot use case analyses. The latter then provide examples by means of which SPARROW will seek to leverage in addressing these shortcomings.

2.2.1. Literature review findings

Based on a critical literature review, a series of potential weaknesses, risks and shortcomings in emergency communication were identified. For clarity, these will be listed and elaborated below:

Uneven technological coverage and uneven implementation of technologies: This mainly concerns the low incidence and emphasis on 5G/LTE technologies in the analysed texts. This may imply weak coverage by these networks or a low level of deployment in a crisis context. At the same time, however, this quantitative indicator may be biased because other types of technologies are overrepresented/emphasized in the overall corpus, and the 'overshadowing' of 5G/LTE technologies is a false result.

However, the analysed data captures and reflects the underutilization of these technologies. In that case, this is a possible limitation of the potential for fast and reliable data communication in the field.

Low representation of D2D communication and network protocols: In the analysed corpus, these technologies have a low level of representation in quantitative terms. D2D technologies are tools enabling direct communication in environments without the appropriate infrastructure. The low quantitative representation of D2D in the analysed corpus may indicate a possible underestimation

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of its importance in building resilient communication systems. However, it is necessary to point out the risk of the same possibility of distortion of quantitative results as in the previous case.

Quantitative dominance of UAVs: The analysed literature greatly emphasizes using UAVs (or drones in general). On the one hand, this may reflect a situation where emergency communication relies heavily on a single type of technology. This may pose a systemic risk and reduce system resilience, as the use of this technology may be limited in certain situations. On the other hand, it is also worth pointing out that the quantitative results may be distorted by the overuse of terms such as ‘UAVs’ (e.g. repetitiveness within the analysed texts).

Minimal emphasis on a resilient society: Another quantified indicator is the low level of emphasis on user inclusion, training, and, in general, working with the population in the context of emergency communication. From a quantitative perspective, the analysed literature shows little emphasis on involving the population in preparing and using crisis tools. This can lead to an overall weakening of the population's reactive capacity and overall social resilience.

Technical and technological limitations: The analysed literature also identifies a series of potential shortcomings of a technical and technological nature. These mainly concern issues such as limited battery capacity and endurance. Drones and many other mobile devices rely on batteries that have limited capacity. This limits their operating time and requires frequent recharging, which can be problematic in emergency situations. We can also include potential interoperability issues in this category. Ensuring compatibility and seamless interaction between different communication systems and technologies is essential for effective coordination and response in emergency situations. It is clear from the analysed literature that interoperability remains a challenge, despite standardization efforts. This category also includes potential insufficient investment and resource allocation. Implementing, maintaining, and upgrading effective emergency communications systems requires significant financial investment and human resources. The analysed data shows that inadequate funding and lack of qualified personnel are common obstacles.

Security and operational limitations: The data corpus also reveals potential shortcomings that can be classified as security and operational limitations. These primarily concern three interconnected areas. First, the analysed discourse strongly emphasizes digital infrastructure and the fact that other systems are potentially dependent on it. This deficiency occurs frequently in the literature. Many modern communication technologies, including drones, IoT devices, and mobile applications, depend on functional digital infrastructure such as the Internet and mobile networks. However, during disasters, damage or failure of this infrastructure is common, rendering these systems inoperable.

Potential lack of cooperation and coordination: The last of the possible shortcomings concerns the need for communication and cooperation. Effective emergency response requires collaboration and partnership between different actors from different contexts. The analysed literature emphasizes that insufficient cooperation and coordination lead to duplication, inefficient use of resources and delays in response.

Practical limitations to satellite-based solutions: user, cost, delays, and prohibitions: An additional literature review also focused on satellite-based communication and its limitations. These include their limited adoption and user familiarity, as well as lower data rates compared to other

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communication technologies. Economically, the cost of satellite communications varies by location. In the U.S., satellite services charge customers between \$1.30 and \$4.00 (1.18 – 3.44 EUR) (per gigabyte per month, whereas mobile data costs typically range from \$1.00 to \$3.33 (0.86 - 2.87 EUR) per gigabyte). This cost disparity can make satellite communications either more or less expensive than mobile data, depending on the region.

Developing and launching a satellite network requires significant time and investment, often taking years. Without pre-existing space infrastructure, satellites are not a viable option for immediate disaster relief efforts. In such situations, terrestrial infrastructure such as cells-on-wheels and microwave links are more commonly deployed. However, when space infrastructure is already in place, satellite communications can be quickly and easily deployed in disaster scenarios.

Some challenges with satellite systems include their susceptibility to atmospheric conditions like rain, which can degrade signal quality, particularly during storms or hurricanes. Latency is another limiting factor, especially in geostationary orbit (GSO) satellite systems. The large distance between GSO satellites and Earth results in higher latency—often exceeding half a second—which can impact real-time applications like voice and video communication. To be noted, this applies to other emerging technologies, such as UAVs, which are also susceptible to meteorologic conditions.

In contrast, non-geostationary orbit (non-GSO) systems operate at much lower altitudes, offering latencies comparable to fixed broadband connections. This makes non-GSO satellites a more effective option for applications requiring low latency, such as disaster response operations.

2.2.2. Vulnerabilities and weak points of individual pilot use cases

This chapter focuses on identifying vulnerabilities and weaknesses in individual pilot use cases in Nicosia, Pilsen, and Trikala, with the aim of identifying key factors that may compromise the scenario, and identification of SPARROW mitigation tools, technologies, or approaches.

Vulnerabilities in the pilot use case in Nicosia

As the pilot use case in Nicosia focuses on preparing for hazards leading to digital collapse due to flash flooding in Nicosia, Cyprus, its aim is to improve preparedness and response during a digital collapse by using alternative communications and dynamic resource management. To do so, it uses several SPARROW technologies, including CITWIN, CESER, ECOMAPP, DYCAMARE, EMER5G, SED and EMPEER.

There are potential risks and challenges associated with the SPARROW use case that can be mitigated by leveraging existing searches. Some key areas of concern include:

- Energy and Infrastructure Dependency
- Network Challenges: Congestion, Interoperability, Prioritization
- Security and Reliability
- Digital Divide and Misinformation
- Operational and Logistical Challenges

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These points demonstrate that while the pilot use case in Nicosia and SPARROW aim to enhance emergency response, it is important to recognize and mitigate potential gaps and challenges by implementing backup systems, ensuring interoperability, and addressing issues such as energy efficiency, security, and the digital divide.

Energy and Infrastructure Dependency

Energy dependency: The reliance of SPARROW technologies, including UAVs, IoT devices and mobile networks, on power sources and a functioning digital infrastructure presents significant risks during disasters, as these elements are vulnerable to failure due to events such as flash floods, which can cause power outages.

Drones, IoT and mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs) face energy limitations due to limited battery life, especially during prolonged disasters. Mitigating this requires energy efficient systems and increased drone deployment. While increased drone deployment is one solution, resource limitations remain. Alternative energy sources, such as portable solar power or energy-efficient grids, should be included in the deployment plan.

Infrastructure Dependency: At the same time, damage to critical infrastructure (power grids, communication towers) can render digital communication solutions ineffective. The use of alternative communication tools such as satellite communications, ad hoc networks and offline tools independent of the regular digital infrastructure as redundancy measures can be used to address this issue.

Network Challenges: Congestion, Interoperability, and Prioritization.

The sharing of spectrum between commercial and emergency networks may lead to congestion or reduced quality of service during periods of high demand, and interoperability challenges between the communication tools of different agencies may hinder coordination. Standardised communication protocols or interoperability frameworks should therefore be established.

In addition, during an emergency, the communications network can become congested, making it difficult for emergency responders to communicate. Prioritising and effectively managing access to channels can become difficult. It is therefore essential to prioritise emergency networks while ensuring that data-driven communications remain functional.

In relation to this, some technologies, such as NVIS, have limited bandwidth, which may limit the types of data that can be transmitted. Prioritising voice calls over data services can hinder effective digital communications. As a mitigation measure, it is suggested that network resource allocation be balanced between voice and data to avoid disruption.

Security and Reliability Concerns: Wireless communication systems are susceptible to a range of security concerns, including eavesdropping and jamming. It is essential to implement robust security protocols (including strong encryption and authentication) and regulations to safeguard sensitive information.

Furthermore, the efficacy of AI-based decision-making is compromised when the data is unreliable or insufficient. Human oversight and validation of AI-driven alerts and recommendations is therefore essential.

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Digital Divide and Misinformation: The reliance on internet communication has the potential to exclude populations in remote areas or areas with poor connectivity. To prevent the digital divide, it is important to ensure that emergency communications reach those who are not online. The use of alternative communication methods, such as radio broadcasts and SMS, alongside internet-based platforms, is therefore recommended.

It is essential to emphasise that warning systems (e.g. sirens, mobile applications) may not be effective in reaching or being understood by all citizens, since oral communication is prone to the dissemination of false information. Consequently, verification of information shared on social media is crucial to prevent the spread of misinformation and rumours.

Operational and Logistical Challenges: A lack of coordination, for example due to differing standards and protocols between different levels of management, can result in unnecessary duplication of actions and an ineffective response. It is therefore important to implement joint training exercises and standardised operational procedures.

The deployment of complex technologies (UAVs, MANETs, 5G solutions) in time-sensitive scenarios may not be feasible. Furthermore, plans developed prior to an event may not be sufficiently flexible to account for the specific circumstances of a given emergency. It is therefore recommended that pre-disaster setup be conducted, and that rapid deployment strategies be in place. In addition, it is essential to ensure compatibility between equipment and technologies, as previously referenced.

The implementation of effective emergency response systems is often hindered by limited financial and human resources, which may be further affected by insufficient training for emergency personnel in the use of advanced communication tools. The regular conducting of drills and the mandatory requirement of hands-on training for first responders are recommended to address these issues.

Vulnerabilities in the pilot use case in Pilsen

The sources identified several potential risks and challenges associated with the SPARROW use case. These included:

- Dependence on digital infrastructure,
- Limited battery life,
- Complexity of integration,
- Limited bandwidth.

Dependence on digital infrastructure: SPARROW heavily relies on digital tools like the Digital Twin platform, drones, and 5G networks, which are susceptible to failures during widespread infrastructure damage or power outages.

Literature sources suggest implementing redundant and backup systems, such as satellite communications and ad-hoc networks, that operate independently of the regular digital infrastructure. The use of offline tools such as radios and satellite phones could also be considered.

Drones are not dependent on external networks such as the internet and are therefore able to create their own wireless network to facilitate communication between devices. In the event of a digital

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breakdown, the only data that would be unavailable is map data. However, this is not a critical issue for drones, particularly for more advanced models. Drones utilise their sensors and algorithms to navigate in space and perform given tasks. They also create their own ad-hoc network, which allows drones to communicate safely and efficiently.

In the event of a disruption to the video transmission, whether due to a lack of mobile signal or other factors, Teradek point-to-point technology is utilized. The directional antennas are equipped with encoders and decoders, enabling the transmission of video signals over extended distances. The maximum range achievable in an unpopulated area is approximately 3 km. This approach enables the streaming of video and its transmission to strategic locations/states.

In case of digital breakdown, prioritization of voice communication over data transmission is recommended. It proved efficient within the last serious floodings in the Czech Republic in September 2024. The collapse of communication was the biggest problem, introducing issues of coverage and quality. Only radios remained, but sometimes the problems were so extreme that even those could not be used. Damage to transmitters and loss of communication has been the biggest problem with some areas completely cut off. Citizens' amateur radios were used in emergency situations as a simple, affordable means of two-way use over a distance of up to fifty kilometres, which is sufficient in given conditions. With citizen radios, it would have avoided the fact that even the town hall could not be reached.

On the other hand, prioritization of voice communication over data transmission is not sufficient due to limited capacities of some people to use ham radios. Not everyone can talk into a radio or mobile phone perfectly and most of the time in case of emergency more confusion arises. For the Drones SIT department, video plus GPS coordinates was the best solution.

Figure 26 Drones SIT's Teradek communication / streaming solution

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As a result, while SPARROW leverages digital tools, it can maintain operational capabilities in the event of widespread infrastructure failures. Redundant systems such as drone-based ad-hoc networks can ensure continued communication. Additionally, drones, with their independent network capabilities, can perform tasks even without external infrastructure. By combining these strategies, SPARROW use case can mitigate risks and maintain its functionality in challenging circumstances.

Limited battery life: Drones and other IoT devices used in SPARROW rely on batteries with limited battery life, which can limit their operating time, especially in prolonged emergency situations. Sources recommend optimizing power consumption for drones and IoT devices and deploying multiple drones to ensure continuity of operations. Further, technologies to extend battery life, such as wireless charging of drones in flight, could be explored.

When considering drones, concurrently, in the most crucial locations, the limitations of batteries can be offset using tether technology. This involves connecting a cable with a "dummy" battery (battery substitute) to the drone, linking the tether to the headquarters, and theoretically enabling flight to unlimited distances, although meteorological constraints and overheating of the machine must be considered.

As far as IoT sensors are mentioned, one advantage of IoT devices is their longevity on battery, which can span multiple years.

While drones and IoT devices offer significant advantages, their reliance on batteries can limit their operational time. To mitigate this, strategies like power optimization, multiple device deployment, and innovative technologies like wireless charging can be employed. Additionally, for drones, tether technology can extend flight duration in critical situations. However, IoT devices, known for their long battery life, can provide continuous monitoring and data collection for extended periods.

Integration complexity: It has been indicated by various sources that the integration of diverse technologies (for example, drones, GIS data, WIS, and LoRa networks) necessitates meticulous planning and coordination, which may result in delays in emergency response times. Moreover, the establishment of a unified platform for the administration and observation of all SPARROW systems may be a potential avenue for consideration. It is recommended that pre-event integration testing be conducted and that standardised protocols for interoperability be established. For this reason, the SPARROW Digital Twin platform will facilitate the integration of discrete technologies. It is anticipated that table-top and field-top exercises will be conducted.

Limited bandwidth, signal interference, and congestion: Sources identified that spectrum sharing, and dense urban environments could lead to signal interference and reduced communication reliability. Data compression, reserved dedicated spectrum bands for emergency use, improve network redundancy to high-density areas, and traffic prioritisation techniques could be implemented to optimise the use of available bandwidth.

LoRa is generally secure and resistant to interference. However, its limited bandwidth can sometimes restrict data transmission rates.

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An alternative method for the transfer of data is the utilisation of Starlink⁴, which is the system currently employed. To illustrate, during a football match, when the BTS (Base Transceiver Station) at the Sokolovna (near Pilsen’s football stadium) is overloaded during the interval, this additional internet connection is a significant benefit. However, there is a possibility that the provider of Starlink may make sudden changes at any time, which could have an adverse effect on this service.

Vulnerabilities in the pilot use case in Trikala

The SPARROW Pilot Use Case (PUC3) in Trikala presents several potential risks and challenges that could be mitigated by drawing on existing best practices in crisis communication and emergency management. Below are some key risks and how leveraging existing solutions could help:

Dependency on digital infrastructure: The pilot use case in Trikala relies on existing smart city infrastructure and data networks, including fibre optic networks, Wi-Fi hotspots, 5G networks and potentially LoRa networks. The literature repeatedly highlights the reliance on functional digital infrastructure as a significant weakness. In the event of a power outage, infrastructure damage due to an emergency or cyber-attack, communications could be disrupted.

Additionally, technologies such as UAVs, IoT sensors, and MANETs (Mobile Ad hoc Networks) have limited battery life especially in harsh situations and high energy consumption in prolonged emergency scenarios.

As mitigation measures, it is recommended to implement energy-efficient protocols, use hybrid energy sources (solar, battery backup), and reduce dependency on a single power source.

Also, the literature proposes to have systems independent of the conventional digital infrastructure, such as satellite communications, ad hoc networks and offline tools (radios, satellite phones). Trikala could consider integrating such backup communication systems. In alignment with the risks related to dependency on digital infrastructure, the Trikala team is exploring the deployment of networks and portable satellite units to maintain communication even when conventional systems fail. The pilot demonstration will also assess the interoperability between SPARROW services and the current local emergency response protocols, ensuring practical applicability in real-world scenarios.

Reliability of wireless networks, congestion or reduced service quality: The pilot use case in Trikala plans to use Wi-Fi, 5G and LoRa networks. The document literature review highlights the limitations of wireless transmission, such as signal interference, packet loss and signal fluctuations, which may affect the reliability of communication. In densely built-up areas, Wi-Fi signal interference can occur. Emergency networks may face congestion or reduced service quality due to spectrum sharing between commercial and emergency systems, especially in urban areas like Trikala.

Thorough testing and coverage planning, implementation of interference detection and mitigation mechanisms could help. Consideration of multiple redundant communication paths would also be beneficial. Prioritization of emergency communication bandwidth using pre-established dynamic spectrum allocation policies. The pilot will pay particular attention to prioritize on real-time the emergency data, leveraging SPARROW’s intelligent network management components. Additionally, field experiments will be organised aiming to explore the feasibility of mobile nodes to dynamically expand coverage and improve congested nodes during crisis events.

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The pilot use case in Trikala includes the integration of data from autonomous buses, smart signs, smart parking systems, environmental monitoring and GIS data into the SPARROW platform (e.g., Trikala Check App, LoRa network, SPARROW systems). Integrated systems are more complex to design, implement and manage and interoperability between different technologies can be problematic. The outputs of the literature review highlight the complexity of integrating different technologies and potential interoperability issues between different systems and devices, as each technology works with different communication protocols. Different emergency communication systems may not be compatible with each other, making it difficult to coordinate rescue operations. Thorough planning, testing, interoperable frameworks that enable seamless communication between different emergency response agencies and standardization of protocols can help overcome interoperability issues.

The SPARROW demonstration pilot in Trikala is aiming to assess interoperable systems by testing real-time data exchange between heterogeneous and fragmented systems, including IoT devices and datasets, GIS platforms, and mobility services. Particular attention will be given on aligning data formats and communication protocols, so that seamless integration across SPARROW components is achieved. Interoperability testing scenarios will also be deployed so that simulated disruptions will be analysed aiming to validate system's resilience and fallback mechanisms.

The SPARROW pilot in Trikala will explore the integration of AI-driven cybersecurity tools, including real-time detection to identify unusual network activity. Emphasis will be given to maintaining the performance of the system, while implementing solid security measures.

In the SPARROW pilot, AI-driven analytics will be combined with human expertise and decision-making to ensure reliability in emergency urban situations. The pilot will include validation workflows where AI-generated alerts and specific recommendations are reviewed by trained responders before action is taken.

Integration of different technologies: the pilot use case in Trikala includes the integration of data from autonomous buses, smart signs, smart parking systems, environmental monitoring and GIS data into the SPARROW platform (e.g., Trikala Check App, LoRa network, SPARROW systems). Integrated systems are more complex to design, implement and manage and interoperability between different technologies can be problematic. The outputs of the literature review highlight the complexity of integrating different technologies and potential interoperability issues between different systems and devices, as each technology works with different communication protocols. Different emergency communication systems may not be compatible with each other, making it difficult to coordinate rescue operations. Thorough planning, testing, interoperable frameworks that enable seamless communication between different emergency response agencies and standardization of protocols can help overcome interoperability issues.

Security and cyber threats: The use of AI and the integration of different data streams increases potential cyber security risks. The literature states that wireless communication systems are susceptible to security risks, such as eavesdropping, cyberattacks, data breaches, and jamming. Appropriate security mechanisms such as end-to-end encryption, intrusion detection systems (IDS),

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and AI-driven anomaly detection for securing data transmission need to be implemented to protect data and infrastructure.

Complexity of real-time data processing: The pilot use case in Trikala plans to use AI for real-time data analysis and decision making. The literature review points out that machine learning depends on data and algorithms that may not be available or reliable in emergency situations, and that predictive models based on historical data may not always be accurate in unpredictable situations. There is also a risk of overlooking signals that could be detected by a human analyst and biases in the data leading to incorrect conclusions. Combining AI with human oversight and expertise, regularly validating and updating models and algorithms to account for different scenarios could reduce these risks. Establish human-in-the-loop oversight, ensuring that AI-generated recommendations are validated by emergency responders before implementation.

Ensuring prioritization and response to vulnerable citizens: Trikala aims to double the effectiveness of prioritization and response to vulnerable citizens. However, the literature warns that prioritization systems can lead to discrimination against ordinary users since restrictions on normal services can prevent important communication between people in the affected area.

In addition, some citizens, particularly vulnerable populations (elderly, disabled, non-tech individuals), may have limited access to smart city communication tools like the Trikala Check App.

Equitable and inclusive access to services and information for all groups needs to be ensured by use of multi-channel communication strategies (radio, SMS, TV alerts) to ensure accessibility beyond digital platforms preventing digital divide.

The SPARROW pilot will deploy multi-level alert and communication strategies to ensure that critical information is reaching all citizens during urgent cases. This is including social groups without access to digital tools, and other vulnerable groups such as elder citizens, citizens in peri-urban areas that are underserved in terms of accessibility and mobility services, or persons with disabilities etc. Specific measures will include a structured and parallel use of multiple means, for example SMS alerts, local radio broadcasts, and coordination with social care services to identify and assist vulnerable individuals.

Limited capacity and reliability of the mobile 'Trikala check app': Trikala envisages an increase in requests and communication through the Trikala Check App. The literature states that the reliability of mobile apps may be limited in some areas. In the event of network congestion during an emergency, application functionality may be affected. Also mentioned is the limited awareness of apps and the fact that not all citizens actively use them. Even though mobile apps exist, many people are either unaware of them or have not installed or fully explored their functions. Promoting the app and its functionality among citizens, and offering alternative communication channels in parallel could reduce the risks associated with exclusive reliance on the app. The literature also mentions the digital divide, where some citizens may not have access to the internet or smartphones.

Additionally, emergency communication via social media and mobile apps may be prone to misinformation and rumours, leading to panic and disinformation during a crisis. Therefore, to leverage AI-powered misinformation detection tools, official fact-checking mechanisms, and trusted government sources to validate crisis information is recommended.

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The SPARROW pilot will organise awareness campaigns aiming to increase the public acceptance and scalability of Trikala Check App and its emergency features. The need of promoting parallel communication channels such as SMS alerts and local radio will be discussed. It is crucial to ensure a trusted, verified messaging from official sources that will maintain public trust and effective communication.

2.3. Best practices in emergency communications

Best practices in emergency communications is a topic to be discussed in the following chapters, based on information obtained from literature review, satellite communication within crisis case studies, and successful approaches identified in individual pilot use cases.

2.3.1. Literature review outcomes

Within the literature review, several strategies and recommended practices that could be applied pre, during and post-emergency were identified. This allowed to draft ten guiding principles for effective emergency communication that were consequently summarized, emphasizing the importance of redundancy and resilience, interoperability, prioritization, security, use of drones, clear and concise communication, trainings, public involvement, coordination, and constant technological innovation of processes.

Redundancy and resilience: This means that systems should be able to function even if some components are damaged or fail. Redundancy and resilience can be achieved through technological diversification, with the use of different technologies — such as satellite, cellular and radio networks — minimising the risk of communication failure if one technology malfunctions. Implementing backup power sources and communication paths ensures uninterrupted operation in the event of primary infrastructure failure. Furthermore, incorporating redundant routes into the network topology mitigates the risk of failure.

Interoperability: It represents the ability of different systems to communicate and share information seamlessly. IP networks can serve as a communication protocol between different emergency response teams. Using standardised protocols and interfaces is recommended to facilitate system integration and interoperability.

Prioritization of emergency communications: Sources agree that prioritising emergency traffic on the network is essential for ensuring the timely delivery of critical messages. The introduction of priority groups for emergency services and authorised users, together with the implementation of call and traffic prioritisation systems, is vital. It is also recommended that the impact of network congestion on emergency communications is minimised.

Security: Ensuring network security and protecting sensitive data are critical aspects of emergency communications. This involves using encryption to protect confidential information, authenticating the identity of users and devices, restricting network and data access to authorised users only, and protecting systems from cyber-attacks.

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Use of drones: UAVs are an effective tool for extending network coverage, collecting data and supporting emergency communications. In areas with damaged infrastructure, drones can serve as temporary base stations, allowing real-time data collection. For example, they can collect and transmit aerial imagery.

Clear and understandable communication: Using clear and understandable language when communicating with emergency responders and the public is essential for an effective emergency response. Messages should include clear instructions and a timeframe for action, as well as a link to a trusted source. Pictures and videos can help attract attention and communicate information more effectively.

Training and exercises: Regular training and exercises for emergency responders in the use of communication technologies and procedures are essential to ensure emergency preparedness. Simulations help responders prepare for different scenarios and identify weaknesses in plans and procedures. Regular exercises and evaluations also help validate and improve communication recovery processes.

Public Involvement: Effective communication with the public is key to building trust and coordinating an emergency response. As two-way communication with the community enables feedback and responses to concerns and needs, this shall be established.

Use of social media: social media is used to disseminate information quickly, monitor public sentiment and, nevertheless, spread rumours. As mentioned above, open and transparent communication with the public helps to build trust.

Coordination and Collaboration: Sources emphasise the importance of coordination and collaboration among the various agencies and organisations involved in emergency response. They recommend establishing effective governance structures, clear policies and procedures, and sufficient funding; building partnerships with other stakeholders prior to a crisis; and ensuring consistent information is shared across different organisations and platforms to facilitate the coordination of shared communication resources and activities, and to ensure clear and reliable communication.

Technology and Innovation: Resources highlight the use of modern technology and innovation in emergency communications. The use of AI for early warning systems, predictive analytics and personalised communications, as well as for early risk detection and real-time situation monitoring with IoT sensors, is envisaged.

In summary, the literature review highlights a multifaceted approach to emergency communications, emphasizing the need for resilient, secure, and interoperable systems, underpinned by clear communication, coordinated efforts, public engagement, and ongoing technological innovation.

2.3.2. Satellite communications in crisis situations: case studies from real disasters

Following case studies highlight the use of satellite technology in disaster recovery operations, like those planned to emulate in pilot use cases. They describe three representative examples of the kinds

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of services used and implemented during real-life disaster recovery operation⁵¹ focusing specifically on the use of alternative telecommunications options and satellite VSAT technology, aligning with SPARROW approach.

Haiti earthquake (2021)⁵²

The southern part of Haiti was the victim of a devastating 7.2 magnitude earthquake, resulting in the injury of 12,763 and the death of 2,248 people, as well as a USD 187,3 million response cost (approximately EUR 160,078 million). The earthquake exposed the country's already-existing susceptibilities. At the time of the disaster, Haiti was dealing with growing food shortages, rampant gang violence, and declining infrastructure – liabilities that have only worsened after the earthquake.

Whilst the damage to ICT infrastructure was severe and is still being quantified, 52 affected areas were rendered inaccessible because of it – particularly the areas along the route from Port-au-Prince to Les Cayes. Data traffic and intermittent coverage by Mobile Network Operators were caused by both the earthquake's effect and the flow of rescuers to the impacted areas. Furthermore, heavy gang presence added to the access difficulty for response teams in contacting victims given the security threat. This also meant the limitation of access to sites where quality coverage may have been attained also restricted the installation of VHF repeaters for security communications. Internet Service Provider (ISP) services were also damaged and, following the influx of humanitarians, were under strain in the initial days of the response.

The ETC provided the government with a response plan that encompassed recommended satellite communication efforts. As additional support, the ITU (International Telecommunication Union) provided its Disaster Connectivity Map system, developed in conjunction with the ETC and Global System for Mobile Communications Association (GSMA), to map connectivity gaps in affected areas.

Whilst this Disaster Connectivity Map system was effective in exposing areas that had lost connectivity, it also became evident that most affected areas lacked coverage prior to the earthquake. To this end, Telecoms Sans Frontières (TSF) and other international ICT responders such as Ericsson Response moved in to provide support in establishing VSAT connectivity.

The humanitarian response operations led by the ETC is a clear example of how private and public entities can partner up to support such efforts after the disaster strikes. The work, which involved the establishment of a radio network for security communications, was the result of an initiative jointly led by the WFP, UNDSS, emergency.lu and Ericsson Response.

⁵¹<https://www.eurisy.eu/satellite-based-services-for-disaster-risk-management/> Eurisy. (2022, July 8). Satellite-based Services for Disaster Risk Management in Athens. <https://www.eurisy.eu/satellite-based-services-for-disaster-risk-management/>.

⁵²<https://www.etcluster.org/document/etc-haiti-sitrep-1-14-19-august-2021> Emergency Telecommunications Cluster (ETC). (2021, August 19). ETC Haiti Sitrep #1: 14–19 August 2021. <https://www.etcluster.org/document/etc-haiti-sitrep-1-14-19-august-2021>.

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Mozambique – cyclone Idai (2019)⁵³

In 2019, Tropical Cyclone Idai made landfall near Beira City in Sofala Province, central Mozambique, causing widespread devastation. The cyclone claimed the lives of over 600 people, injured 1,600 others, and resulted in approximately USD \$773 million (664 million EUR) million in damages to Mozambique's buildings and infrastructure. As Cyclone Idai moved inland as a tropical storm, it also caused significant damage in eastern Zimbabwe.

A disaster report by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) revealed Mozambique's critical shortcomings in emergency preparedness, coordination, and response. These included the lack of a backup communication system for issuing alerts and managing disaster relief, as well as the absence of a city evacuation strategy, particularly in low-lying, vulnerable regions. At an international pledging conference to secure funds for Mozambique's reconstruction, WMO Secretary-General Petteri Taalas acknowledged the need for Mozambique to "build resilience."

In the aftermath of Cyclone Idai, satellite-based technologies played a crucial role in supporting relief efforts. The Copernicus Emergency Mapping Service and the International Charter Space and Major Disasters leveraged satellite data to provide on-demand imaging of flooded areas, assisting in the coordination of rescue and recovery operations. Télécoms Sans Frontières (TSF) deployed VSAT satellite equipment to facilitate humanitarian coordination and established broadband-enabled centres to support relief activities.

Mozambique's reliance on fiber infrastructure had progressively diminished its use of satellite backhaul traffic. Following the cyclone, the Communications Regulatory Authority (ARECOM) admitted underestimating the risks associated with phasing out satellite technology in favour of fiber. Reflecting on this, ARECOM stated, "It was a mistake to phase out satellite just because fiber arrived."

This case study thus underscores the vulnerability of terrestrial infrastructure to disruptions and the critical need for diverse and redundant communication systems employing multiple technologies. The event also highlights the versatile applications of satellite-based technologies during disasters. Satellites can provide vital real-time data for monitoring natural events and mapping affected regions, enabling better-coordinated emergency responses and mitigating the consequences of disasters.

German floods (2021)⁵⁴

Although many of the previously mentioned incidents occurred in countries particularly vulnerable to climate-related disasters, developed nations are not exempt from such threats. Despite having advanced infrastructure, resources, and expertise, these countries also face significant vulnerabilities. A notable example occurred in 2021, when Germany was struck by devastating floods caused by intense rainfall. According to Télécoms Sans Frontières (TSF), the collapse of

⁵³ <https://www.etcluster.org/document/etc-mozambique-sitrep-1>

Emergency Telecommunications Cluster (ETC). (2019, March 17). ETC Mozambique SitRep #1.

<https://www.etcluster.org/document/etc-mozambique-sitrep-1>.

⁵⁴ https://www.geerassociation.org/components/com_geer_reports/geerfiles/GEER%20Report%202021%20Western%20European%20Floods%20Final%20w%20GPS%20coordinates_comp.pdf

Lemnitzer, A., Stark, N., Gardner, M., George, M., Mueller, J., Nichols, E., ... Willems, J. (2022). Geotechnical Reconnaissance of the 2021 Western European Floods (GEER-076). Geotechnical Extreme Events Reconnaissance (GEER) Association.

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telecommunications and power infrastructure made it “extremely difficult for relief organizations to contact victims, locate missing persons, and coordinate their efforts.”

The floods claimed at least 184 lives and caused widespread damage to critical infrastructure, including communication networks. Even a week after the initial rainfall, mobile networks in the affected regions remained unstable, with operators still working to restore services. The breakdown of telecommunication systems severely impeded rescue efforts and intensified the human impact of the disaster. Although rescue teams were equipped with satellite phones, they were unable to use them due to a regional ban on satellite communication. This restriction was imposed to avoid interference with a radio telescope operated by the Max Planck Institute for Radio Astronomy in Bad Münstereifel-Effelsberg. Within a 30-kilometer radius of the telescope, the Federal Network Agency prohibits satellite services—including those provided by Iridium, Globalstar, and Starlink. According to Iridium, this restriction zone is unique globally. Four days after the flooding, and in response to mounting concerns from affected areas, the Federal Network Agency temporarily lifted the Iridium service ban to support emergency operations. Iridium swiftly updated its satellite software to allow communication within the disaster zone. To further support relief efforts, the agencies dispatched a specially equipped vehicle to the most heavily impacted areas, delivering critical VSAT based telecommunication services to local populations and assisting emergency teams in coordinating their response. As the large-scale natural disasters frequently lead to the failure of terrestrial communication networks, primarily due to the destruction of physical infrastructure, the response to Germany’s floods could have been significantly enhanced by timely access to satellite-based communications. Ensuring such access during emergencies requires not only the necessary hardware but also regulatory flexibility regarding spectrum use. To improve resilience in future events, it is essential to establish coordination protocols with protected facilities—such as radio telescopes—to enable temporary spectrum sharing during crises. Developing electromagnetic-safe emergency procedures and contingency plans would substantially strengthen both preparedness and response efforts in vulnerable regions. The case studies have thus confirmed the key role of effective coordination and cooperation between the public and private sectors, the availability of redundant communication systems, timely access to infrastructure, as well as shed light on regulatory flexibility. At the same time, they have demonstrated that the absence of these elements significantly increases vulnerability in crisis situations.

2.3.3. Successful approaches and tools of individual pilot use cases

This section presents the individual use cases developed within the SPARROW project and assesses their alignment with identified best practices in emergency communication.

Good practices from the pilot use case in Nicosia

The literature review identified 10 guiding principles for effective emergency communication. They focus on effective information sharing in times of crisis, integration of different technologies to ensure reliable and resilient communications, use of drones and wireless networks for fast and effective responses and building of trust between emergency responders and the public through transparent and understandable communications.

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The description of the pilot use case in Nicosia scenario is aligned with the following recommended practices:

- Emergency communication and prioritization
- Energy-efficient and redundant networks
- Technology integration for situational awareness
- Interoperability and rapid deployment
- Public engagement and awareness

Emergency communication and prioritization

Sources identified following principles related to prioritization and emergency communication that might be relevant to the pilot use case in Nicosia:

Prioritization aspects: In emergency situations, it is important to prioritise voice communication over data communication. Also, it is vital to establish priority groups where public safety users should be prioritized in terms of radio resource allocation and connection establishment.

- *Prioritizing Communications* (eMPS, network resources): In the pilot use case in Nicosia, where communication between emergency response teams and citizens is critical, systems that prioritize emergency calls and messages can be implemented. Therefore, it is important to prioritize emergency communications and ensure timely delivery of critical information.
- *Data prioritization* (emergency communications, timely delivery): In the pilot use case in Nicosia, it is important to prioritize emergency communications and ensure timely delivery of critical information. Implementation of prioritization will ensure delivery of important messages even during network congestion.
- *Prioritization of calls and traffic:* (message delivery during congestion): Implementation of prioritization will ensure delivery of important messages even during network congestion. It is important to diversify the means of disseminating warnings and information after a disaster, including TV, radio, mobile networks, social media, sirens and video turnstiles.
- *Virtualization technologies* (SD-RAN and RAN slicing allowing flexible network sharing): Enables flexible and efficient sharing of network resources and optimization of network utilization for emergency communications.

Communication-related aspects:

- *Timely and clear communication:* (sharing key information): Key information should be shared in a timely and clear manner with affected communities.
- *Selective message delivery:* (region-based messages): Messages should be delivered based on region to reduce the amount of redundant data in the network. This strategy classifies messages by destination address into regional central nodes and ferry nodes. This ensures accurate delivery of data packets to the appropriate region and reduces redundant data packets in the network.

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- *Automation of data collection and patient triage:* (wireless sensors, algorithms): Wireless sensors and special algorithms speed up patient triage and streamline response.
- *Use of LMR:* (dedicated frequencies, minimizes interference): The use of dedicated LMR (land mobile radio) frequencies minimizes the risk of interference and ensures communication availability even in case of network congestion. Isolation and prioritisation of emergency services' traffic ensures reliable communication even in crisis situations.
- *Communications security:* (encryption, data protection): Due to the sensitivity of information shared during emergencies, it is essential to secure communication systems and protect data through encryption.

SPARROW's Emergency Communication Prioritization Module (ECOPRIM) envisions a revolutionary approach to communication prioritisation during emergencies. It introduces a paradigm shift by integrating context awareness, analysing data from a multitude of sources. These features collectively position SPARROW as a game-changer, redefining the standards for emergency internet provision beyond the state of the art. Additionally, the SPARROW project aims to evolve its in-house "5G-in-a-box" solution EMER5-G (currently at TRL 3), expanding it with cognitive spectrum usage capabilities, along with a context-aware traffic prioritisation mechanism.

In the pilot use case in Nicosia, how things develop, as people's own reports on their situation, based on questionnaires developed by SSH, can cause those responding to change what they see as important. This is in line with the idea of giving priority to what is most important.

Energy-Efficient and Redundant Networks

Energy saving technologies, e.g. D2D, MANET, with minimal energy consumption. D2D and MANET, which are optimized for minimal energy consumption, can be used to maintain the operation of communication systems in situations where access to power is limited (e.g., power failure).

Redundancy and backup for critical systems, minimize damage risk. Redundancy and backup are essential for critical systems to minimize the risk of physical damage.

Diversification of access technologies e.g. by means of satellite, TETRA, GSM, WiMAX. The use of different technologies will ensure the availability of communication even if one technology fails.

Optimization of drone placement minimizing energy consumption. In the pilot use case in Nicosia, drone placement algorithms should be optimized to maximize coverage and quality of service, minimize energy consumption and achieve uniform load distribution.

Within the pilot use case in Nicosia, the principle of redundancy will be aligned by the deployment of SPARROW's alternative communication tools (EMER5G, SEDs, EMPEER), that will enable citizens to communicate amongst themselves and with authorities.

Network Redundancy and energy-efficiency will also be achieved through SPARROW's Signal-area Expansion Drones (SEDs) to redefine the possibilities of aerial support in emergency response. These advanced drones are envisioned to operate with remarkable energy autonomy, utilising charging bases across the area of operation, enabling them to maintain sustained flight over extended periods, a critical advantage in protracted emergencies.

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Technology integration for situational awareness

Sources identified following potential of integrating different technologies to create a robust and flexible system, comprising:

The utilisation of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) as temporary base stations has emerged as a promising solution to restore communication in affected areas. The integration of UAVs with real-time data facilitates the collection of crucial information that supports decision-making processes for emergency responders. The employment of UAVs as base stations ensures seamless connectivity in areas where infrastructure has been compromised, thus enhancing the efficiency and efficacy of emergency response operations.

The utilisation of multimedia applications for the purpose of sharing images, video, voice, and situational awareness is of paramount importance in the context of rescue operations. The leveraging of applications that facilitate the sharing of multimedia content (images, video, voice) for the purpose of situational awareness and the coordination of rescue operations is a crucial element of this process.

NDN (Named Data Networking) allows hierarchical naming, flexible communication. A hierarchical naming scheme can be used to enable flexible and independent communication between intervening components for efficient communication.

KubeEdge, a system that centralises cloud-based monitoring to make services more resilient. It makes sure that workloads continue to operate even when there are network disruptions or hardware failures. In the pilot use case in Nicosia, KubeEdge can create a cloud-based system for monitoring and updating tasks of intervening components.

Analysis and feedback ensuring effectiveness evaluation, improvement, since the effectiveness of crisis communications should be regularly evaluated and adjusted as necessary.

Combination of IoT, AI, and cloud computing to enhance the visualization of disaster-hit areas (e.g., CITWIN's 3D representations) is mentioned.

Situational awareness in SPARROW the pilot use case in Nicosia will be achieved by integrating following tools:

The utilisation of SED drones for the purpose of conducting aerial assessments facilitates the collection of real-time data (e.g. video) to inform the decision-making process of emergency responders. In the context of the SPARROW project, drones offer advanced data services, including real-time video streaming and remote sensing, thereby ensuring that First Responders (FRs) are equipped with critical, high-resolution information.

The City Digital Twin (CITWIN) will be utilised to create a visualisation of the disaster-hit area for the purpose of Digital Breakdown Simulation. This will include three-dimensional representation of structures in the area, critical infrastructure locations, and personnel. The result of this will be dynamic, real-time city-scale simulations that not only visualise the current state of urban environments and CIS, but also predict future vulnerabilities and anticipate evolving risks.

DYCAMARE is a critical asset management recommendation engine that aims to ensure situational awareness in emergency situations by providing dynamic, lightweight, and accurate

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recommendations, even in situations where data and resources are limited. It achieves this through a user-driven, semi-empirical approach that integrates user input, fuzzy logic, and learning from past experiences and lessons learned, thereby improving the accuracy of its recommendations. The VASE and CESER tools are to be integrated within this platform.

Interoperability and Rapid Deployment

Sources highlight the integration and collaboration of different technologies as a best practice in emergency communications. Combining the strengths of each technology allows to overcome their limitations and create a robust, reliable and flexible communications system.

Spectrum Sharing: (between operators, continuity of communication): In the event of a single mobile network outage, spectrum sharing between operators can be used to ensure continuity of communication. Dedicated frequency bands, especially the 700 MHz and 400 MHz, have been designated for public safety in Europe to ensure robust communication during disasters. This is relevant to the situation in Nicosia, where there may be a communications outage.

Self-Organizing Networks (SON) - automatic reconfiguration, infrastructure damage: The implementation of Self-Organizing Networks (SONs) allows for automatic network reconfiguration in case of infrastructure damage, which is crucial for maintaining communication even during floods.

Integration of different technologies (e.g. IoT, satellite, LMR, LTE): Combining different communication technologies (e.g. AWRN, IoT, satellite communication) to create a robust and flexible system. Integration of LMR and LTE to exploit the reliability of LMR and the broadband capabilities of LTE.

Edge computing: (data processing, reduced latency): Processing data at the edge of the network reduces latency and improves efficiency in situations where the central infrastructure is unavailable, which can be useful in the event of a digital outage.

Rapid Deployment: (mobile technologies, drones, mesh networks): In the pilot use case in Nicosia, rapid deployment of communication systems is crucial, which can be ensured by using mobile technologies such as drones and mesh networks. Systems must be quickly deployable and fault tolerant.

Interoperability: (devices and systems, IP-based networks): Due to the involvement of different organizations in the response in the pilot use case in Nicosia, it is important to ensure that devices and systems can communicate with each other using IP-based networks.

Scalability (support growing users, expand coverage): Communication systems in the pilot use case in Nicosia should be scalable to support a growing number of users and expand geographic coverage.

Mobility support (reliable communication for moving personnel): Reliable communications for emergency personnel and equipment must be ensured even as they move around the affected area.

Use of IP networks (interoperability between teams): IP networks ensure interoperability between different emergency response teams.

MCOP (Mission Critical Open Platform - open platform, MC capabilities): Creating an open platform for mission critical (MC) communications that reduces integration efforts and enables the development of applications that leverage the MC capabilities of LTE and 5G networks.

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Public Engagement and Awareness

Within the literature review, the sources identified strategies that could enhance public involvement. Use of SMS messages for efficient information dissemination. In a situation where voice communication is overloaded or unavailable, SMS messages can be used to efficiently and reliably disseminate key information and warnings.

Community engagement supporting active involvement, before, during, after. The community should be actively involved in the communication process, before, during and after the crisis.

Two-way communication enabling community feedback, concerns. It is important to get feedback from communities, and to consider their concerns and needs.

Multi-channel approach to communication comprising traditional and digital media. Combining traditional media (radio, TV) with digital platforms (social media, SMS) will ensure a wider reach and reach different target groups.

Localised communication with tailored messages, trusted networks. Messages should be tailored to specific cultural, linguistic and geographical contexts and use trusted local networks. Messages should be delivered based on region to reduce the amount of redundant data in the network.

Within PUC 1, SPARROW intends to deploy ECOMAPP, enabling the communication of citizens and FRs. Also, the active public engagement will be supported by the deployment of SPARROW's alternative communication tools (EMER5G, SEDs, EMPEER), enabling citizens to communicate amongst themselves and with authorities, supplying the necessary dynamic data to CESER.

Good practices applied in the pilot use case in Pilsen

Within the literature review, various recommendations principles for effective emergency communication were identified. The pilot use case scenario in Pilsen has been brought into line with the following recommended practices:

- Redundancy and resilience,
- Prioritization of emergency communications,
- Clear and understandable communication,
- Security,
- Use of drones,
- Technology and Innovation.

Redundancy and backup systems: Sources stress the importance of redundancy and backup systems to ensure continuous communication even in case of infrastructure damage. Redundancy can be achieved by diversification of technologies, backup systems and network topology.

The use of different technologies, such as satellite, cellular and radio networks, minimizes the risk of communication failure if one technology fails. The implementation of backup power sources and communication paths ensures uninterrupted operation in the event of failure of the primary infrastructure. The use of redundant routes in the network topology reduces the risk of failure.

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To reach the public effectively, a multichannel redundant communication approach (including SMS, social media, mobile applications, and traditional media) is recommended. This redundancy ensures that warnings reach a wider audience even if one communication path fails.

The SPARROW's PUC2 Traffic Control Failure objective compliant with the above-described principles, since its aim is to develop and implement alternative traffic control strategies in Pilsen to address the immediate aftermath of a digital breakdown, therefore in accordance with the principles of redundancy and diversification of technologies. SPARROW will focus on integrating the alternative traffic control measures into SPARROW's CITWIN platform, providing a realistic 3D representation of the city's traffic infrastructure

Prioritization: Sources agree on the need to prioritize emergency traffic in the network to ensure timely delivery of critical messages. Introduction of priority groups for emergency services and authorized users, implementation of call and traffic prioritization systems, and congestion management mechanisms minimizing the impact of network congestion on emergency communications is seen as essential.

Recommended practices suggest prioritising communication and implementation of priority access for FRs. In emergency situations, it is important to prioritise voice communication over data communication. SPARROW could consider implementing systems that allow this, such as the eMPS (enhanced mobile phone system) mentioned in the resources. The introduction of priority groups for emergency responders, as described in the resources, could further improve the effectiveness of communication during a crisis. Implementing priority access systems like eMPS, which prioritize emergency communications, could ensure that FRs (First Responders) always have priority during a traffic control failure. This can reduce congestion and prioritize critical messages in SPARROW's emergency communication network.

The SPARROW's PUC2 Traffic Control Failure objective is aligned with the aforementioned principles, as its objective is to enhance the priority given to FRs' access routes, ensuring a swift and unimpeded response to emergency situations by utilising SPARROW's emergency communication system, including the self-powered ruggedized mobile 5G Network, to prioritise and streamline communication for FRs.

Figure 27 Emergency vehicle warning displayed in the car driving in Pilsen's mobility test polygon

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Clear and understandable communication: Using clear and understandable language when communicating with emergency responders and the public is key to effective emergency response. Messages should include clear instructions, a time frame for action, and a link to a trusted source.

SPARROW's Warning Information System (WIS) could be optimized by targeting alerts to specific regions or vulnerable groups using both digital and traditional media channels for inclusivity and accessibility.

The utilisation of GIS data in SPARROW Pilsen use case for accurate mapping of infrastructure locations and effective crisis management. The Warning Information System (WIS) and GIS data will play a crucial role in disseminating real-time alerts and mapping CI locations. While the SPARROW use case highlights the role of geographic information systems in targeted messaging, there is an opportunity to explore how these messages can be further refined to address the specific vulnerabilities and needs of different groups.

Security: Ensuring network security and protection of sensitive data is a critical aspect of emergency communications. The use of encryption to safeguard confidential information, the authentication of user and device identity, access control to restrict network and data access to authorised users, and cybersecurity measures to protect systems from cyber-attacks are regarded as indispensable.

The implementation of robust encryption and access control within the SPARROW communications framework will ensure the security of sensitive data in the event of an emergency situation. This measure is vital to prevent unauthorised access and to maintain public confidence in emergency messaging systems.

While this particular use case does not explore the potential for digital breakdowns, it is essential to acknowledge that cyberattacks pose a substantial threat that could result in widespread digital disruptions. Incorporating security aspects could present an interesting impetus for further consideration.

Use of drones: The utilisation of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), or drones, has been demonstrated to be an effective tool for the extension of network coverage, the collection of data, and the provision of support for emergency communications. Drones in SPARROW could be configured for optimal trajectory and altitude to provide extensive coverage with minimal energy use. This aligns with best practices that recommend using drones as temporary communication base stations and signal relays during failures. Optimizing the 3D placement of drones, including their altitude, can maximize signal coverage and link quality. SPARROW could also consider using AI to predict signal strength between drones and IoT devices, which would help maintain stable connections and optimize drone routes.

Although this particular use case doesn't address it, the optimization of drone trajectories and flight altitudes presents a compelling challenge for future research and implementation.

Technology and Innovation: Resources support the use of modern technology and support innovation in emergency communications. These technologies include artificial Intelligence (AI for early warning, predictive analytics, and personalized communications), edge computing to reducing latency and improving energy efficiency, and IoT sensors for early risk detection and real-time situation monitoring.

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Machine learning could help predict high-risk zones and optimize resource allocation for FRs based on historical traffic failure data. AI tools can also help predict traffic disruptions, enabling proactive adjustments in SPARROW's Digital Twin model to maintain traffic flow during breakdowns. While SPARROW does not currently use AI, sources indicate that AI can play an important role in emergency communications. For example, AI could be used to predictively analyse data from IoPST (Internet of Public Safety Things) devices to anticipate criminal activity or natural disasters, enabling public safety authorities to take preventative measures.

SPARROW's emergency communication system will rely on LoRa for continuous connectivity, the potential for AI integration offers further enhancing the system's capabilities.

Good practices from the pilot use case in Trikala

Based on the literature review, several tools and methodologies can be adapted to strengthen the SPARROW project's pilot use case in Trikala. Below are key recommended practices aligned with SPARROW's objectives:

Prioritization in emergency communication systems: The pilot use case in Trikala focuses on prioritizing vulnerable citizens to ensure availability of emergency services. The results of the literature recommend prioritizing emergency communications, prioritizing critical users and services (giving precedence to critical users and services), and introducing priority groups for emergency responders. Implementing such a prioritisation system within the communication channels used in PUC3 (such as the 'Trikala check app') would ensure that requests for assistance from vulnerable citizens such as those in digital houses with elderly citizens of special needs are prioritised. It is also recommended to prioritise voice calls over data in emergency situations, which should be considered when designing communication protocols for PUC3.

Auto-configuration using AI and machine learning: The use of Self-Organizing Networks (SON) and machine learning models is recommended to optimize resource allocation and predict emergencies in real time. Thus, literature proposes the use of machine learning to optimize resource allocation and predict emergency situations. Trikala is already planning to use AI for data analysis and real-time decision making. The application of machine learning could further improve the predictive capabilities of the pilot use case in Trikala, for example by predicting potential crisis points during the 'Mill of Elves' event based on historical attendance and incident data. The use of Machine Learning models to optimize resource allocation and predict emergency situations is aligning with SPARROW's AI-based crisis management tools.

Ensuring reliable communication via SMS: SMS is highlighted as a robust and efficient communication channel, particularly when other networks are overloaded. Thus, literature mentions the use of SMS messages for efficiency and reliability. In the context of the pilot use case in Trikala, SMS messages could serve as a reliable backup communication channel for disseminating important information to citizens, especially those who may not have constant access to the Internet or a smart application. The project should also explore spectrum sharing between mobile operators to maintain uninterrupted service during network failures.

Rapid deployment & connectivity solutions: Trikala's plan to integrate LoRa networks aligns with best practices recommending low-power, long-range communications for sensor-based crisis monitoring.

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Alternative communication systems and their rapid deployment: the pilot use case in Trikala focuses on the preparation and deployment of alternative communication systems. In this context, the literature emphasises rapid deployment using technologies such as UAVs (unmanned aerial vehicles), mesh networks and satellite systems. The use of UAVs as temporary base stations to create ad-hoc networks in case of failure of conventional networks could be very relevant for the pilot use case in Trikala, especially to ensure communication during large events such as the 'Mill of Elves'. Drones could also analyse and transmit real-time data (e.g. aerial imagery) for better decision making by emergency services. Trikala is already considering the integration of different data networks, and adding the ability to rapidly deploy a communications infrastructure using drones would enhance its resilience.

In consequence, optimizing drone trajectory and altitude to balance signal coverage and loss could be suggested if the pilot use case in Trikala is considering the use of drones. The literature recommends optimizing drone trajectory and altitude for efficient signal coverage and minimizing energy consumption. Metaheuristic optimization algorithms are recommended to optimize drone placement since these algorithms seek suboptimal solutions for complex optimization problems.

Citizen engagement and crisis response: effective two-way communication with the public is vital. The literature review repeatedly emphasizes the importance of two-way communication with the community to obtain feedback, address concerns, and satisfy needs and encourages feedback from the community and taking their views into account. It is essential to gather feedback from communities and allow them to express their concerns and needs. Integrating citizen feedback mechanisms into the 'Trikala check app' and other the pilot use case in Trikala communication channels is key to improving its effectiveness and building trust. SPARROW's plan to integrate emergency communication into the Trikala Check App aligns with best practices of community engagement and real-time feedback mechanisms.

Use of multiple communication channels (Multichannel Approach): Literature recommends the use of multiple channels (mobile apps, radio, TV, sirens) to ensure wider coverage and redundancy, which is essential during digital system outages.

Trikala plans to use different data networks - Using platforms like social media and ECOMAPP for incident reporting and situation monitoring. Building public trust in digital communication channels is crucial, especially for newer systems like mobile emergency apps. Apps must be easy to use and accessible to all. Creating warning systems that are easy to use, including mobile apps with intuitive design and features.

All emergency communications systems must be efficient and intuitive for public safety personnel and communications professionals to use effectively.

Together with the increasing number of information, rumours and misinformation shall be managed with AI tools that can help monitor public sentiment, counter misinformation, and ensure credibility in crisis communications.

Emergency Trainings & Testing: Literature highlights the importance of regular exercises to validate and improve recovery processes and to prepare teams for different scenarios. Regular exercises to validate and improve the recovery process, train team members, and work with new equipment to

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identify gaps and improve preparedness. These exercises are conducted in a variety of environments and weather conditions to ensure the team is prepared for deployment in any location and time. The pilot use case in Trikala plans to test dynamic solutions for emergency responders. SPARROW's plan to create a dynamic matrix of solutions for first responders (FRs) aligns with best practices recommending regular simulation exercises to optimize response strategies. AI-driven evaluation of crisis response effectiveness can improve future disaster preparedness.

Thus, these recommended practices—ranging from prioritized communication and AI-driven resource optimization to citizen engagement, reliable backup systems, and regular training—can significantly enhance the effectiveness, resilience, and inclusivity of the SPARROW pilot in Trikala.

2.3.4. Summary of Good practices within emergency communication systems.

This chapter provided a mapping of recommended approaches and best practices in crisis communication, which were identified based on several key sources. The main outputs are findings from a literature review focused on crisis management and communication, an overview of case studies using satellite communication tools in emergency situations, and proposed solutions in individual pilot cases of cities involved in the SPARROW project.

Literature review outlined a theoretical framework for understanding the key principles of effective communication in crisis situations, including the need for redundancy, interoperability, and trustworthy information transfer. These principles were then searched in the design of use cases for individual pilot cities, where it has already become evident that certain cities possess their own resources and have taken concrete steps worth highlighting.

Case studies focusing on the use of satellite communications were also particularly useful, serving as examples of good practice in conditions where traditional infrastructure has been compromised. These studies show how satellite technology can ensure continuity of communications when conventional networks fail.

3. Critical Infrastructure (CI): Threats typologies, Vulnerabilities and Good practices

Critical infrastructures form the essential foundations for maintaining public order, national security, public health, and the economic functioning of a territory. Their protection and resilience have become top priorities in a context marked by increasing threats, growing risk complexity, and the heightened interconnection of systems. This chapter aims to provide an overview of identified vulnerabilities, through a review of threat typologies, an analysis of preparedness gaps, and a compilation of best practices in risk management applied to critical infrastructures. A comprehensive compilation of articles that underwent literature review is presented in Appendices 7.1, meticulously categorized based on their thematic themes.

3.1. Threat typologies review - analysis based on literature review

The first step in any resilience strategy for critical infrastructure lies in a clear understanding of the threats that may affect it. This section presents an analysis of threat typologies found in scientific and institutional literature, distinguishing between cyber risks, natural hazards, and systemic risks. Although distinct in nature, these categories converge in their potential impact on essential infrastructures, threatening their continuity of service, safety, and coordination capacity. This review aims to highlight the diversity, evolution, and growing interdependence of threats faced by operators and authorities responsible for the protection of critical infrastructures.

The literature first highlights the growing prominence of cyber threats, which increasingly target both information systems and the control mechanisms that underpin essential services such as energy, telecommunications, and transport. These attacks have the potential to disrupt service continuity, compromise data integrity, and jeopardize physical safety. Their transnational nature and technical complexity amplify their systemic impact and make their origin difficult to trace, posing major challenges for coordinated crisis response. This also remains a significant threat to critical infrastructures. Their frequency and intensity are rising due to climate change, and their impact often extends beyond immediate damage to physical assets. Disruptions in one sector can quickly cascade into others: for example, the flooding of an electrical substation can knock out power to hospitals, telecom systems, or water distribution networks. Historical disaster scenarios illustrate how natural events can initiate complex sequences of infrastructure failure with far-reaching consequences. Another key concern lies in systemic risks. These emerge from the dense interdependencies that characterize modern infrastructure networks, where a localized disruption—whether technical, operational, or intentional—can trigger domino effects across multiple sectors. The intricate connectivity of electricity, transport, health, finance, and communications systems makes them collectively vulnerable to even minor failures. In addition, the emergence of hybrid threats further

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complicates the risk landscape. These threats combine malicious actions, disinformation, and digital attacks, often in politically tense or unstable contexts. In such cases, critical infrastructures may be targeted not only for their strategic utility but also for their symbolic role in maintaining public confidence and social order.

Figure 28 Semantic representation of key themes extracted from the SPARROW corpus (literature review and stakeholder interviews)

In summary, the threat typologies identified in the literature reflect a growing complexity of the risk landscape. Critical infrastructure resilience can no longer rely on sectoral approaches alone. It requires a systemic and forward-looking understanding of vulnerabilities, encompassing technological, human, and territorial dimensions of potential crises. As emphasized by Pescaroli and Kelman, enhancing cross-sector coordination and adaptive mechanisms is essential in a context of increasing uncertainty.

3.1.1. Cyber threats

Cyber threats include all forms of malicious activity directed at digital systems, networks, or data assets. When such threats affect critical infrastructure, their consequences become strategic in nature. Disruptions can compromise essential services such as energy, water, transportation, health, and public safety, creating cascading effects that impact both populations and institutional stability. A wide array of attack methods continues to emerge and evolve. These include ransomware attacks that encrypt data for ransom, spear phishing campaigns targeting individuals to access protected systems, distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks that overload networks, and zero-day exploits that take advantage of unknown vulnerabilities. These techniques exploit a fast-changing technological landscape, shaped by the spread of the Internet of Things (IoT), the use of artificial intelligence, and the increasing integration of information systems with operational technologies.

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Industrial control systems, including supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) platforms, are particularly exposed. Originally designed with limited cybersecurity considerations, these systems now operate essential physical processes such as electricity distribution, water treatment, and traffic regulation. Their compromise can lead to widespread service interruptions and safety risks, especially when fallback procedures and redundancies are lacking.

The growing interconnection between power grids, transportation systems, and communications infrastructure increases vulnerability to coordinated attacks. Technical failures, when left unaddressed, can trigger complex multi-sector disruptions. These events often expose the interaction between technical gaps, organizational weaknesses, and human factors. Cyber threats are also increasingly shaped by geopolitical dynamics. In some contexts, they are used as part of hybrid strategies that combine digital sabotage, disinformation, and political pressure. Such campaigns often aim not only to disrupt infrastructure operations but also to undermine public trust and weaken institutional stability. Despite progress in recognizing these risks, there remains a persistent gap between the pace at which threats evolve and the capacity of institutions to respond. Fragmented governance structures, legal limitations on public-private cooperation, and weak cross-border coordination continue to hinder the development of effective cybersecurity policies. In many cases, institutional responses are slowed by a lack of shared protocols, insufficient training, and underdeveloped mechanisms for anticipating and managing digital risks. Cybersecurity is now a critical component of infrastructure resilience. Addressing these risks requires a comprehensive approach that combines technical protection, mapping of interdependencies, cross-sector collaboration, and ongoing training for all relevant actors. Preparedness must be organizational as well as technological, with a focus on building flexible and adaptive systems capable of absorbing shocks and maintaining continuity of service.

3.1.2. Natural hazards

Natural hazards are a major threat to critical infrastructures due to their ability to directly damage physical assets, disrupt supply chains, isolate territories, and cause cascading failures across governance and crisis management systems. Both scientific and institutional literature agree that the intensification of climatic events—exacerbated by climate change—exposes critical infrastructures to increasingly frequent, intense, and prolonged disruptions. Among the most documented hazards are floods and extreme weather events. According to studies by Public Safety Canada (2024)⁵⁵ and the EHNE (2025)⁵⁶, these phenomena can overwhelm electric grids, damage pumping stations, block transport infrastructure, and disrupt communication networks. The digital dimension is far from secondary: disabling a telecom interconnection hub or flooding a data centre can compromise a territory's entire coordination capacity. Earthquakes and landslides also represent major risks. Their suddenness can cause the collapse of vital infrastructure, such as bridges, tunnels, rail lines, or power stations. The technical literature, including research by Nathalie Fabry and Sylvain Zeghni (2023)⁵⁷,

⁵⁵Sécurité Publique Canada. (2024). Adaptation à l'évolution des menaces. <https://www.securitepublique.gc.ca/>

⁵⁶EHNE. (2025). Infrastructure critique : une géographie des systèmes vulnérables en Europe. <https://ehne.fr/>

⁵⁷Fabry, N., & Zeghni, S. (2023). La résilience des infrastructures urbaines dans la smart city. CREOGN & Université Gustave Eiffel. <https://hal.science/hal-04067046/>

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points to the persistent structural vulnerabilities in certain exposed areas. These physical shocks can also break essential digital links—damaging fiber, corrupting servers, or cutting power—further complicating crisis response efforts. Wildfires are another growing threat, especially in peri-urban zones where infrastructure networks are both dense and vulnerable. Beyond physical destruction (e.g., high-voltage lines, relay stations, transportation routes), wildfires may disrupt emergency response by cutting electricity or interfering with data transmission. Bach, Bouchon, and Fekete (2013)⁵⁸ also highlight indirect impacts—extreme heat, smoke, reduced visibility—that may paralyze digital infrastructures or hinder access to critical assets. Heatwaves and prolonged droughts create systemic stress, particularly on water and energy systems. Reduced cooling capacity for power plants or data centres, combined with increased energy demand, can lead to widespread outages. These extreme episodes also elevate wildfire risk and test the design limits of digital infrastructure, often calibrated for milder conditions.

Finally, storms and snowstorms, though sometimes underestimated, pose a serious risk to service continuity. Collapsed overhead lines, fallen trees, or rail line closures can isolate entire regions. The 2024 EU Strategic Framework⁵⁹ warns about the specific vulnerabilities of mechanical systems to be freezing, the difficulty of accessing infrastructure in winter, and reduced field team performance. These events impact both the physical availability (e.g., power, access) and the digital functions (e.g., telecom, internet) of critical systems. Although these natural hazards have long been identified, their intersection with digital infrastructure now gives them a new dimension. A localised physical failure can quickly escalate into a digital crisis if it disrupts supervision, command, or coordination systems. This interdependence fully justifies the SPARROW project’s approach, which treats digital outage not just consequently but as a potential amplifier of natural crises. Therefore, critical infrastructure resilience requires dual anticipation—both physical and digital.

3.1.3. Systemic risks

Systemic risks differ from other threat categories due to their diffuse, cross-sectoral, and often unpredictable nature. Rather than resulting from a single event, they arise from the growing interdependencies between technical, economic, and social systems, whose complexity often exceeds traditional modelling and forecasting capacities. In the field of critical infrastructure, these risks are particularly concerning due to the tight connectivity between vital networks—electricity, telecom, health, transport, finance—where the failure of one can precipitate a partial or total breakdown of the others.

Literature from both institutional and academic sources, including Fabry and Zeghni (2023)⁶⁰, emphasizes the collective vulnerability created by this hyperconnectivity. A localized outage—for

⁵⁸Bach, C., Bouchon, S., Fekete, A., Birkmann, J., & Serre, D. (2013). Adding value to critical infrastructure research and disaster risk management: The resilience concept. *S.A.P.I.EN.S*, 6(1). <https://journals.openedition.org/sapiens/1626>

⁵⁹Council of the European Union, “Schéma directeur pour la protection des citoyens de l’UE,” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/>.

⁶⁰Fabry, N., & Zeghni, S. (2023). La résilience des infrastructures urbaines dans la smart city. CREOGN & Université Gustave Eiffel. <https://hal.science/hal-04067046/>

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instance, in an electrical infrastructure—can lead to mobile communication blackouts, halted transport systems, temporary shutdowns of hospital services, or disrupted food supply chains. These cascading effects, as seen in the 2006 European blackout or the global logistics disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, demonstrate how sensitive modern systems are to systemic shocks.

Three main drivers contribute to the emergence of these risks:

- *The increasing complexity of digital systems*, including mass integration of connected technologies (IoT), smart automation, and cloud infrastructure. These elements create shared points of failure: a single software flaw or misconfiguration can impact several sectors at once.
- *The globalization of production and distribution chains*, making logistical systems highly sensitive to disruptions. Local incidents can have global consequences, as shown by prolonged supply chain interruptions for electronic components and medical devices during the pandemic.
- *The hyper concentration of critical capabilities*—data centres, energy hubs, transport nodes, storage platforms—magnifying the impact of local failures due to a lack of redundancy or robust contingency planning.

These risks are particularly hard to anticipate, as they often remain invisible during normal operations. Their emergence reveals unmanaged dependencies, coordination breakdowns, or blind spots in strategic planning. Further note that these vulnerabilities are sometimes intensified in dense urban and peri-urban areas, where networks are physically and functionally intertwined. In this context, Arnaud Barichella (2022)⁶¹ highlights new challenges posed by digital infrastructure concentration and rapid technological transformation. His work stresses that growing reliance on platforms and critical information systems introduces new fragilities often underestimated by traditional security models. Within the SPARROW project framework, systemic risks hold relevance. On one hand, digital outages can act as amplifiers of crisis by disrupting management, communication, or coordination systems. On the other hand, digital tools—when properly designed and anticipated—offer powerful levers to map interdependencies, simulate crisis scenarios, and activate integrated responses. Addressing systemic risks thus requires a shift in scale: it is no longer enough to secure each infrastructure in isolation. Instead, we must foster a culture of systemic resilience, capable of absorbing complex shocks and limiting domino effects.

⁶¹Barichella, A. (2022). La numérisation des infrastructures critiques : risques systémiques. Institut Delors. <https://institutdelors.eu/>

Figure 29 Network graph of risk categories and associated concepts affecting Critical Infrastructure

3.2. Identified gaps and vulnerabilities in CI preparedness

Identifying vulnerabilities is a crucial step in building a robust resilience strategy for critical infrastructures. While threats are now better characterized in public policies, European directives, and specialized literature, the actual preparedness of operators and territories remains marked by significant disparities, persistent blind spots, and structural weaknesses in continuity management.

The literature review highlights several types of systemic gaps. First, many publications point to fragmented governance in crisis management. Responsibilities are often dispersed across various institutional levels (state, local authorities, private operators) without a harmonized framework for coordination during degraded conditions. The European Commission’s report on infrastructure resilience (2024)⁶² emphasizes the need for an integrated approach, which remains insufficiently applied at the territorial level. Second, there is a general lack of awareness or underestimation of interdependencies between networks. Whether in energy, logistics, healthcare, or telecommunications, critical infrastructures no longer operate in silos. However, few systems consider cascading failures, as illustrated by the power outages analysed in IRSEM (2018)⁶³ and Public Safety Canada (2024)⁶⁴. This results in difficulty anticipating systemic scenarios and

⁶²Council of the European Union. (2024). Schéma directeur pour la protection des citoyens de l’UE. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/>

⁶³IRSEM. (2018). Cybermenaces sur les réseaux électriques européens. <https://www.irsem.fr/>

⁶⁴Sécurité Publique Canada. (2024). Adaptation à l’évolution des menaces. <https://www.securitepublique.gc.ca/>

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implementing genuinely cross-cutting contingency plans. A third area of vulnerability lies in the insufficient integration of digital risks into preparedness policies. As the digitalization of infrastructures accelerates, security audits often remain confined to IT, without addressing operational systems (OT) or critical interfaces between subsystems. Several documents, including the 2024 EU strategic framework, note that degraded-mode procedures are poorly formalized or not well understood by field operators. This leaves organizations heavily dependent on automated systems, whose failure could paralyze entire command chains. Local operational capacity also appears as a recurring weakness. Numerous field reports highlight a lack of specific training in digital resilience, high turnover in sensitive roles, and a lack of regular crisis simulation exercises. Smaller municipalities in particular struggle to mobilize the human, technical, and financial resources needed for proactive preparedness.

Finally, the complexity and multiplicity of crisis management tools create additional barriers. According to the literature, this complexity hinders the appropriation of systems, especially in degraded conditions. Poor ergonomics, weak interoperability, and unclear decision-making chains are all obstacles to effective and coordinated crisis response. These shared findings show that beyond the technical components of critical infrastructures, it is the organizational, leadership, and training conditions that ultimately shape their true resilience. The need for cross-functional capacity building, simplified processes, and clarified responsibilities is widely recognized but unevenly implemented across territories. This vulnerability review therefore aims to provide a structured diagnosis of the gap between declared resilience strategies and operational realities. It serves as a common understanding from which targeted recommendations will be developed, tailored to the challenges of the SPARROW project and applicable both locally and nationally.

3.2.1. Analysis based on the literature review

The review of scientific and institutional literature highlights several persistent shortcomings in the preparedness of critical infrastructure against identified threats. These vulnerabilities span organizational, technological, and structural aspects of resilience frameworks.

The first weakness concerns the fragmentation of responsibilities. The governance of critical infrastructures is often shared among multiple public and private actors operating at different institutional levels. This fragmentation hinders crisis coordination, complicates decision-making processes, and causes inconsistencies in response capacity across regions or sectors. This finding, documented in the EU Council's Strategic Framework for Critical Infrastructure Protection (2024)⁶⁵ and the Public Safety Canada report (2024)⁶⁶, underscores the absence of a shared culture of crisis management and resilience. A second vulnerability is the growing reliance on non-resilient digital systems. While digitalization has improved operational efficiency, it often lacks systematic risk assessments. Few organizations have rigorous cybersecurity auditing policies, system redundancies, or regular continuity testing. This concern is compounded by the increasing dependence on

⁶⁵Council of the European Union. (2024). Schéma directeur pour la protection des citoyens de l'UE. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/>.

⁶⁶Sécurité Publique Canada. (2024). Adaptation à l'évolution des menaces. <https://www.securitepublique.gc.ca/>

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technologies such as SCADA systems, IoT, or cloud infrastructures, which are essential for day-to-day CI management yet remain vulnerable to cyberattacks or systemic failures, as noted by Abdelgawad (2023)⁶⁷ and Dierich et al. (2019)⁶⁸.

The literature also points to the absence of integrated multi-risk scenarios in planning frameworks. Too often, continuity or crisis plans are based on sectoral logics or isolated risk typologies (cyber, climate, technical). This siloed thinking prevents the anticipation of cascading effects, as highlighted in the work of Pescaroli and Alexander (2016)⁶⁹, who advocate for a systems-based approach to interdependencies and crisis propagation. Another critical issue involves the weak risk culture in strategic sectors such as logistics, finance, or transportation. Sensitivity to digital or systemic risks remains insufficient at the strategic level, and resilience-related investments are often a low priority. Arnaud Barichella (2022)⁷⁰ underscores structural gaps in the incorporation of digital security issues into European CI governance.

Across the board, the literature converges on the need to integrate digital risks as a transversal factor in preparedness policies, rather than a siloed threat. It emphasizes the importance of stronger coordination mechanisms between operators, local governments, and central authorities capable of mapping critical interdependencies and designing system-wide, rather than asset-specific, responses. This literature-based analysis provides a solid foundation for diagnosing vulnerabilities in critical infrastructure. It sheds light on the current gaps to be addressed and, more importantly, on the levers to activate in order to build truly systemic resilience—at the intersection of physical, organizational, and digital dimensions.

3.2.2. Gaps and vulnerabilities identified within the stakeholders' interviews.

The interviews conducted with various stakeholders—including infrastructure operators, local authorities, network managers, and public emergency services—provided an opportunity to compare literature-based findings with operational realities. While several theoretical vulnerabilities were confirmed by those interviewed, the discussions also brought to light specific gaps related to day-to-day practices, anticipation capacity, and organizational maturity regarding digital risks. A key issue raised was the lack of awareness around digital interdependencies, as shown in Figure 30 where frequency across interviews indicates how many stakeholders raised each issue. Many professionals acknowledged difficulty in mapping their critical digital dependencies:

⁶⁷Abdelgawad, A. A. (2023). An updated system dynamics model for analysing the cascading effects of critical infrastructure failures. In J. Radianti, I. Dokas, N. Lalone, & D. Khazanchi (Eds.). <http://dx.doi.org/10.59297/XMVD9392>

⁶⁸Dierich, A., Tzavella, K., Setiadi, N. J., Fekete, A., & Neisser, F. (2019). Enhanced crisis-preparation of critical infrastructures through a participatory qualitative-quantitative interdependency analysis approach. In Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Information Systems for Crisis Response and Management (ISCRAM). Valencia, Spain.

⁶⁹Pescaroli, G., & Alexander, D. (2016). Critical infrastructure, panarchies and the vulnerability paths of cascading disasters. *Natural Hazards*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-016-2186-3>

⁷⁰Barichella, A. (2022). La numérisation des infrastructures critiques : risques systémiques. Institut Delors. <https://institutdelors.eu/>

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outsourced servers, cloud-based software, process automation, remote maintenance, and invisible interconnections between operators. This opacity—reported in Cannes, Leuven, and Pilsen—makes it difficult to anticipate cascading effects from an outage or cyberattack. In Cannes, for instance, a network loss caused by a UPS failure disrupted multiple critical services. In Leuven, the crisis manager highlighted poorly identified dependencies on hosting providers and cloud systems. As noted by EENA, this lack of visibility on critical assets is a major vulnerability in several European countries. Another key finding concerns the lack of training and capacity building dedicated to digital outage scenarios. While most organizations are relatively prepared for climatic or energy-related crises, very few have tested scenarios focused on digital infrastructure failures such as network breakdowns, IT system lockouts, or mobile communication blackouts. In Leuven, the crisis manager pointed to the absence of simulation tools for cyber incidents, despite a clear operational need. This lack of preparedness limits the ability to adapt in real time—particularly when the tools themselves (e.g. GIS software, alert platforms, messaging systems) become unavailable.

The interviews also revealed a significant gap between national regulatory frameworks and local implementation. Although regulations like the NIS2 directive or the DORA regulation exist, their practical application remains inconsistent. Field actors cited insufficient support, burdensome regulatory requirements, and partial awareness of obligations. EENA emphasized the disparity in continuity cultures across Europe, with countries like Finland and Sweden leading in redundancy and preparedness, while others still struggle to integrate such concepts into their strategies. Another recurring issue is the lack of qualified human resources, particularly in cybersecurity related to critical infrastructure. This issue exists in mid-sized municipalities and local technical departments. In Cannes, digital upskilling considered as a strategic priority yet remains constrained by available resources. In Leuven, the need for targeted training in digital crisis scenarios was explicitly mentioned. In some cases, cybersecurity responsibilities are outsourced with no structured internal governance, limiting strategic oversight.

Additional vulnerabilities reported by interviewees include:

- A lack of interoperability between technical systems, especially during power outages (e.g., video surveillance system shutdowns in Cannes, with fallback to human monitoring).
- Poor anticipation of cascading effects, such as simultaneous loss of connectivity, surveillance, signalling, and alert systems (noted in both Pilsen and Cannes).
- Regulatory constraints, such as GDPR, perceived as obstacles to inter-institutional cooperation during crises (EENA).
- Persistent energy vulnerabilities, despite the installation of generators, due to limited or uneven autonomy across critical facilities (Cannes and EENA feedback).
- These field observations support the need for targeted, gradual, and pragmatic support to strengthen digital preparedness among operational actors. Key action areas include:
 - Building competencies (training and awareness for digital crisis management).
 - Sharing alert and crisis management tools tailored to local contexts.

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- Formalizing backup procedures for degraded-mode operations, including alternative communication systems.
- Systematizing feedback and lessons learned from past digital failures.

Figure 30 Key Gaps and Vulnerabilities in Critical Infrastructure Preparedness Identified by Stakeholders

Ultimately, the interviews confirm that digital resilience is not merely a technical issue. It relies on the collective capacity to understand, anticipate, and manage disruption, while fully embracing the complexity of interdependencies between physical, digital, and human systems.

3.2.3. Summary of CI gaps and vulnerabilities

The cross-analysis of findings from the literature review and stakeholder interviews makes it possible to outline a structured typology of vulnerabilities currently affecting critical infrastructure preparedness. These vulnerabilities can be grouped into three complementary dimensions: organizational, technological, and human.

From an organizational perspective, the main weakness lies in fragmented governance, marked by the coexistence of multiple public and private actors with sometimes unclear responsibilities. This dispersion leads to weak intersectoral coordination, undermines the coherence of prevention strategies and emergency plans, and hampers integrated crisis response under degraded conditions.

From a technological standpoint, critical infrastructures are increasingly dependent on digital systems that lack resilience. Redundancy mechanisms, digital contingency plans, and supervision tools are often missing, under-dimensioned, or ill-suited to complex crisis scenarios. This fragility is especially concerning since digital functions now underpin real-time supervision, command, and alert capabilities.

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On the human and cultural level, a persistent underestimation of digital and systemic risks delays the development of a true resilience culture. The lack of specialized training, the scarcity of exercises focused on digital outages, and the difficulty in mobilizing teams during technological crises all weaken organizational responsiveness to large-scale disruptive events.

These vulnerabilities are not isolated; they reflect a structural coherence of weaknesses as explained in the Figure 31. Fragmented governance encourages disparate practices, which in turn hinder technical anticipation and slow skill development among teams. Therefore, building a coherent digital preparedness strategy requires simultaneous action on all three fronts: clarifying governance, strengthening tools, and fostering human resilience.

Within the SPARROW project, this cross-cutting diagnostic forms a solid foundation for identifying effective levers for action. It highlights the need to design systems that are both technically robust and organizationally agile—fully integrating digital risks into the broader continuity architecture for essential services. This analytical base will serve to guide the next section, which focuses on best practices in resilience for critical infrastructure.

Figure 31 Network of Underlying Factors Contributing to Gaps in Critical Infrastructure Preparedness

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3.3. Good Practices in CI Preparedness

Ensuring the resilience of critical infrastructures (CI) in the face of increasingly complex and hybrid threats requires a structured understanding of what constitutes effective preparedness. This section presents a synthesis of best practices in CI preparedness, drawn from two complementary sources: a review of scientific and institutional literature, and operational insights gathered from stakeholder interviews conducted within the SPARROW project. Together, these sources offer a rich and diverse overview of tested strategies, innovative measures, and replicable models that enhance digital resilience. The following sub-sections aim to highlight both theoretical foundations and practical field experiences, serving as a reference for shaping context-specific resilience strategies.

3.3.1. Literature review outcomes

The scientific and institutional literature highlights a coherent set of best practices aimed at strengthening the resilience of critical infrastructures in the face of growing and diverse threats. These practices, developed across various countries and sectors, encompass technical engineering, governance, cybersecurity, and integrated risk management. Their common value lies in their ability to transcend fragmented approaches by proposing systemic and adaptable solutions. One of the most frequently cited approaches is the "all-hazards" methodology. Inspired by North American models and gradually adopted in European frameworks, this method aims to design continuity plans that account for a full range of hazards—natural disasters, cyberattacks, technical failures, social unrest, etc. Public Safety Canada (2024)⁷¹ highlights how this approach helps avoid siloed responses and anticipates cascading effects by structuring crisis plans around critical functions rather than rigid scenarios. The establishment of redundancy and recovery capabilities is another key best practice, emphasized in many documents, including the EU Council's Strategic Framework for Critical Infrastructure Protection (2024)⁷². This involves duplicating critical resources (power supply, data centres, communication channels), as well as maintaining manual fallback procedures when digital systems fail. According to Dierich et al. (2019)⁷³, the ability to switch quickly to alternative configurations is a strong indicator of organizational maturity in resilience.

Another crucial element is the development of public-private cooperation models. Several publications, including those by Bach, Bouchon, and Fekete (2013)⁷⁴, stress the vital role of partnerships between infrastructure operators, local authorities, state agencies, and tech companies. These alliances facilitate expertise sharing, secure information exchange, and more coherent responses to cross-sector threats. Multi-actor anticipation cells and intersectoral exchange platforms are regularly cited as particularly effective setups. Early warning and detection systems also represent a highly recommended best practice. These rely on a combination of active cyber

⁷¹Sécurité Publique Canada. (2024). Adaptation à l'évolution des menaces. <https://www.securitepublique.gc.ca/>

⁷²Council of the European Union. (2024). Schéma directeur pour la protection des citoyens de l'UE. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/>

⁷³Dierich, A., Tzavella, K., Setiadi, N. J., Fekete, A., & Neisser, F. (2019). Enhanced crisis-preparation of critical infrastructures through a participatory qualitative-quantitative interdependency analysis approach. In Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Information Systems for Crisis Response and Management (ISCRAM). Valencia, Spain.

⁷⁴Bach, C., Bouchon, S., Fekete, A., Birkmann, J., & Serre, D. (2013). Adding value to critical infrastructure research and disaster risk management: The resilience concept. *S.A.P.I.E.N.S.*, 6(1). <https://journals.openedition.org/sapiens/1626>

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surveillance, environmental sensors, artificial intelligence, and predictive modelling. In this regard, Pescaroli and Kelman (2017)⁷⁵ emphasize the need to link these technologies to clear decision-making processes and a rapid-response culture. The integration of technological monitoring with anticipatory governance is seen as essential for responding to early signals. Lastly, the valorisation of feedback (REX) is frequently identified as a condition for continuous improvement in resilience systems. The structured analysis of past crises—whether cyber incidents, power outages, or intersectoral breakdowns—helps identify flaws, consolidate good practices, and reinforce organizational memory. Abdelgawad (2023)⁷⁶ underlines the benefit of dynamic modelling to evaluate the impact of decisions taken during complex crises and improve future preparedness.

Within the SPARROW project, these lessons converge toward a shared imperative: the need for an integrated model combining robust digital tools and a resilient organizational culture. To address outages and crises affecting critical infrastructures, resilience must be seen not just as a technical issue, but as the intelligent combination of physical redundancy, organizational flexibility, and collective intelligence. These best practices provide a reference base for drafting context-specific recommendations, to be developed in the next sections of this report.

3.3.2. Best practices identified within the stakeholders' interviews.

Interviews conducted within the SPARROW project with a diverse range of operational stakeholders, including municipalities, traffic and IT departments, civil protection services, and European organisations, revealed a common foundation of good practices in managing digital risks. These practices as per highlighted in Figure 32, whether technical, organisational, or procedural, reflect a growing maturity and awareness among local actors. They also illustrate the capacity for innovation at the territorial level, even in contexts with limited resources.

In Cannes, several concrete actions have been implemented to ensure continuity of essential services: energy redundancy with fixed and mobile generators, alternative protocols in case of network failure, and the integration of analogue radios, satellite phones, and ADRASEC systems into crisis response plans. In Leuven, although simulation tools are still lacking, the city has developed a structured continuity plan that includes digital aspects and conducts regular backup exercises. In Pilsen, while responses are mostly human driven, the use of a digital twin for traffic management opens new possibilities. Meanwhile, EENA emphasizes several practical levers: hosting emergency call centres in physically protected sites, sharing surveillance among critical actors, and integrating cyber profiles into crisis teams. Overall, these field insights show that digital resilience depends as much on technological anticipation as on local organization, cooperation, and adaptive capacity.

The interviews also highlighted additional concrete and promising initiatives already deployed at various scales. One of the most significant is the integration of digital outage scenarios into internal crisis management protocols. In Cannes, alternative procedures have been developed to address

⁷⁵Pescaroli, G., & Kelman, I. (2017). How critical infrastructure orients international relief in cascading disasters. *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*, 25(2), 56–67. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-5973.12118>

⁷⁶Abdelgawad, A. A. (2023). An updated system dynamics model for analysing the cascading effects of critical infrastructure failures. In J. Radianti, I. Dokas, N. Lalone, & D. Khazanchi (Eds.). <http://dx.doi.org/10.59297/XMVD9392>

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Internet or power outages, including resilient communication methods like VHF radios, satellite phones, and analogue frequencies (Ville de Cannes, 2025 interview). At the European level, EENA also reports the use of pen-and-paper decision trees and protected underground infrastructures, such as 112 centres in Finland, demonstrating a pragmatic approach to digital continuity (EENA, 2025 interview). Another identified best practice is the use of crisis simulation tools, especially for complex digital scenarios like cyberattacks, blackouts, or connectivity loss. In Leuven, the crisis manager notes the lack of such tools despite a strong need (City of Leuven, 2025 interview). In contrast, other stakeholders, particularly in traffic management, already use digital twins to simulate traffic disruptions and test system resilience (Traffic Management, 2025 interview). These simulators offer both training value and a way to validate degraded coordination mechanisms.

In several regions, interviews revealed the existence of collaborative monitoring mechanisms among critical actors, both institutional and informal. In Cannes, ongoing coordination between the city, municipal police, and technical services helps cross-check weak signals and prepare coordinated responses (City of Cannes, 2025 interview). At the European level, EENA emphasizes the need for shared surveillance among operators, emergency call centres, and local authorities to collectively anticipate systemic effects from digital or energy disruptions (EENA, 2025 interview). Another key takeaway is the appointment of digital or cybersecurity focal points within crisis units. In Cannes, IT department staff monitor critical infrastructure status, such as data centres, networks, and UPS—and support crisis teams during incidents (City of Cannes, 2025 interview). EENA confirms this trend across Europe, with the rise of cyber profiles in operational cells, particularly in countries affected by major attacks (e.g., Spain, Belgium, Germany) (EENA, 2025 interview).

Lastly, several municipalities have chosen to invest in technical redundancy infrastructure, such as generators, source inverters, or satellite terminals. In Cannes, these assets are now installed in critical buildings—Palais des Festivals, crematorium, administrative centres—to ensure minimum autonomy in the event of a network failure (City of Cannes, 2025 interview). In Sweden and Denmark, as EENA notes, some emergency centres are hosted on physically separated sites interconnected through multiple operators to maximize service continuity (EENA, 2025 interview).

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Figure 32 Best Practices for Digital Resilience in Critical Infrastructure – Insights from Stakeholder Interviews

These initiatives show that it is possible to deploy operational digital resilience, even with limited resources, provided that approaches are tailored to local contexts, existing capacities are leveraged, and a collective learning mindset is encouraged. They also highlight the importance of human ownership of tools and methods, as well as intersectoral cooperation, in managing critical situations where technology alone is not sufficient.

As part of the SPARROW project, these real-world insights offer concrete foundations for formulating actionable recommendations based on replicable and context-sensitive practices.

3.3.3. Summary of CI preparedness best practices

The cross-analysis of literature findings and field interviews highlights a coherent set of best practices structured around three key action principles. Although distinct, these principles interconnect to form the foundation of an integrated approach to critical infrastructure resilience in the face of digital outages and systemic threats.

The first principle is to anticipate complex threats, especially by integrating digital scenarios into preparedness strategies. This implies moving beyond sector-specific risks and planning for multi-hazard scenarios that combine physical, technological, and cyber elements. This need was echoed in several stakeholder interviews—for example, in Leuven, where the crisis manager reported the current lack of cyber incident simulation tools despite strong demand (City of Leuven, 2025 interview), and in Pilsen, where responses to signalling outages still rely heavily on manual procedures due to a lack of digital protocols (City of Pilsen, 2025 interview). Developing early signal detection capabilities, supported by regular exercises and structured feedback loops, improves responsiveness and enables adaptation to evolving threats, as noted in exchanges with EENA (EENA, 2025 interview).

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The second principle is to proactively organize digital resilience. This includes deploying redundant systems, establishing contingency procedures for IT failures, and designating cyber focal points within crisis management frameworks. In Cannes, this approach has led to the installation of generators and satellite terminals in critical buildings (City of Cannes, 2025 interview), as well as the inclusion of IT personnel in crisis units. EENA confirms that integrating cyber profiles into operational teams is a major resilience factor, especially in countries that have experienced large-scale attacks (EENA, 2025 interview). This organization requires not only technical anticipation, but also human readiness to maintain decision-making capacity even without usual digital tools.

The third principle is to strengthen territorial cooperation as a prerequisite for coordinated response. Information sharing among public, private, and institutional stakeholders; mutualization of tools (monitoring, alert systems, training); and the progressive development of a shared intersectoral crisis culture are all key success factors. In Cannes, coordination between the city, municipal police, and technical departments has led to practical backup solutions in the event of power outages (City of Cannes, 2025 interview). EENA emphasizes the value of interconnected platforms among call centres, municipalities, and operators to ensure fluid information flows during crises (EENA, 2025 interview). These collective dynamics help overcome traditional silos and build distributed resilience based on network intelligence.

Table 3 Summary of Interview’s insights

City/Org	Critical Events	Critical Services	Emerging Tech	Cascading Effects	Lessons Learned
Cannes	Power outage, telecom loss, UPS failure	Admin, registry, finance, HR, police, crematorium	Starlink, SaaS, cloud, resilience kits	Surveillance loss, crematorium halt, antenna damage	Fixed generators, radio redundancy, communication upgrades
EENA	Cyberattacks, natural disasters	112 call centers, public alert systems	AI, private 5G, edge, blockchain, Galileo	Failures in healthcare, energy, comms	Interoperability, low-tech backups, legal barriers
Leuven	None reported	IT, hospitals, childcare, nursing homes, public order	None (need for simulation tools)	Considered during planning (power failures)	Need simulation tools, proactive planning
Pilsen Municipal Police	Power outages	Traffic lights, surveillance	Digital twin (limited use)	None formalised	Manual backup, limited interdepartmental coordination

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Pilsen – Traffic	Power/digital failures	Traffic signals, acoustic sensors	Smart sensors	Surveillance loss during outage	Safe design, generator backups, control room security
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Within the SPARROW project, these best practices represent concrete levers to strengthen the robustness of critical infrastructures against digital disruptions and systemic crises. Their widespread implementation, however, requires a strategic shift: from a reactive and siloed logic to a territorial, interconnected, and proactive resilience model that fully integrates the digital dimension as a structuring element of modern crisis management.

4. Cross-cutting themes

Beyond the specific analyses of emergency communication systems and critical infrastructure vulnerabilities, this section identifies and synthesises overarching themes and interdependencies that emerged consistently across all stakeholder interviews and literature reviews. These "cross-cutting elements" represent fundamental challenges and opportunities that transcend individual sectors or communication channels, highlighting the systemic nature of resilience in the face of digital breakdowns. Understanding these interconnected factors is crucial for developing a holistic and effective SPARROW architecture that can address the complex interplay between different critical domains and ensure robust crisis response.

4.1. Existing policies and regulations regarding satellite-based communication

For resilient networks in times of disaster, general telecommunication regulatory frameworks and disaster specific policies and regulations are equally critical. Public authorities are obliged to be the designers and implementers of last resort connectivity solutions required during disaster management. In worst case scenarios, setting principles and imposing obligations on private sector players may not be enough. Picard and Pickard⁷⁷ state that in disaster communications, communication policies have two priorities: *enabling the public to communicate with authorities and enhancing communication among authorities themselves.*

There could also be an additional goal of keeping/ recovering user-to-user communication to enable affected communities to stay connected with each other or with the outside world. However, this would be the case only after necessary resources are allocated to the first two priorities dependent on the conditions after the specific disaster. Saving lives becomes the priority when managing disaster recovery, and unfortunately, existing conventional regulatory frameworks are often a burden to this objective due to their inadequacy for the specific conditions of a disaster. Decision-makers need to be pragmatic with regulatory silos and priorities. Competition, consumer rights, or privacy frameworks create additional challenges for next generation connectivity and disaster response solution. Authorization frameworks with long assessment and public comment periods that are developed to ensure competitive and transparent environments are ideal in non-emergency times but slow to respond to urgent needs in emergencies. As such, having a well-understood and flexible system of issuing waivers or recognizing exceptions in the operation of emergency telecommunications is necessary in emergencies, such as to enable additional connectivity until service providers recover their networks or when location information in a device could mean saving

⁷⁷https://robertpicard.net/assets/docs/Picard_Pickard_Principles_of_Media_Policy.18531920.pdf

Picard, R. G., & Pickard, V. (2017, April). Essential principles for contemporary media and communications policymaking. Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism.

https://robertpicard.net/assets/docs/Picard_Pickard_Principles_of_Media_Policy.18531920.pdf

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a life. It is advisable to establish a system that ensures that government decisionmakers' authority to quickly issue temporary waivers and exceptions in expressly and clearly set forth in a country's law or regulations, it is clear how and to whom to request waivers and exceptions when normal government operations are compromised, and does not require waiting periods, multiple layers of review, or the submission of documents that would be impossible to provide in the middle of disasters. The preparedness element in disaster management is not solely dependent on strengthening state control and regulations. Enabling means to keep the telecommunications industry resilient is equally important. In times of disaster, public authorities, particularly regulators, are required to take immediate actions, including:

- Orchestrating public and private stakeholders, primarily operators, to readily adapt disaster-ready protocols.
- Ensuring redundant networks.
- Encouraging operators to pursue cooperation, for example, for providing technical support to each other, national roaming when necessary, or satellite operator-mobile operator interconnection.

For instance, in Australia, the Strengthening Telecommunications Against Natural Disaster Package developed after the 2019/2020⁷⁸ bushfires aim to increase and improve resilience of affected communities. The package includes connectivity solutions such as satellite supported cells on wheels.

Finally, it is important that telecommunications regulators, emergency response authorities, and customs/border authorities coordinate on emergency response procedures long before emergencies occur. This coordination is important because in past emergencies, a lack of coordination has left critical emergency response personnel or equipment unable to enter the effected country or blocked by local emergency response authorises when attempting to deploy within a country to the most affected areas. This coordination should include a declaration that emergency telecommunications is a critical element in response activities, so it is afforded priority treatment.

4.2. Ethical and legal considerations

Emergency communication systems and critical infrastructure resilience planning raise essential ethical questions that must be addressed proactively. These considerations are not merely procedural but foundational to ensuring public trust, equitable service provision, and the responsible deployment of technologies in crisis contexts.

- *Privacy and data protection:* Emergency communication systems may collect sensitive data, including geolocation, personal health, or behavioural patterns. Systems must be designed to prioritize data minimization, anonymization, and user consent, wherever feasible.

⁷⁸https://www.infrastructure.gov.au/sites/default/files/strengthening-telecommunications-against-natural-disasters_1.pdf Department of Infrastructure, Transport, Regional Development and Communications (Australia). (n.d). Strengthening Telecommunications Against Natural Disasters: Market research report.

https://www.infrastructure.gov.au/sites/default/files/strengthening-telecommunications-against-natural-disasters_1.pdf.

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- *Equity and inclusion:* Ethical emergency preparedness requires deliberate attention to at-risk and marginalized populations. Response frameworks must ensure that no community is excluded due to language, disability, geographic isolation, or socioeconomic status.
- *Transparency and accountability:* Algorithms, alerts, and decisions made during emergencies must be transparent. Where AI or automation is used, mechanisms must exist for human oversight and explanation.
- *Dignity and autonomy:* Communication during crises must respect the dignity and autonomy of individuals—avoiding coercive messaging or panic-inducing alerts and supporting informed choice even under duress.
- *Ethical governance:* should be embedded in the design, implementation, and review of emergency technologies, drawing on public consultation and multidisciplinary oversight bodies. Emergency communications and critical infrastructure preparedness operate within a complex web of legal requirements and regulatory standards that vary across jurisdictions. Ensuring lawful operation is a prerequisite for effective and legitimate response.
- *Data protection regulations:* Frameworks such as the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)⁷⁹ establish conditions for lawful data processing, which are to be referred to when handling citizen data during emergency alerts or surveillance.
- *Telecommunications law:* Use of public and private networks for emergency broadcasting, including spectrum allocation and priority access, must comply with national and EU-level telecom regulations.
- *Cybersecurity and critical infrastructure protection:* Legislation like the NIS2 Directive⁸⁰ and national critical infrastructure protection acts define responsibilities for safeguarding digital systems against disruption, including protocols for incident reporting and information sharing.
- *Cross-border legal coordination:* As crises often span borders, harmonizing legal frameworks (e.g., mutual assistance treaties, interoperability standards) is crucial for efficient international response.

Resilient systems must be designed with built-in compliance features, legal risk assessments, and operational readiness to adapt to evolving legislation.

⁷⁹<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02016R0679-20160504>
European Parliament & Council. (2016, April 27). Regulation (EU) 2016/679 ... (General Data Protection Regulation) [Consolidated text]. EUR-Lex. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02016R0679-20160504>.

⁸⁰<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022L2555&qid=1755848651433>
European Parliament & Council. (2022, December 14). Directive (EU) 2022/2555 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union (NIS 2 Directive). EUR-Lex. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022L2555>.

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4.3. Societal impact and community engagement

Emergency preparedness and critical infrastructure resilience must be understood not only through the lens of technology and policy, but as deeply embedded in the social fabric. Communication systems deployed during crises directly affect how people perceive risk, respond to instructions, and maintain trust in institutions. A resilient society is not simply one that owns robust technology, but one that has cultivated informed, connected, and empowered communities.

One of the foremost challenges in societal engagement is the disparity in awareness and preparedness across demographic and geographic lines. Studies have shown that populations with lower digital literacy, limited access to information infrastructure, or social marginalization are less likely to respond effectively to emergency alerts. For instance, during the 2018 wildfires in Greece, several communities failed to evacuate in time partly due to inconsistent communication channels and limited understanding of evacuation protocols. Community trust plays a critical role in shaping responses to official guidance. Research in disaster sociology highlights that people are more likely to act on alerts and guidance from sources they perceive as credible and familiar. This makes local engagement — involving municipal authorities, neighbourhood leaders, and community-based organizations — essential in crafting and disseminating emergency communications.

Participatory design in emergency planning further enhances both usability and legitimacy. When community members are involved in co-developing alert systems or evacuation maps, the resulting tools tend to be more practical and better tailored to local needs. For example, the "Map Kibera" initiative in Nairobi involved slum residents in mapping informal settlements to improve crisis response capabilities, demonstrating how localized knowledge can fill critical information gaps⁸¹.

Another key factor is cultural and linguistic accessibility. In multilingual or multicultural regions, the availability of alerts and preparedness materials in multiple languages can determine whether entire populations are reached effectively. Accessibility also involves ensuring that persons with disabilities can receive and respond to alerts — whether through vibration-enabled devices, visual alerts, or caregiver networks. Inclusive design is not only ethically necessary but functionally vital. Finally, ongoing engagement must extend beyond the crisis moment. Public preparedness campaigns, school-based education programs, and community-led simulations have been shown to significantly enhance long-term resilience. The 2020 OECD report on "Enhancing the Resilience of Critical Infrastructure" recommends embedding community feedback mechanisms and social participation indicators into national risk management frameworks.

Societal resilience is, therefore, not a passive outcome but an active, collective process. It emerges when people are treated not merely as recipients of alerts, but as partners in preparedness. Building such partnerships requires investment in communication, trust-building, and participatory governance — pillars as critical as any technical standard or legal framework.

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5. Strategic recommendations

The increasing digitalisation of critical infrastructures and emergency communication systems offers both immense opportunities and growing risks. As the SPARROW project has shown, digital dependencies are reshaping the resilience landscape in complex ways, exposing new forms of vulnerability while also enabling more sophisticated crisis response capabilities. To operationalise resilience in this evolving context, institutional actors across the public, private, and research domains must engage in coordinated, yet differentiated actions. Resilience cannot be achieved by technological means alone—it must be supported by coherent governance frameworks, inclusive practices, and ethical safeguards.

This section presents a set of strategic recommendations developed based on a multi-level analysis involving literature review, field interviews, and stakeholder consultations. The recommendations are structured around four key stakeholder groups: policymakers and regulators, civil protection authorities and first responders, infrastructure operators and private sector actors, and research and innovation bodies. Each group has a distinct role to play in building a European resilience architecture that is robust, inclusive, and future-oriented.

5.1. For policymakers and regulators

Policymakers hold the responsibility of creating the structural conditions under which resilience becomes both legally mandated and operationally feasible.

One of the most urgent challenges is the fragmentation of legal and institutional frameworks across Member States, which hinders coordinated response efforts, especially in cross-border crises. Alignment with EU directives such as the NIS2 Directive, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and the European Electronic Communications Code⁸² is not only a matter of legal compliance but a necessary step toward interoperability and mutual assistance.

At the same time, regulators must ensure that emergency systems speak a common technical language. The adoption of open, standardised communication protocols—such as 3GPP's Mission-Critical Services, ETSI EMTEL specifications, and the Common Alerting Protocol (CAP)—should be mandated across jurisdictions. Without these standards, systems risk becoming siloed, and responders may be unable to exchange information during critical moments. Resilience also requires sustained investment. Funding schemes should prioritise "resilience by design," supporting the development of redundant infrastructure, decentralised systems, and inclusive preparedness measures. These schemes must explicitly account for vulnerable populations, including those in remote areas, with disabilities, or lacking digital access.

⁸²Publications Office of the European Union. (n.d.). European Electronic Communications Code [Summary]. Retrieved September 4, 2025, from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/summary/european-electronic-communications-code.html>

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Finally, regulatory agencies must be equipped not only to legislate but to monitor and enforce compliance. They should be empowered to evaluate the ethical, cybersecurity, and functional reliability of crisis communication tools and infrastructure. Certification systems, periodic audits, and performance evaluations during stress simulations can serve as key mechanisms to ensure readiness and accountability.

Table 4 Summary of recommendations for policymakers and regulators

Objective	Recommended actions
Ensure regulatory coherence	- Align national laws with EU frameworks (e.g., NIS2, GDPR, EECC) - Minimise cross-border regulatory fragmentation
Mandate interoperability	- Enforce use of open standards (e.g., 3GPP MCX, ETSI EMTTEL, CAP) - Promote common technical frameworks
Fund resilience by design	- Establish targeted funds for infrastructure hardening, redundancy, and inclusive preparedness initiatives
Strengthen oversight and compliance	- Empower agencies to certify/employ ethical and secure crisis tools - Introduce resilience audits for critical operators

5.2. For civil protection authorities and first responders

Frontline actors—such as emergency services and civil protection agencies—require systems and protocols that are reliable, redundant, and designed for real-world contingencies. Communication networks should be diversified to include broadband (5G), device-to-device, satellite, LPWAN, and even analogue channels, ensuring operability under partial or complete digital failure. Cross-border cooperation must be institutionalised through regular joint exercises that employ shared operating procedures and interoperable languages, ideally in simulation environments that involve both citizens and private-sector partners.

Ethical principles must be at the core of operational protocols. The delivery of alerts and the execution of interventions should uphold human dignity, proportionality, and non-discrimination. Communication platforms must also be designed with accessibility in mind—providing multilingual, offline-capable, and disability-friendly interfaces that reach all segments of the population, including those with limited digital access.

Table 5 Summary of recommendations for first responders

Objective	Recommended actions
Guarantee robust emergency communications	- Deploy multi-tiered systems (5G, D2D, LPWAN, satellite, analog) for redundancy

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Promote joint preparedness	- Organise cross-border simulations with SOP harmonisation - Include civilians and private actors in drills
Embed ethical principles in operations	- Integrate human rights, non-discrimination, and proportionality in alert and response protocols
Enhance accessibility	- Develop multilingual, offline-capable platforms - Design systems usable by people with disabilities and low digital literacy

5.3. For infrastructure operators and private sector stakeholders

Private actors responsible for lifeline services—such as energy, water, transport, and telecommunications—must embed resilience into the technical and organisational design of their systems. Infrastructure should be modular, with clear fallback mechanisms, including manual overrides and decentralised communication capabilities to mitigate cascading failures. Collaboration with public authorities is essential in the joint development of threat models and risk scenarios, including cyber-physical simulations and stress-testing of systemic interdependencies.

Beyond infrastructure, private companies have a role to play in citizen engagement. This can take the form of co-organising community preparedness events, integrating awareness messaging into existing customer interactions (e.g., utility bills), or co-financing resilient digital infrastructure at the local level. Transparency must also be enhanced through real-time information sharing, public-facing dashboards, and structured incident reporting protocols to build public trust during disruptions.

Table 6 Summary of recommendations for private sector stakeholders

Objective	Recommended actions
Build resilience into system design	- Integrate fallback modes (manual overrides, decentralised control) into infrastructure architecture
Engage in shared risk modelling	- Co-create cyber-physical risk scenarios with public authorities - Map interdependencies and simulate cascading failures
Partner with communities	- Support awareness campaigns and preparedness drills - Use everyday interactions (e.g., energy bills) for resilience messaging
Ensure transparency in crises	- Implement live dashboards and incident logs - Establish clear public communication and accountability protocols

5.4. For research and innovation Institutions

The research and innovation community are critical in developing the tools, knowledge, and governance frameworks that underpin long-term resilience. A key priority is the development of explainable, human-in-the-loop AI systems that support decision-making without compromising transparency or accountability. Such tools must be tailored to the needs of emergency responders and operate reliably under real-world constraints. In addition, innovations must be co-designed with

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end users from the outset. Testbeds, living labs, and participatory design processes involving citizens, responders, and municipal officials ensure that technological solutions are contextually relevant, usable, and trusted. Equally important is the translation of research outputs into policy-relevant formats—such as standards, operational guidelines, and timing-aligned policy briefs—so that scientific insights can be integrated into institutional planning cycles. Lastly, all new tools and systems should be benchmarked through comparative trials conducted under simulated crisis conditions, allowing evidence-based decisions around procurement, certification, and deployment.

Table 7 Summary of recommendations for research and innovation institutions

Objective	Recommended actions
Prioritise ethical and usable AI	- Develop explainable, human-in-the-loop decision tools suitable for emergency contexts
Co-design with stakeholders	- Use living labs, participatory design, and testbeds to involve end users (responders, citizens, local authorities)
Translate science into policy	- Produce timely policy briefs, standards, and operational guidelines based on project outputs
Test and benchmark innovations	- Run comparative trials of novel technologies (e.g., UAV relays, quantum-secure links) under simulated crisis conditions

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6. Conclusion

Deliverable D2.1, "Gap analysis and best practices for emergency communications and critical infrastructure preparedness under digital breakdowns," marks a pivotal milestone in the SPARROW project. This report has meticulously dissected the complex landscape of critical infrastructure resilience and emergency communication, particularly in an era defined by increasing digital interdependencies and evolving threat vectors. By synthesising extensive literature reviews, international survey inputs, in-depth stakeholder interviews, and analyses of real-world pilot use cases, this deliverable has successfully mapped current systems, illuminated systemic vulnerabilities, identified operational best practices, and laid a robust foundation for the co-design of the SPARROW architecture.

The comprehensive gap analysis has unequivocally highlighted that whilst individual entities often possess commendable localised backup and continuity measures (e.g., generators, redundant data centres, BCPs), significant vulnerabilities persist at the systemic level. A recurring theme across all stakeholder perspectives is the profound impact of cascading effects – where a localised digital or power disruption can trigger widespread failures across interconnected critical sectors like energy, healthcare, transport, and communications. This interconnectedness, whilst offering efficiency in normal operations, becomes a critical fragility during crises, often exacerbated by poorly mapped hidden dependencies on third-party services, APIs, and digital certificates. The interviews particularly underscored the operational disconnects that can arise when theoretical crisis governance plans meet the complex reality of a large-scale digital collapse, revealing a critical need for more robust, real-time, and adaptive response mechanisms.

Furthermore, the analysis revealed a pressing need for enhanced interoperability across disparate emergency communication systems and between various critical infrastructure operators, both nationally and transnationally. The current reliance on low-tech fallbacks (e.g., manual traffic management, pen-and-paper decision trees) in the absence of digital connectivity, whilst necessary, underscores the limitations of existing digital solutions in truly resilient crisis management. Regulatory constraints, coupled with human and political obstacles, can further impede seamless coordination and information sharing, even when the technical solutions might exist. A notable gap identified is the scarcity of simulation tools capable of anticipating and modelling the effects of complex digital incidents, which currently hinders proactive planning and strategic decision-making.

Despite these challenges, the deliverable also celebrates existing strengths and best practices that SPARROW can build upon. Many critical entities are proactively investing in power redundancy, network resilience, and formalising Business Continuity Plans. The progressive adoption of alternative communication systems, such as satellite terminals and dedicated radio frequencies, demonstrates a clear recognition of the need for independent communication channels. The willingness of stakeholders, exemplified by EENA and the City of Leuven, to actively engage, contribute to testing, and share insights, provides a fertile ground for the co-design and successful deployment of the SPARROW system.

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The "cross-cutting elements" identified in this report are paramount for the SPARROW project's success. They emphasise that resilience is not merely a technical problem but a multifaceted challenge requiring a holistic, integrated approach. The future SPARROW architecture must therefore be designed with inherent resilience in mind, ensuring its own operational continuity even under adverse conditions. It must prioritise secure, real-time, and multi-modal information exchange, providing advanced situational awareness and robust decision support that is intuitive and accessible to a diverse range of users, from first responders to municipal authorities. The insights strongly advocate for human-in-the-loop AI systems that support decision-making without compromising transparency or accountability, tailored to the unique needs of emergency responders and operating reliably under real-world constraints.

In this context, the following strategic recommendations synthesise the core lessons drawn from SPARROW's analytical work and stakeholder engagement.

Summary of the strategic recommendations: Based on the cross-analysis conducted in this deliverable, the SPARROW project outlines the following strategic directions to strengthen the digital resilience of emergency communications and critical infrastructures:

- First, there is a need to strengthen integrated governance frameworks. This involves promoting coordinated, multi-level governance models that clarify responsibilities, support intersectoral cooperation, and align legal frameworks with operational realities. Second, digital risk must be embedded into all preparedness planning. This requires moving beyond sector-specific scenarios by integrating digital disruptions into continuity plans and crisis exercises, with particular attention to cascading effects and network interdependencies.
- Third, it is essential to reinforce local and territorial capacities. Municipalities and operators should be equipped with technical guidance, simulation tools, and training tailored to their available resources. Recognising the critical role of local actors in adapting resilience strategies to real-world conditions is key to operational effectiveness.
- Fourth, redundancy and fallback systems must be expanded. Ensuring access to alternative communication, energy, and data management solutions can help maintain continuity during digital outages. Analog tools and degraded-mode protocols should be fully integrated into crisis planning.
- Fifth, stronger public-private and intersectoral cooperation is needed to facilitate structured collaboration between authorities, infrastructure operators, technology providers, and civil society. This will help improve situational awareness and enable faster, more coordinated response efforts.
- Finally, knowledge-sharing and innovation must be supported through the development of open, accessible platforms that allow feedback, lessons learned, and best practices to be exchanged across territories. In parallel, the design of user-centred technologies and decision-support tools should be encouraged to enhance crisis management capabilities.

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Together, these recommendations offer a strategic foundation for building more robust, anticipatory, and inclusive resilience systems that can help communities and infrastructures better withstand the increasing complexity of digital crises.

Looking ahead, the findings of D2.1 will directly inform the subsequent work packages of the SPARROW project, particularly the technical design and development phases. The project must focus on:

- Developing and integrating robust, interoperable communication solutions that bridge existing gaps and align with relevant European and international standards.
- Designing intuitive and secure platforms for real-time information sharing and collaborative decision-making.
- Exploring and implementing advanced simulation and modelling tools to enhance preparedness and training.
- Ensuring compliance with critical EU legislation such as NIS2, CER, and GDPR, explicitly mapping system requirements to regulatory provisions.
- Prioritising continuous stakeholder engagement and co-design to ensure the developed solutions are contextually relevant, usable, and trusted by end-users.
- Implementing rigorous testing and benchmarking under simulated crisis conditions to validate effectiveness and inform future procurement and deployment decisions.

In conclusion, Deliverable D2.1 provides a comprehensive and actionable roadmap for the SPARROW project. By systematically addressing the identified gaps and leveraging existing best practices, SPARROW is uniquely positioned to deliver significant European added value. The project's success will not only enhance the preparedness and resilience of critical infrastructures and emergency services across the Union but also contribute fundamentally to a more secure, coordinated, and resilient Europe in the face of an increasingly complex and unpredictable threat landscape. The insights gathered are a testament to the collaborative spirit necessary to tackle such grand societal challenges.

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7. Appendices

7.1. Complete List of Theme-based References

Theme – Critical communications

Label	Reference
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Theme – Critical infrastructure

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7.2. SPARROW Questionnaire (T2.1)

SPARROW Emergency Communication Tools Evaluation Questionnaire

Dear Sir or Madam,

Thank you very much for participating in the Emergency Communication Tools and Best Practices survey. The SPARROW project (Solid Preparedness and Resilience for Robust Operations during disaster Wilderness) is a project funded by the European Union (Horizon Europe). The project aims to deliver a pioneering solution for enhancing societal resilience and crisis management in the face of digital breakdowns by developing a collaborative platform that improves crisis communication, closes gaps in digital emergency preparedness and contributes to a safe and resilient European way of life.

This survey evaluates various aspects of emergency communication tools, systems, and channels based on their usability, performance, and long-term impact. Completion of the survey will take about

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10 minutes of your time. As we value protecting the data you provide, we will ensure the security of your data in accordance with the following privacy policy.

GDPR compliance

Adhering to European General Protection Regulation (GDPR no. 2016/679), data collection and analysis in this survey will be used for scientific purposes only and will be treated in an aggregated form. No personal identifying information will be disclosed at any point of this study. Data will be stored securely on [Specify storage location, e.g., EU-based secure servers], accessible only to authorized research team members. Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary, and you have the right to withdraw at any time without providing a reason or consequences.

If you choose to drop out before completing the survey, your responses will not be analyzed or included in the study. If you request withdrawal after submitting the survey, we will delete your data upon request, provided it has not already been anonymized or aggregated into the research findings.

Your contribution will give us valuable insights into how emergency response organizations in Europe are currently practically handling crisis communication. For any questions or to request data deletion, please contact [Insert Contact Email].

- Demographics
- Institution: _____
- Profession: _____
- Role in your organisation: _____
- Years of experience in Emergency Management: _____
- Age: _____
- Education: _____
- Gender: _____
- Citizenship: _____

Current Tools and Usage frequency during latest crisis

Please state the last major incident (e.g. flood, pandemic, terrorist attack or similar) in which crisis communication tools were used by your organisation.

Incident: _____

Second, please indicate how often and for what purpose each tool was used during this incident.

Third, please indicate whether you think the instrument is relevant in crisis communication during digital breakdowns.

Finally, please rank the individual tools according to their relevance in crisis communication from your point of view.

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II.I Emergency Communication Tools

Tool	Frequency of use						Relevant for Crisis Communication (CC) during digital breakdowns	Rank	Usability and Performance Using UMUX Scale
	Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Less frequent	Never	Not Applicable			
Crowdsourcing Platforms							y/n		
Social media							y/n		
SMS/text messaging							y/n		
Mobile Apps							y/n		
Websites							y/n		
Chatbots							y/n		
Other Tools:							y/n		

Usability Metric for User Experience (UMUX)
(Finstad, 2010).

Please rate the emergency communication tools used by your organisation in terms of their usability and performance in the context of crisis communication on a scale from 7 (strongly agree) to 1 (strongly disagree).

	Strongly agree	Agree	Somewhat agree	Either agree or disagree	Somewhat disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
The tool's performance significantly reduces the time needed to communicate vital information during crises.	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
This tool's capabilities meet my requirements.	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
This tool is easy to use.	7	6	5	4	3	2	1

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Using this tool is a frustrating experience.	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
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II.II Emergency Communication Systems

System	Frequency of use						Relevant for CC during digital breakdowns	Rank	Usability and Performance Using UMUX Scale
	Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Less frequent	Never	Not Applicable			
Drones							y/n		
Internet of Things (IoT)							y/n		
Mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs, DTNs)							y/n		
Delay Tolerant Networks (DTNs)							y/n		
Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs)							y/n		
Next-Generation Networks (Never Die Network (NDN), Aerial Networks (AMS) etc.)							y/n		
Other Systems:							y/n		

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	Strongly agree	Agree	Somewhat agree	Either agree or disagree	Somewhat disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
The tool's performance significantly reduces the time needed to communicate vital information during crises.	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
This system's capabilities meet my requirements.	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
This system is easy to use.	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
Using this system is a frustrating experience.	7	6	5	4	3	2	1

II.III Emergency Communication Channels

Channel	Frequency of use						Relevant for CC during digital breakdowns	Rank	Usability and Performance Using UMUX Scale
	Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Less frequent	Never	Not Applicable			
Satellite communication Technologies							y/n		
Cellular Technologies (5G, LTE and LTE-A, 4G LTE, TETRA etc.)							y/n		
Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN) Technologie (WLAN):							y/n		
Ad-hoc Networks							y/n		

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Low-Power Wide-Area Networks (LPWAN)							y/n		
Terrestrial Wireless Technologies (y/n		
Device-to-Device (D2D) communications							y/n		
Other channels:									

	Strongly agree	Agree	Somewhat agree	Either agree or disagree	Somewhat disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
The tool's performance significantly reduces the time needed to communicate vital information during crises.	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
This technology's capabilities meet my requirements.	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
This technology is easy to use.	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
Using this technology is a frustrating experience.	7	6	5	4	3	2	1

Are there any tools/systems/channels that are not currently available to you, but which you consider useful for crisis management?

(Open ended)

In your opinion, which tools/systems/channels are the most essential for crisis communication during digital breakdowns?

(Open ended)

In what ways do you think that these tools/systems/channels will contribute to overcoming crisis communication challenges during digital breakdowns?

(Open ended)

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As part of the project, it is planned to explore the results of this survey in more depth at a later stage through online interviews or online focus groups. We would be delighted if you would support our project by actively participating in one of the above-mentioned formats (online interview or online focus group). Financial compensation will be granted for further participation in these planned surveys.

If you are interested in participating in a follow-up interview or focus group, please provide your email below. Participants Thank you very much!

Email: _____

Thank you for participating! Your feedback is invaluable to improving emergency communication.

If you have any questions about this survey, please contact [email/phone of the responsible team].

7.2.1. Survey results

Reported incidents: Participants were asked to identify the most recent major incident in which their institution used emergency communication systems, channels, or tools. The responses were diverse and covered a wide range of crisis types as per indicated in Figure 33. After normalization and categorization, the most frequently reported incident types were:

Figure 33 Incident Type

Floods and pandemics were the most cited incidents, reflecting the widespread impact of these events and the critical role of communication systems in managing them.

Scope of deployment: Participants also indicated the geographical scope of their institution's deployment during the reported incident (see Figure 34).

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Figure 34 Geographical scope of the institution's deployment during the reported incident

This distribution illustrates the variety of operational contexts in which participants applied emergency communication systems.

Most deployments occurred at the local and regional levels, underscoring the importance of localized emergency response capabilities. However, a significant number of participants also reported involvement in national and international operations, suggesting cross-border collaboration and broader crisis management responsibilities.

Emergency Communication Systems

Concerning emergency communication systems, starting from its usage, participants were asked to indicate which advanced communication systems they used during their most recent emergency incident (see Figure 35). The results revealed varied adoption of technologies, with some being used more frequently than others.

Figure 35 Emergency Communication Systems used during the most recent emergency incident

Drones were the most frequently reported system, underscoring their increasing importance in situational awareness and real-time data collection. MANETs and IoT technologies were also used frequently, suggesting a trend toward decentralized, sensor-driven communication infrastructures.

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Participants were asked to mention any other systems used for emergency communication. The presence of multiple "other systems" indicates that institutions are employing customs or unconventional technologies tailored to specific operational needs.

Notable Comments and Technologies - Other systems

Participants were asked to mention any additional systems, channels, or tools used for emergency communication. The questionnaire had three input fields for each category (systems, channels, and tools). Participants could enter one additional system, channel, or tool in each field (see Table 8)

Table 8 Other systems

Other system 1	<p>Radio & Communication Networks: TETRA, HZS Analog Radio Network, BOS digital radio, digital radio BOS Austria, radio equipment</p> <p>Digital Platforms: INSARAG Coordination Management System, MoI Intranet</p> <p>Alerting Systems: SMS alerting, governmental systems</p> <p>Specialized Tools: GI POLIS, sensor-based measurement systems via UMTS</p> <p>Mobile Networks: classic mobile network used</p>
Other system 2	<p>Radio Systems: BOS analog radio, digital radio (TETRA), digital radio HZSMobile & Internet Tools: Internet, mobile phones incl. Zello, mobile phones</p> <p>Specialized Systems: Motorola system, Pegas network technology, VISO</p>
Other system 3	<p>Digital Communication: E-Mail, Web portal of the city of Pilsen + Safe Pilsen</p> <p>Hybrid Networks: Connecting the analogue and digital network of the Fire Brigade</p> <p>Alert Systems</p> <p>Surveillance: Wireless system (camera)</p>

These insights demonstrate that emergency responders depend on a variety of communication tools, including traditional radio, digital platforms, mobile networks, and customized systems, to maintain communication during crises.

Frequency of System Use During Incidents

Participants rated how frequently they used each system during the most recent incident on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = never; 2 = less frequently; 3 = monthly; 4 = weekly; 5 = daily). The results are shown in Table 9.

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Table 9 Frequency of system use during incidents

System Type	M (Mean Frequency)	SD (Standard deviation)
Other system 2	4.91	0.30
Other system 1	4.73	0.88
Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs)	4.67	0.82
Mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs)	4.64	0.79
Internet of Things (IoT)	4.62	0.77
Delay Tolerant Networks (DTNs)	4.33	1.16
Drones	4.27	1.12
Other system 3	4.25	1.50
Next-Generation Networks (NDN, AMS)	4.00	1.41

Relevance of Systems in Emergency Communication

Participants were asked to rank the systems they used based on their perceived relevance to emergency communication. Other System 1 (e.g., analog/digital radio and TETRA) was most frequently ranked first, indicating its central role in emergency communication. Drones and MANETs were also commonly ranked in the top three, reflecting their growing operational importance. IoT systems were consistently ranked in the top three but less frequently as the top choice. Next-generation networks and DTNs appeared in lower ranks, suggesting that they are still emerging or are used in more specialized contexts. Overall, this ranking distribution highlights a hybrid landscape in which traditional systems and modern technologies are both valued depending on the operational context and deployment maturity.

Usability and Performance of Emergency Communication Systems

Participants rated the usability and performance of each system using the UMUX scale, which was then normalized to a range of 0–100. Table 10 summarizes the results.

Table 10 Usability and performance of Emergency communication systems

System	M	SD
Other System 2	69.70	10.88
Other System 1	66.12	17.74
Other System 3	58.33	5.89
MANETs	44.77	32.34
Drones	33.07	31.70
IoT	28.95	31.18
WSNs	20.00	29.08

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NDN/AMS	18.75	27.61
DTNs	12.81	23.31

Other systems involving mobile phones and traditional radio were rated the most usable and performant. DTNs, NDN/AMS, and WSNs received the lowest usability scores, likely due to limited familiarity or technical complexity. There was high variability in usability ratings for drones, suggesting mixed experiences among users.

Interim Conclusion: Emergency Communication Systems

The survey results, which focus on emergency communication systems, provide a comprehensive overview of how these systems are perceived and utilized across diverse organizations and incident types. Several key insights emerge:

System usage and adoption

- Traditional systems (e.g., TETRA, analog/digital radio, and mobile phones) are the most frequently used and are highly rated for their usability and relevance.
- Modern technologies, such as drones, MANETs, and the IoT, are being adopted more frequently, with drones being the most frequently used advanced system.
- Emerging systems such as DTNs, WSNs, and next-generation networks demonstrate limited adoption and mixed usability, suggesting both potential and barriers to operational integration.

Frequency and Relevance of respective systems

- Most of the systems used during incidents were employed daily, particularly traditional and mobile-based systems.
- Rankings confirm the central role of traditional systems, while drones and MANETs are gaining recognition for their operational value.

System Usability and Performance

- Other System 2 category (e.g., mobile phones and Motorola systems) achieved the highest usability scores, followed by the Other System 1 and Other System 3 categories. DTNs and NDN/AMS scored the lowest in usability, suggesting the need for better integration, training, or system refinement.

Key Performance Indicators – Emergency Communication Systems

Table 11 shows the derived key performance indicators (KPIs) based on the emergency communication systems results.

Table 11 Key Performance Indicators – Emergency communication Systems

KPI	Definition	Current Benchmark
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System Usage Rate	% of respondents using a system during incidents	Drones: 41.8%, MANETs: 34.3%, Other system 1 (mainly: 32.8%, IoT: 22.4%
Frequency of Use	Mean frequencies of usage	Other systems 2: M=4.91, Other system 1: M=4.73, WSNs: M=4.67
Top Relevance Ranking	Most relevant systems ranked	Other System, Drones, MANETs
Average Usability Score	Mean UMUX score (0–100)	Highest: Other System 2 (69.7), Lowest: DTNs (12.8)

This interim analysis underscores the ongoing importance of reliable and well-integrated communication systems, as well as the expanding role of advanced technologies in emergency response. The analysis also emphasizes the need for usability improvements and training to encourage the adoption of new systems.

Emergency Communication Channels

This section presents the usage statistics of various emergency communication channels as reported by survey participants during a specific incident.

Emergency Communication Channel Usage

Figure 36 depicts the emergency communication channels used by participants during their last incident.

Figure 36 Distribution of communication channel types by percentage.

As shown in Figure 36, cellular technologies (e.g., 5G, LTE, and TETRA) were by far the most used channels, as reported by 52 respondents. Wireless LAN (WLAN) and satellite communication

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technologies followed with 22 and 18 users, respectively. Fourteen respondents used device-to-device (D2D) communication, indicating its growing relevance in field operations. Ad-hoc networks and terrestrial wireless technologies had limited but notable use. Low-power wide-area networks (LPWAN) and other channels 2 and 3 were not reported.

These results underscore the importance of robust, high-availability mobile and wireless infrastructure in emergency scenarios while highlighting the limited operational integration of newer or more specialized technologies.

Frequency of Channel Use During Incidents

Table 12 Frequency of Channel Use During Incidents

Channel Type	M	SD
Wireless Local Area Network Technologie (WLAN)	4.95	0.21
Terrestrial Wireless Technologies	4.89	0.33
Cellular Technologies (5G, LTE and LTE-A, 4G LTE, TETRA etc.)	4.87	0.56
Device-to-Device (D2D) communications	4.64	0.84
Ad-hoc Networks	4.57	0.54
Satellite Communication Technologies	4.06	1.35
Other channel: Short wave	3.00	-
Low-Power Wide-Area Networks (LPWAN)	-	-

Although all examined systems showed frequent usage, these results confirm that WLAN-based, terrestrial wireless, and cellular technologies (5G, LTE, LTE-A, 4G LTE, TETRA, etc.) are the backbone of emergency communication due to their consistent usage (see Table 12). D2D and ad hoc networks also exhibited significant usage, albeit with slightly higher variability. Satellite communication had the lowest average usage and the highest variability, suggesting that it is used more selectively or under specific conditions. Low-power systems, such as shortwave, seem to be underutilized.

This breakdown highlights the dominance of cellular and WLAN technologies in daily emergency operations while showing that satellite and ad hoc solutions serve more specialized or backup roles.

Relevance of Channels in Emergency Communication

Cellular technologies are clearly the most relevant communication channel in emergency situations. WLAN and D2D communications are also valued, particularly for supporting roles. Satellite and terrestrial wireless technologies are considered important, albeit secondary, likely due to their situational use. Ad-hoc networks and other channels are considered less central but still relevant in specific contexts.

Usability and Performance of Emergency Communication Channels

Table 13 Usability and performance of Emergency Communication Channels

Channel	M	SD
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Terrestrial Wireless Technologies	73.15	3.03
Device-to-Device (D2D)	71.15	14.38
Cellular Technologies	69.75	8.45
WLAN	67.66	9.49
Satellite Communication	66.18	14.50
Ad-hoc Networks	62.50	12.73
Other channel: Short wave	41.67	0.00

As shown in Table 13, terrestrial wireless technologies and D2D communication are the most usable and high-performing channels. Cellular and WLAN technologies also perform well, further establishing their pivotal role in emergency communication. Satellite and ad hoc networks demonstrate greater variability, suggesting that they may be more context-dependent or require specialized training. Shortwave technology, as another channel for emergency communication, had only one rating and scored significantly lower.

Interim Conclusion: Emergency Communication Channels

Analysing emergency communication channels reveals a clear preference for reliable, high-availability technologies that support real-time coordination and information exchange. The findings underscore the dominance of cellular and WLAN-based systems, as well as the growing importance of device-to-device and terrestrial wireless solutions.

- *Channel Usage and Adoption:* Cellular technologies, such as LTE and TETRA, were used by 77.6% of respondents, making them the most widely adopted channel. Following that were WLAN (32.8%) and satellite communication (26.9%), with D2D communication (20.9%) and terrestrial wireless (13.4%) also showing notable use.
- *Frequency of respective Channels:* Most users frequently use WLAN, terrestrial wireless, and cellular technologies daily. Satellite communication, on the other hand, showed a broader distribution, indicating its use in more specialized or backup scenarios.
- *Perceived Relevance of Channels:* Cellular technologies were overwhelmingly ranked as the most relevant channel. WLAN, D2D, and satellite communication were also frequently ranked in the top three.
- *Channel Usability and Performance:* Terrestrial wireless and D2D communication received the highest usability scores (73.1 and 71.2, respectively). Cellular and WLAN technologies also scored highly, reinforcing their operational reliability. Satellite and ad hoc networks had more variable usability, suggesting context-specific challenges.

Key Performance Indicators – Emergency Communication Systems

Table 12 highlights the derived KPI's regarding emergency communication channels.

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Table 12 Key Performance Indicators – Emergency Communication Systems

KPI	Definition	Current Benchmark
Channel Usage Rate	% of respondents using a channel during incidents	Cellular: 77.6%, WLAN: 32.8%, Satellite: 26.9%
Frequency of Use	Mean frequencies of usage	Wireless Local Area Network Technologie (WLAN): M=4.95, Terrestrial Wireless Technologies: M=4.89, Cellular Technologies: M=4.87
Top Relevance Ranking	Most relevant systems ranked	Cellular, Satellite, and D2D Technologies
Average Usability Score	Mean UMUX score (0–100)	Highest: Terrestrial (73.1), Lowest: Channel 7 (41.7)

This interim conclusion emphasizes the crucial role of cellular and WLAN technologies in emergency communication. It also acknowledges the increasing significance of D2D and terrestrial wireless solutions. Additionally, it emphasizes the necessity of ongoing investment in the usability and integration of satellite and ad hoc systems.

Emergency Communication Tools

This section presents the usage statistics for various emergency communication tools as reported by survey participants during a specific incident.

Emergency communication tools usage

The assessed tools include traditional and digital platforms such as social media, SMS, mobile apps, websites, chatbots, and others (see Figure 37).

Figure 37 Emergency Communication Tools used during the most recent emergency incident

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The most frequently used tools were social media (e.g., Facebook, X, local and national media) and SMS/text messaging (e.g., WhatsApp, national messenger services), followed closely by mobile apps and websites (see Table 15). Crowdsourcing platforms, chatbots (e.g., ChatGPT), and other tools (see Other tool 1: e.g., a multi-channel downlink alerting and information application for cellphones, intranets, media, press conferences, and SARCALL) were used by only one respondent each (1.5%).

Frequency of tools used during incidents

Table 13 Frequency of Tools Use During Incidents

Tool Type	M	SD
Mobile Apps	5.00	0.00
Chatbots	5.00	-
Websites	4.60	1.00
Social media	4.51	0.99
Other Tool 1	4.50	0.84
SMS/Text Messaging	4.44	1.08
Crowdsourcing Platforms	4.00	-
Other Tool 2: Town hall meetings	3.00	-
Other Tool 3	-	-

As shown in Table 13, the highest average usage was among mobile apps, chatbots, and websites, at or close to 5. Other tools, such as the multi-channel downlink alerting and information application, cell phone, intranet, media, press conferences, and SARCALL, as well as social media and SMS/text messaging, also scored high. Other Tool 2 had the lowest mean usage.

Relevance of tools in emergency communication

Social media and text messaging were the most frequently ranked tools, taking the top two spots (Ranks 1 and 2). Mobile apps received strong support for ranks two and three. Websites were more commonly ranked in the middle (Ranks 3 and 4). Other tools (e.g., Tools 1 and 2) appeared occasionally, suggesting niche or context-specific relevance. Crowdsourcing platforms and chatbots were rarely ranked, suggesting a lower perceived importance.

Usability and performance of emergency communication tools

Table 14 lists the participants' usability and performance ratings of emergency communication tools.

Table 14 Usability and Performance of Emergency Communication Tools

Tool	M	SD
Other Tool 1	77.08	10.78

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Mobile Apps	70.31	8.18
SMS/Text Messaging	69.24	11.24
Social media	63.85	15.50
Chatbots	62.50	-
Websites	61.29	17.12
Crowdsourcing Platforms	50.00	-
Other Tool 2: Town hall meetings	-	-
Other Tool 3	-	-

Tool 1, mobile apps, and SMS/text messaging received the highest average usability scores, indicating strong performance and user satisfaction. Social media, chatbots, and websites performed moderately well. There was limited data on crowdsourcing platforms, but they showed average usability.

Interim conclusion: Emergency communication tools

The survey results provide a comprehensive view of how respondents use, perceive, and evaluate various emergency communication tools. The findings highlight the strengths and limitations of the tools in real-world emergency contexts.

- **Tool Adoption and Usage:** Mobile apps, SMS/text messaging, and social media are the most widely used tools during emergencies. Websites are also used frequently, though less so than mobile apps, SMS/text messaging, and social media. Crowdsourcing platforms, chatbots, and "other tools" are used less frequently, often in niche or specialized contexts.
- **Frequency of Use:** All respondents who used mobile apps and chatbots used them daily. Social media and SMS were also used frequently. Websites had a high daily usage rate but showed more variability.
- **Perceived Relevance:** Social media and text messaging were the most frequently ranked tools for communicating with the public in an emergency. Mobile apps were often ranked second or third, indicating a strong, though slightly less critical, perceived importance.
- **Websites** were consistently ranked in the middle. Crowdsourcing platforms and other tools were rarely ranked highly.
- **Usability and Performance:** Tool 1, mobile apps, and SMS/text messaging received the highest usability scores, indicating strong user satisfaction. Social media, websites, and chatbots performed moderately well. There was limited data on crowdsourcing platforms.

Key Performance Indicators – Emergency Communication Tools

Table 15 highlights the KPI's regarding emergency communication tools.

Table 15 Key Performance Indicators – Emergency Communication Tools

KPI	Definition	Current Benchmark
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101168499.

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Tool Usage Rate	% of respondents using a tool during incidents	Social media: 56.7%, SMS/text Messaging: 53.7%, Mobile Apps: 49.3%
Frequency of Use	Mean frequencies of usage	Mobile Apps: M=5.00, Chatbots: M=5.00, Websites: M=4.60
Top Relevance Ranking	Most relevant systems ranked	Social media, SMS
Average Usability Score	Mean UMUX score (0–100)	Highest: Tool 1 (77.08), Lowest: Crowdsourcing Platforms (50.0)

The results show that social media, SMS, and mobile apps are the most widely used and relevant tools in emergencies, valued for their reach and reliability. Tools with high usability, like SMS and mobile apps, are more likely to be trusted and used under pressure. While newer tools like chatbots show potential, their adoption remains limited. Overall, the most effective tools are those that combine accessibility, simplicity, and consistent performance.

Additional systems/channels/tools

Next, participants were asked to suggest additional systems, channels, and tools that were not currently available to their organization but that they considered useful for crisis management.

A total of 20 suggestions were made across four system/channel/tool slots. The first slot received most mentions (14 out of 20), indicating that most respondents had at least one additional tool in mind. The subsequent slots (2-4) received fewer responses, suggesting that respondents had fewer secondary suggestions.

Respondents added the following systems, channels, and tools:

- AI
- Bodycam stream
- Own (organizational) app for communication and alerting for volunteers and emergency personnel Organization's emergency services
- IT alerting system, currently not fully functional
- Complete networking of crisis management authorities and IRS units on one platform
- Mesh radio/networks
- Employee app with communication option
- Radio network access for more effective communication with IRS units
- Reverse SMS system
- Satellite Internet connection
- STARLINK
- STARLINK or its alternative

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- Analog radio as backup, too much focus on digital radio
- App-based alerting tool
- Amplification of analogue radio signal at the scene
- Pager
- Amplification of mobile radio networks at the scene
- Operations management software for integrated operations management with communication option

Suggestions include technological innovations, such as AI, Starlink, and mesh networks, as well as infrastructure improvements, such as analog radio as a backup, pagers, and radio network access for more effective communication with IRS units. Several tools focus on redundancy and resilience, such as satellite internet connections, reverse SMS systems, and mobile network reinforcement.

Emergency Communication during digital breakdowns

The last section of the questionnaire focused on emergency communication during digital breakdowns. Participants were asked to select the systems, channels, and tools that they thought might be relevant for emergency communication during digital breakdowns, as well as how these systems, channels, and tools could help overcome challenges in crisis communication.

Emergency Communication Systems for Digital Breakdowns

The systems listed in Figure 38 had the highest number of valid responses, indicating that they were considered the most relevant for emergency communication during digital breakdowns. “Further” systems 1-3 are additional emergency communication systems that participants listed if they were not already included above. “Other” systems 1-3 were presented in Chapter 4.3.1.

Figure 38 Emergency Communication Systems for Digital Breakdowns

The following systems received no valid responses, suggesting that the participants did not consider them relevant:

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- Delay-Tolerant Networks (DTNs)
- Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs)
- Next-Generation Networks (NDN, AMS, etc.).

Participants added the systems highlighted in Table 16 that they perceived as relevant for crisis communication during a digital breakdown.

Table 16 Perceived relevance for crisis communication in case of digital breakdown

System	Comments
Further system 1	Analogue infrastructure Digital/analog radio network Comprehensive analog radio coverage as a backup, analog fixed network supply for guards Radios Ladder-based ad hoc networks Local radio broadcasts Municipal radio powered from an external source Contacting the help of amateur radio in the Czech Republic Network-independent or self-sufficient analog and digital radio Information transmission with the help of patrols of the Municipal Police Satellite internet connection Siren System TETRA comms
Further system 2	Own network which can be operated independently Local sound systems (sirens, messengers, etc.) Telephone
Further system 3	Detector with pen and pad and bag as well as vehicle/bicycle/motorcycle etc...

These results suggest that participants valued resilient, low-tech, and decentralized systems. There was a clear preference for analog backups and community-based communication methods. Emerging technologies, such as DTNs, WSNs, and NDNs, may require clearer communication of their benefits or more practical use cases to become more relevant. Additionally, participants were asked to explain how their chosen systems would contribute to overcoming challenges in crisis communication. Table 17 shows all comments regarding the respective system.

Table 17 Comments regarding respective system

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System	Comments
Drones	<p>Alternative communication method</p> <p>Image acquisition independent of external networks</p> <p>Monitoring</p> <p>real time info widely shared</p> <p>Visibility of multiple information, freedom from obstructions and signal throughput. Drones can have multiple controllers - one controller at HQ, one at the pilot</p>
Internet of Things	<p>Look up and research current information, access to online data storage, email communication and live working systems</p>
Mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs)	<p>Flexible tool in remote areas</p> <p>Enables access to the network and accelerates the exchange of information from the affected area</p> <p>Connection speed</p> <p>Connecting via mobile phones</p> <p>Independent networks that can build a parallel structure</p>
Other System 1	<p>Due to overlapping with RF, communication should also be ensured, for example in the event of prolonged power outages</p> <p>Change to paper forms and f2f meeting</p> <p>Easy communication</p> <p>Only currently available and comprehensive communication option in the event of time pressure and possible Internet outages</p> <p>Independent system</p> <p>Local communication is maintained</p> <p>Independent system</p> <p>Protected system not dependent on external networks - only requires a specific power supply</p> <p>Reliable backbone for all responders</p> <p>Connection with KOPIS, Intervention Commander</p>
Other System 2	<p>Analogue communication system</p> <p>Functioning fallback level if devices are still available in the area</p> <p>Easy, fast and efficient information of the citizen</p> <p>Connection with KOPIS, Intervention Commander, IRS components</p>
Other System 3	<p>Verbal information, back-up system</p>

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Participants emphasized the need for resilient, independent, and user-friendly communication systems in the event of a digital breakdown. They valued tools like drones and MANETs for their flexibility and real-time capabilities. They also saw analog systems, such as radio networks, sirens, and face-to-face communication, reliable fallbacks.

Even low-tech methods, such as pen-and-paper reporting and loudspeakers, were considered essential, underscoring the importance of redundancy and local control. Ultimately, effective crisis communication relies less on advanced technology and more on accessibility, simplicity, and human-centred solutions.

Emergency Communication Channels for Digital Breakdowns

Figure 39 summarizes the responses from the participants regarding the perceived relevance of various communication channels in crisis scenarios during digital breakdowns.

Figure 39 Emergency Communication Channels for Digital Breakdowns

Cellular technologies were identified as the most relevant due to their widespread availability and effectiveness in crisis scenarios. Satellite communications were also highly valued for their independence from terrestrial infrastructure. Device-to-device (D2D) and ad hoc networks were recognized for their potential in localized, infrastructure-independent communication. Terrestrial wireless technologies, shortwave technology, and especially LPWAN were rarely considered relevant by most participants.

The participants were again asked to add any emergency communication channels they perceived as relevant for crisis communication during a digital breakdown. In total, eight additional channels were mentioned, as depicted in Table 21 .

Table 21 Additional channels

Channel	Comments
Further channel 1	SMS via emergency-powered cell towers

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	Digital/analog radio networks Local radio broadcasts Alerting devices (e.g., pagers or sirens)
Further channel 2	Predefined routines for employees (distributed in advance)
Further channel 3	Amateur radio (Ham radio)

Respondents emphasized the importance of redundant, low-tech, and analog systems as critical backups. Radio-based communication, both public and amateur, was highlighted for its reliability and independence from digital infrastructure. They also considered predefined routines essential for maintaining communication continuity.

Emergency Communication Tools for Digital Breakdowns

The final section evaluates the perceived relevance of various digital and analog tools for emergency communication in the event of a digital breakdown. Figure 40 shows the participants' ratings of the relevance of predefined tools.

Figure 40 Emergency Communication Tools for Digital Breakdowns

SMS/text messaging was the most frequently selected tool. It is valued for its directness, reliability, and broad accessibility, even during internet service disruptions. Mobile apps were also considered useful, especially those designed for offline use or point-to-point communication. Although social media is vulnerable to digital disruption, it is still considered vital for mass communication and public awareness. Websites and other tools (see Other Tool 1 and Other Tool 2) were selected less frequently, likely due to their dependence on stable internet access. Chatbots received no selections, suggesting limited perceived utility in crisis scenarios.

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Participants were asked again to explain how their selected tools contribute to overcoming challenges in crisis communication. Table 18 shows all comments regarding the respective tools.

Table 18 Comments regarding respective tools

System	Comments
SMS/Text Messaging	Seen as resilient and potentially functional longer than internet-based tools. Targeted and mass communication. Vulnerable to digital disruption
Mobile Apps	Information from mobile applications can be sent via an external transmitter and receiver to another device (point to point) Communication, video sharing Offers alternative routes to comms Traditional map
Social Media	Public awareness and information dissemination. Vulnerable to digital disruption but vital channels of communication
Websites	Useful for information retrieval, but highly dependent on digital infrastructure.
Crowdsourcing Platforms	Self-hosted organizational app (for internal coordination)
Other Tools (Tool 7 & 8)	Emphasized traditional media like radio stations and media outlets. Seen as reliable, familiar, and resilient in crises.

The participants suggested additional tools, one of which was the radio, a frequently trusted tool. Other tools suggested were sirens and warning systems for immediate, nonverbal alerts; loudspeaker announcements for localized communication; and bulletin boards/reporting points, which can be useful for community-level coordination. The results show that participants value redundant, analog, and community-based tools. Evidently, there is a strong preference for low-tech solutions that are independent of digital infrastructure.

Final Summary and Discussion

Diverse and Evolving Communication Landscape

The survey reveals an intricate and ever-changing landscape of emergency communication systems, channels, and tools. Although traditional technologies like analogue/digital radio, SMS, and mobile phones continue to be essential to emergency communication, modern technologies such as drones, mobile apps, MANETs, and the IoT are increasingly being integrated. These newer systems are valued

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for their flexibility, autonomy, and real-time capabilities, particularly in dynamic or infrastructure-compromised environments.

Usability and Reliability Drive Adoption

Across all categories, usability and reliability were key drivers of adoption. Intuitive, robust, infrastructure-independent systems and tools, such as TETRA, SMS, and mobile apps, received the highest usability scores and were the most frequently used. In contrast, emerging technologies such as DTNs, NDNs, and crowdsourcing platforms demonstrated low adoption and usability. This suggests the need for better integration, training, or clearer operational use cases.

Cellular and WLAN Technologies Dominate Channels

Cellular technologies, such as LTE and TETRA, were the most widely used and highly rated communication channels. WLAN and D2D communication followed closely behind. These channels are considered essential for real-time coordination, broad accessibility, and resilience. However, while less frequently used, satellite and ad-hoc networks are recognized for their strategic value in specific or backup scenarios.

Tools Must Balance Reach and Redundancy

Of all the tools, SMS, social media, and mobile apps were the most frequently used and considered the most relevant. SMS stood out for its resilience and reach, even in environments with low connectivity. Despite its vulnerability to digital disruption, social media was praised for raising public awareness. Mobile apps demonstrated high usage frequency and usability, suggesting significant potential when integrated into emergency protocols.

Digital Breakdown Scenarios Highlight Need for Redundancy

When asked about communication during digital breakdowns, participants emphasized low-tech, analogue, and community-based solutions. They considered tools such as amateur radio, sirens, loudspeakers, and predefined routines essential for maintaining communication continuity. This reflects an understanding that redundancy and decentralization are critical in crisis scenarios where digital infrastructure may fail.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) Confirm Trends

The derived KPIs reinforce the reported findings:

- Usage rates were highest for cellular systems, SMS, and social media.
- Frequency of use was highest for WLAN, mobile apps, and terrestrial wireless technologies.
- Top relevance rankings consistently favoured traditional and hybrid systems.
- Usability scores were highest for analogue/digital radio systems, mobile apps, and SMS.

The SPARROW survey highlights the importance of a hybrid communication strategy blending modern digital tools and proven analogue systems. Although innovation is important, resilience, usability, and accessibility are the foundation of effective emergency communication. Future efforts should focus on:

- Enhancing the usability of emerging technologies.

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- Training and preparedness for low-tech fallback systems.
- Integrating tools into cohesive, multi-layered communication frameworks.

This approach will ensure that emergency responders can maintain communication under any circumstances, especially when it matters most.

7.3. Stakeholders Interview agenda (T2.2)

- Total Duration: 45 minutes
- Format: Videoconference
- Objective: To gather feedback on the resilience of critical infrastructure in the face of digital disruptions.

Introduction (5 minutes)

- Welcome and thank the interviewee for their time
- Brief overview of the SPARROW project and the aim of the interview
- Clarify that the interview is confidential and anonymized unless the interviewee agrees otherwise
- Recap of the structure and duration of the interview
- Ask for consent to record or take notes

Ensuring Continuity of Critical Services During Digital Disruptions (10 minutes)

- Can you describe major digital disruptions your organization/ city/ clients have faced (e.g., cyberattacks, system outages)?
- What protocols or plans are in place to ensure service continuity during such events?
- Which services do you consider critical in your context?
- What challenges have you encountered, and what best practices have emerged?

Role of Emerging Technologies in Strengthening Resilience (10 minutes)

- Are you using or considering emerging technologies to enhance resilience?
- How do these technologies help mitigate risks or improve response times?
- What are the benefits or limitations you've observed in practice?

Cascading Effects of Infrastructure Failures (10 minutes)

- Have you experienced cascading impacts (e.g., one failure triggering others across systems)?
- How did you detect and manage these interdependencies?
- What strategies are in place to prevent or respond to such chain reactions?

Lessons Learned and Preparedness (5 minutes)

- What key lessons has your organization learned from past crises?
- Have those lessons led to lasting changes in policy, infrastructure, or coordination?
- What would you recommend to others facing similar challenges?

Closing (5 minutes)

- Recap of key points shared

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- Ask if the interviewee has any final comments or questions
- Thank the interviewee again for their contribution

7.4. Pilot use case descriptions as from project proposal

Pilot Use Case 1: Flash floods leading to digital breakdown

Motivation: The motivation behind Pilot Use Case 1 (PUC1) in Cyprus is to prepare for hazards leading to digital breakdown. Cyprus is suffering from the consequences of climate change, manifesting as severe rain events leading to flash flooding (e.g. flash floods of 2018). REACT's mission as an NGO focuses on citizen well-being with emphasis on public and personal safety, thus being interested in deploying resources from its over 4500 members for support during crisis situations.

Objective: The primary objective of PUC1 is to enhance the training and preparedness of various civil protection organizations, fostering the island's resilience against climate events leading to digital breakdown. Here we consider an extreme rain event over the capital city of island, Nicosia*, causing flash flooding that leads to:

i) a power outage to several CIs and residences.

ii) a communications failure amongst the dispatched FR teams; and

iii) a failure in the (government's) citizen alerting platform because of i) and ii). The rainwater overwhelms the old town region, where hundreds of locals and tourists become stranded, while the overall road network becomes severely congested. The objectives therefore of the pilot are to augment the existing preparedness and response mechanisms during digital breakdown, focusing on alternative communications amongst teams of FRs and amongst citizens and crisis managers, and dynamic management of assets and responding teams as the situation unfolds. These objectives align with SPAR-R0W's objectives of improved resilience against digital breakdowns crises. The following figures show the impacted area and some of the available response vehicles.

Implementation: The implementation of PUC3 in Cyprus involves the use of several SPARROW technologies. Initially, an extensive visualization of the disaster-hit area will be created through CITWIN, leveraging the collected data (T3.1), including 3D representations of structures in the area, CI locations (e.g., power grid and high-voltage transformer locations, telecommunication towers and lines, water network, hospitals, etc), available assets and their status including personnel (e.g. ambulances, fire-trucks, response units, etc), and novel tools of SPARROW. A detailed scenario will be created through CESER capturing all aspects, such as threats, timing of critical events, citizen responses, cascade effects on interdependent infrastructures, and updated information on the vulnerability of infra-structures (based on VASE), to enable trainees to develop mitigation responses. SPARROW also intends to deploy ECOMAPP, enabling the communication of citizens and FRs. This imparts a dynamic nature to the scenario evolution, as the citizen self-reported status, informed by SSH-developed questionnaires, can alter the responders' priorities. DYCAMARE will also facilitate this process through appropriate response action recommendations. In parallel, the deployment of SPARROW's alternative communication tools (EMER5G, SEDs, EMPEER), will enable citizens to

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communicate amongst themselves and with authorities, supplying the necessary dynamic data to CESER. The PUC will run through multiple scenarios, evaluating each time the trainees' responses and increasing their prepared-ness for digital breakdown situations, while also enhancing their decision-making skills under stressful conditions.

KPIs: Improve deployment time for alternative communication systems by 25%; Measure the reliability of communication transmission using peer-to-peer communications; Ensure public awareness during crisis by providing alter-native communication means; Response time improvement to citizens under duress and vulnerable groups; Successful testing of dynamic solutions for FRs.

[*The change of the Pilot location from Larnaca to Nicosia was made in consultation with the relevant state authorities of the Republic of Cyprus, as well as with the affected municipalities. Certain scheduled projects in the city of Larnaca could potentially interfere with specific aspects of the exercise. At the same time, according to the competent authorities, organizing the exercise/pilot in the capital city will facilitate greater participation of first responders.]

Pilot Use Case 2: Traffic control failure scenario

Motivation: The motivation behind Pilot Use Case 2 (PUC2) in the city of Pilsen, Czechia, lies in addressing the critical scenario of traffic control failure during a digital breakdown. Recent instances of traffic light failures in Pilsen highlight the vulnerability of the current traffic control system. In the event of a digital breakdown, the collapse of city traffic poses significant challenges, demanding an immediate alternative to regulate traffic flow. The priority given to FRs also needs enhancement to ensure efficient access routes in such scenarios.

Objective: The primary objective of Pilot Use Case 2 (PUC2) in Pilsen is to assess and enhance the city's resilience against traffic control failure during a digital breakdown. In the face of a breakdown scenario where traditional traffic control mechanisms are compromised, the goal is to implement and evaluate a set of innovative technologies and methodologies. The objective is twofold: i) To develop and implement alternative traffic control strategies in Pilsen to address the immediate aftermath of a digital breakdown. SPARROW will focus on integrating the alternative traffic control measures into SPARROW's Digital Twin platform, providing a realistic 3D representation of the city's traffic infrastructure; ii) To enhance the priority given to FRs' access routes, ensuring a swift and unimpeded response to emergency situations by utilising SPARROW's emergency communication system, including the self-powered ruggedized mobile 5G Network, to prioritise and streamline communication for FRs. In essence SPARROW targets at validating the effectiveness of these measures in a real-world scenario, considering the unique challenges posed by a digital breakdown. By aligning the implementation with SPARROW's tools, the aim is to bolster the city's preparedness, response, and recovery capabilities in the face of disruptions to traditional traffic control systems. This PUC serves as a critical step toward establishing best practices and refining strategies for resilient urban infrastructure management in the context of digital breakdowns. The following figures show the initial setup of the platform in the city of Pilsen.

Implementation: Several SPARROW technologies and systems will be tested in this scenario, including:

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the utilization of *traffic control panels and TraMod* for real-time traffic control and modelling. The use of traffic control panels and TraMod will relate to SPARROW's Digital Twin platform and integrate real-time data from these sources, providing a comprehensive 3D representation of the city's traffic infrastructure.

ii) the deployment of *drones* for the transmission of live images from the stage, enabling comprehensive monitoring and assessment. IN essence, SPARROW drones will transmit live images from the scene, contributing to real-time monitoring during the crisis. The streaming data will be integrated into the SPARROW platform for analysis and decision-making.

iii) The leveraging of the *LoRa* data network to enable efficient data transmission and communication; the integration of the *Warning Information System (VIS)* for real-time alerts and information dissemination to the public. The LoRa data network will be utilized for efficient data transmission, including communication between devices and sensors deployed during the scenario. SPARROW's emergency communication system, especially the self-powered ruggedized mobile 5G Network, will complement the LoRa network, ensuring continuous communication capabilities.

iv) The utilisation of *GIS data* for accurate mapping of infrastructure locations and effective crisis management. The Warning Information System (VIS) and GIS data will play a crucial role in disseminating real-time alerts and map-ping CI locations, respectively.

v) The implementation of the *SITRAFFIC Scala 1.8* system by Siemens for advanced traffic control, which will contribute to advanced traffic control and monitoring. The insights from SITRAFFIC Scala 1.8 will be incorporated into the Digital Twin, enabling stakeholders to assess traffic flow and make informed decisions during the crisis.

vi) The utilisation of the *test polygon* for autonomous mobility in Bory near the FRs' location, enhancing the understanding of autonomous vehicle integration in crisis scenarios. Insights from the autonomous mobility test will contribute to SPARROW's understanding of the dynamics of autonomous vehicles in crisis situations, potentially influencing emergency response strategies

KPIs: Reduce by 25% the time taken to establish an alternative traffic control system after the onset of a digital breakdown; Improve by 50% the effectiveness of the enhanced priority for FRs' access routes during the crisis; In-crease by 40% the ability of the implemented systems to manage and regulate traffic flow during the simulated scenario; Measure the reliability of data transmission, especially through drones and the LoRa data network. Improve the effectiveness of the Warning Information System (VIS) by ensuring public awareness and safety during the traffic control failure.

Pilot Use Case 3: Smart Crisis Preparedness and Response in Trikala

Motivation: The Pilot Use Case 3 (PUC3) in Trikala, Greece, is motivated by the city's role as a digital and smart city flagship, showcasing a commitment to technological innovation and sustainable urban development. Trikala's smart city initiatives, spanning automated vehicles, electromobility, and AI cybersecurity tools, position it as a front-runner city in the European Union's Mission for '100 Climate Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030.' The motivation behind PUC3 is to leverage Trikala's advanced smart infrastructure to enhance crisis prevention and preparedness during large-scale events, such as the annual 'Mill of Elves' thematic park attracting a significant influx of visitors. The city's

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commitment to climate neutrality, citizen well-being, and cutting-edge technology forms the backdrop for testing innovative solutions in the context of urban resilience.

Objective: The primary objective of PUC3 in Trikala is to assess and augment crisis prevention and preparedness mechanisms during large events, focusing on real-time management, alternative communication systems, and dynamic solutions for FRs. Specific objectives include Real-time Management for Large Events: To develop and test real-time management strategies for planning, organizing, and monitoring during large events, with a focus on the 'Mill of Elves' thematic park. As well as to integrate crisis prevention and preparedness features into the Municipal platform 'Trikala check app' to enable residents to send requests directly to the Municipal Authority. Alternative Communication Systems: To prepare and deploy alternative communication systems that can be rapidly activated, targeting FRs and citizens, as well as to prioritize vulnerable citizens, such as those in digital houses with elderly citizens of special needs, by ensuring emergency call-for-help services are readily available. Dynamic Matrix of Solutions for FRs: To create a dynamic matrix of solutions applicable for testing by FRs, supported by visualization means, to avoid rapid panic movements.

Implementation: The implementation of Pilot Use Case 3 (PUC3) in Trikala aligns with the SPARROW project's objective of enhancing crisis prevention and preparedness using advanced technologies. Leveraging Trikala's existing smart city infrastructure, the implementation focuses on integrating available data and aligning with SPARROW tools. Key aspects include Integration of Smart Infrastructure: such as Autonomous Buses and Intelligent Signs, Smart Parking and Environmental Monitoring, as well as GIS Data Platform. More specifically, SPARROW will integrate data from autonomous buses and intelligent signs into the SPARROW platform by utilising real-time location data, traffic conditions, and bus schedules for enhanced situational awareness during crisis events. The platform will also incorporate data from smart parking systems and environmental monitoring sensors by including information on parking availability, air quality, and other environmental parameters, providing valuable insights for crisis management. The system will finally utilise Geographic Information System (GIS) data for mapping infrastructure locations, allowing SPARROW to create a comprehensive spatial representation of the city, including critical assets such as power grids, telecommunications, and transportation networks. Citizen Engagement Platforms: SPARROW also intends to enhance the functionality of the 'Trikala check app' by integrating it with SPARROW's emergency communication system, and ECOMAPP to enable residents to report incidents, request assistance, and receive real-time updates during crisis situations. The platform will also integrate data from sensors deployed in the city, including those used for behaviour tracking, security management, and suspicious activity detection. Align these data streams with SPARROW's analytical tools to improve crisis response capabilities. Testing and Visualization Tools: SPARROW also intends to develop a dynamic matrix of solutions for FRs within the SPARROW platform by integrating testing and visualisation tools that will allow responders to simulate and assess various crisis scenarios, optimising their response strategies. ETrik will also leverage SPARROW's AI-friendly environment to analyse municipal digital data by Integrating AI operations for real-time decision-making during crisis events, addressing cybersecurity challenges by design, ensuring the secure operation of digital infrastructure and AI processes. Data Networks: ETrik will utilise fibre optics network, WiFi spots, and the 5G network for seamless data connectivity and ensure the integration of these networks with

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SPARROW's communication system to maintain uninterrupted data flow, especially during digital breakdown. The PUC will also explore the integration of the LoRa network to enhance SPARROW's capabilities in collecting and transmitting data from various sensors distributed throughout the city.

KPIs: Response time improvement during large events; Increase the number of requests and communications through the 'Trikala check app.' by 50% ; Improve deployment time for alternative communication systems by 25%; Increase 2 times the effectiveness in prioritizing and responding to vulnerable citizens; Successful testing of dynamic solutions for FRs. Reduction in panic movements during crisis events.

7.5. Privacy Policy for the Online Survey in T.2.1, SPARROW project

The controller responsible for the processing of your personal data in connection with this survey is Johanniter Österreich Ausbildung und Forschung gem. GmbH (JOAFG). The registered address of JOAFG is Johanniter Österreich Ausbildung und Forschung gem. GmbH, Ignaz-Köck-Str. 22, 1210 Vienna, Austria. The company registration number is 389613k, HG Wien.

Thank you for answering this survey conducted for the Horizon Europe project SPARROW (“solid preparedness and resilience for robust operations during disaster wilderness”). This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101168499. SPARROW aims to deliver a pioneering solution for enhancing societal resilience and crisis management in the face of digital breakdowns. Your answers will contribute to gain a better understanding for (communication) tools used for crisis management, especially during a digital breakdown. Answering the survey will take approximately 10 minutes of your valuable time.

Processing of data

All data collected during the survey will be treated confidentially and will only be viewed or processed by the project-involved employees of Johanniter Österreich Ausbildung und Forschung gem. GmbH (JOAFG). Information that could lead to an identification of the person will be changed or removed. The following categories of personal data may be collected during this survey: age, gender, level of education, country, institution/organization, role. All survey responses will either be fully anonymized or pseudonymized. If pseudonymization is used, only authorized personnel will have access to re-identifiable data, and all identifiers will be removed before data analysis. No automated decision-making or profiling will take place. The results will be further processed in the form of a report and possibly further scientific publications.

Voluntary nature of participation

Participation in this survey is voluntary. Participants may withdraw at any time without giving reasons and without incurring any disadvantages. If you choose to withdraw from the survey, your responses will be deleted. For this purpose, a personal code will be generated by asking specific questions (which will also help you to restore the code later). In case of withdrawal please contact: forschung@johanniter.at.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101168499.

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Confidentiality and anonymity

Your information will be used solely by researchers for research purposes in the context of the above research project. Survey data will be stored on secure servers located in Vienna, Austria. Data is encrypted in transit and at rest. Only authorized personnel will have access to raw survey data.

Personal information will not be shared with anyone outside the research team of this project, except under the following circumstances:

1. If required by law or legal process, we may disclose your personal data to comply with legal obligations.
2. If necessary to protect the rights, property, or safety of our organization, our participants, or others, we may share your data with relevant authorities.

The tool “Lime Survey” will be used to conduct the survey, hosted on premise at the server of Johanniter Österreich Ausbildung und Forschung gem. GmbH (JOAFG) in Austria, Vienna. This means that data are not transferred or stored outside of this server. The published research results (publications, research reports) have no personal reference and therefore do not allow any conclusions to be drawn about your identity. Data processes in lime survey will be in accordance with the privacy policy which can be reviewed via this link: <https://www.limesurvey.org/privacy-notice>

Data protection

The data will be processed based on your consent for the purpose of carrying out the above-mentioned research project (collection, evaluation, generation of results, publications). The legal basis for this is the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), namely in particular Art 6(1)(a) (consent) and Art 9(2)(j) (research purposes in the public interest) in conjunction with the Austrian Research Organization Act (FOG). Your personal contact data (name, address, telephone number, e-mail address, job title) will be stored - if applicable - for up to 10 years after the end of the project period (i.e. until 31.12.2032) and then deleted. The collected questionnaire ("raw data") will be kept for 10 years from the date of publication of the results of the project to demonstrate compliance with good scientific practice and then destroyed. Data required for the assertion, exercise and defence of legal claims will be stored for up to 30 years and subsequently deleted. You have the right to information, correction, deletion, restriction of processing, data portability, objection, and a right of appeal to the data protection authority at any time in accordance with legal provisions (in particular Art 15 to 22 DSGVO with the restrictions in § 2d paragraph 6 FOG).

The data will also be processed to demonstrate compliance with good scientific practice. The legal basis for this is Article 6(1)(e) GDPR (public task). This processing is necessary for performing a task carried out in the public interest, namely, retaining data for scientific research purposes to demonstrate compliance with good scientific practice. Furthermore, the data will be processed for the assertion, exercise, and defence of legal claims. The legal basis for this is Article 6(1)(f) GDPR (legitimate interests). This processing is necessary to protect the controller's legal rights, and such interest is not overridden by the interests or rights of the data subjects.

To exercise your data rights under GDPR (access, correction, deletion), please contact our Data Protection Officer at datenschutzbeauftragter@johanniter.at

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Consent

I consent to the processing of my personal data and the information provided during the survey - for the purpose of my participation in the SPARROW research project as described above. The consent is voluntary. I can revoke my consent at any time with effect for the future, whereby the lawfulness of the processing carried out based on the consent until revocation is not affected. A revocation has the consequence that my data will no longer be processed for the above-mentioned purposes from that point on. I hereby confirm that I have read and understood this declaration of consent.

7.6. Interview Consent Form

Project Name:	SPARROW (Solid Preparedness and Resilience for Robust Operations during Disaster Wilderness)
Event Name:	SPARROW Interview
Organizer name:	European forum for urban security
Event location:	Online
Event Type:	Interview
Participant Name:	
Participant Organization: (if applicable)	
	I have been provided with information about the project and my rights as a participant.
	<p>I understand that the SPARROW project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The SPARROW project aims to improve preparedness and resilience during emergencies, especially digital breakdowns. • Focus groups and workshops are part of the research to identify needs, best practices, and gaps. • My input will be used for the research and development purposes of SPARROW, including but not limited to tools and frameworks for crisis communication and emergency response.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In relation to SPARROW research activities: • agree to take part in the present focus group or workshop as a participant and complete all the exercises that aim to understand the end user's needs and objectives, which will be linked to the SPARROW research and development activities. • I agree that my personal data which is gathered during and as the result of my participation in this task will be:

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• collected and retained for the purpose of this project research and development activities, and• accessed and analyzed by the SPARROW Consortium researchers to achieve project research objectives.
	<p>I acknowledge that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• My participation is voluntary, and I am free to withdraw from participation at any time without explanation.• My anonymity is guaranteed, and I will not be identified in publications or otherwise without my express written consent.• I am aware of the legal ground on which the processing of my personal data is based, namely consent as per Art. 6 (1) (a) GDPR.1• I am aware that I might withdraw my consent for the processing of my personal data, without affecting the lawfulness of the processing prior to the withdrawal of consent.• I am aware that I have the following rights as a data subject, which I can exercise with the controller:<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The right to access.• The right to rectification.• The right to erasure.• The right to restriction of processing.• The right to be informed about recipients after a request for rectification,• erasure or restriction of processing.• The right to data portability.• The right to object.• The right not to be subjected to automated individual decision-making, including profiling.• To file a complaint with my national Data Protection Authority.• I have been informed of the procedure on how to exercise these rights with the controller, namely: sending an e-mail to SPARROW@netlaw.bg• I am aware of the purposes for which my data is gathered and processed in project SPARROW research activities.

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • My data will be protected and kept safe throughout this project and accessed and analyzed by SPARROW consortium researchers to implement the project. • My data will be stored for the duration of the project and kept for 5 years after the final payment of Grant Agreement 101168499.
By signing this document, I agree to:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • participate in the Interview under the terms set out above • the processing of my data.
Date:	
Signature:	

If you would like to make a complaint about any part of the event, please do so by contacting any of the people below:

Project Coordinator:	<p>Christos Laoudias (UCY) laoudias.christos@ucy.ac.cy</p> <p>Mathaios Panteli (UCY) panteli.mathaios@ucy.ac.cy</p>
You should contact the Data Protection Officer if: To exercise your rights listed above You have a query about how your data is used by the organizer; You would like to report a data security breach (e.g. if you think your personal data has been lost or disclosed inappropriately); You would like to complain about how the organizer has used your personal data.	<p>Kristina Isakzay (Law and Internet Foundation) kristina.isakzay@netlaw.bg SPARROW@netlaw.bg</p>
You should contact the Ethical advisor of SPARROW if you have concerns about how the research was undertaken or how you were treated by the research team.	<p>Kristina Isakzay (Law and Internet Foundation) kristina.isakzay@netlaw.bg SPARROW@netlaw.bg</p>